

Depend (/ able / ing on / on) • nissayati, avalambati, nissita, avassita / avassayitabba / nissāya, upādāya, paticca / upajivati, anujivati

Interdepend (ence / ent) • aññamaññāvalambana / aññamaññāvalambī

Dependent origination • paṭicca samuppāda

Dependently originated phenomena • paṭicca samuppannā dhammā

Cause (/ less / lessly / way) • kāraṇa; niḍāna; ṭhāna. hetu; paccaya. janeti; uppādeti; kārāpeti; ussukkāpeti, janita; uppādita; kārita; ussukkāpeti. / ahetuka; heturahita; appatiṭṭha / ahetukam; appatiṭṭham / ussāpita-magga, padikavedikā

Causing (/ attachment / disunion / injury / remorse) • samuṭṭhāpaka / ratikara; madaniya / bhedakara / veyyābādhika / upatāpaka

Causat (ion / ive / tive verb) • hetuvāda; janakatta; phaluppādana / hetubhūta; samuppādaka; (in grammar :) hevatthaka / hetvatthakriyā

Causal (/ ity / ly) • hetusambhūta; paccayāyatta / sahetukatā / hetusoṭhānaso

∅ and then, the river flowed, and flowed, and flowed . . .

∅ thus acknowledging, neither accepting nor rejecting, in the stillness of awareness, the way things are, AS IT IS i.e yathābhūta . . .

∅ like walking on the edge of a razor sharp blade, of a sword . . .

∅ cultivate insight or vipassanā / vipaśyanā (in Pali / BSk. Buddhist Sanskrit)

A somewhat consolidated analysis/synthesis, interwoven with the teachings of the Buddha in Pali and a recently published scientific experiment by (clinical) psychologist(s) dealing with issues of well-being, mindfulness and nonattachment via evaluation of Buddhist psychology, apropos interconnectedness, along with some enquires that the readers of this work, might want to ask or ponder upon . . .

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Ode to . . .

—
**O Beloved Master, the absolute truth . . . Shunyata,
my Beloved Teacher Sakhyamuni Buddha,
my Beloved Trainer Jetsun Milarepa,
my Beloved Mother Nature . . .
what am i, without you . . . ?
Just a figment of imagination!**
—

No ce kira taṃ, vakkali, attā sīlato upavadati; atha kiñca te kukkucçaṃ ko ca vippaṭṭisāro”ti?

”In that case, Vakkali, why do you have remorse and regret?”

”Cīrapaṭṭikāhaṃ, bhante, bhagavantaṃ dassanāya upasaṅkamtukāmo, natthi ca me kāyasmim
tāvaticā balamattā, yāvatahaṃ bhagavantaṃ dassanāya upasaṅkameyyan”ti.

”For a long time I’ve wanted to go and see the Buddha, but I was physically too weak.”

Alaṃ, vakkali, kiṃ te iminā pūtikāyena diṭṭhena? Yo kho, vakkali, dhammaṃ passati
so maṃ passati; yo maṃ passati so dhammaṃ passati. Dhammañhi, vakkali, passanto
maṃ passati; maṃ passanto dhammaṃ passati

”Enough, Vakkali! Why would you want to see this rotten body? One who sees the
teaching sees me. One who sees me sees the teaching. Seeing the teaching, you see
me. Seeing me, you see the teaching”

– SAMYUTTA NIKĀYA 22.87, 9 THERAVAGGA, VAKKALISUTTA¹

Abstract

Atthi, bhikkhave, ajātaṃ abhūtaṃ akataṃ asaṅkhatāṃ, no cetaṃ, bhikkhave, abhaviṣṣa ajātaṃ
abhūtaṃ akataṃ asaṅkhatāṃ. Nayidha jātaṃ bhūtaṃ katassa saṅkhatassa nissaraṇaṃ paññāyetha.
Yasmā ca kho, bhikkhave, atthi ajātaṃ abhūtaṃ akataṃ asaṅkhatāṃ, tasmā jātaṃ bhūtaṃ katassa
saṅkhatassa nissaraṇaṃ paññāyati”ti.

**There is an unborn, unoriginated, uncreated, and unformed . . . If there was not this
unborn, this unoriginated, this uncreated, this unformed . . . Freedom from the world of the
born, the originated, the created, the formed, would not be possible . . . But since there is an
unborn, unoriginated, uncreated, and unformed . . . Therefore is freedom possible from the
world, of the born, the originated, the created and the formed!**

– NETTI, PAṬINIDDESAVĀRA, VIBHAṄGA 11, PAÑÑATTIHĀRAVIBHAṄGA

yo paṭiccasamuppādaṃ passati so dhammaṃ passati; yo dhammaṃ passati so paṭiccasamuppādaṃ
passatīti.

**One who sees dependent origination sees the teaching. One who sees the teaching sees
dependent origination.**

– MAJJHIMA NIKĀYA 28, MAHĀHATTHIPADOPAMASUTTA, THE LONGER SIMILE OF THE
ELEPHANT’S FOOTPRINT

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In this context, in my limited grasp, after a few meditation periods and reading through a few material, i endeavour to share some insights regarding the teachings of the Buddha, apropos the words **depend** and **interdepend**. Succinctly, here, i

- 1 begin with the bottom-up approach, where, first the root words are presented from the available dictionaries
 - 2 then based on the teachings of the Buddha in Pali language, whatever limited was grasped, i have presented an exposition, that is . . .
 - 3 interweaved with, what i have read regarding . . .
- 3.a ⊕ a scientific experiment, titled - **Promotion of well-being by raising the awareness on the interdependent nature of all matters: Development and validation of the interconnectedness scale**, by **Ben C. L. Yu** (PhD in Psychology), **Winnie W. S. MAK** (with clinical training fellowship, Ph.D. in Clinical Psychology and postdoctoral training in clinical services research) and **Floria H. N. Chio** (Phd in Psychology), all of whom specialize in dealing with research regarding stigma reduction, psychological distress, mental health promotion via technologies, and application of Buddhist psychology for individual/collective well-being. Their study in Yu et al. (2020), aims to develop and validate the Interconnectedness Scale based on Buddha's teachings on interconnectedness and examines the relationship of interconnectedness with various indicators of well-being, mindfulness, and nonattachment. Further, their study aimed to examine the incremental value of interconnectedness in accounting for well-being above and beyond the effects of mindfulness and nonattachment. And lastly . . .
- 3.b ⊕ a response/counter article with correction, in Buddhist teachings on interconnectedness, titled - **Dependent Arising and Interdependence**, by the Theravādin school trained and ordained **Bhikkhu Anālayo**, of Amarapura-Rāmañña Nikāya sect, now a retired professor of the Numata Centre for Buddhist Studies at the University of Hamburg. In his article Anālayo (2021b), with correction in Anālayo (2021a), the author talks about dependent arising or dependent origination of the Buddha's teachings and points to the development of the notion of interconnectedness or interdependence, as a perspective of causality, attributed to the later Chinese Huayan Buddhist school, the starting point which is the considered most elevated, extravagant, lengthy scripture, the Flower Ornament Sutra, or Avatamsaka Sutra in Sanskrit (Avatamsaka is translated as Huayan in Chinese, and read as Kegon in Japanese). Futher, the author puts forth his views on the need of foundation of proper research, based on operationalized concepts which are clearly defined to avoid conflation (i.e merging of two or more sets of information, texts, ideas, or opinions into one, often in error), as has been propoorted by Yu et al. (2020), according to Bhikkhu Anālayo's perspective and for this, he provides his insights about the teachings of the Buddha and bolsters up support with a range of references in Buddhist teachings, both historical and present day, incorporating both the Indian Pali and Chinese āgamas.
- 4 Finally, on the way, as and where needed, i put titbits of clarifications, to make the whole research paper, wholesome (Pali - *sappāyabhuta*) to read! Many points might be known, however scattered or might slip from one's awareness. To circumvent this issue, these titbits are provided and further, for the uninitiated, these titbits might reveal some insights about the teachings of the Buddha! These titbits will appear in **blue**. Also, imbued within this work, where needed, are constructs that end with enquires, in **BOLD italic red**, which the readers of this manuscript might also want to ask, *as investigating into the nature of truth, is what was the basis of the Buddha's teachings. Like the enquiry - Is it true?*

In summary, i **endeavour to look at these teaching of the Buddha, from a few limited perspectives of my own and also share my personal insights that might have come to awareness, in meditations! Note again, it not what i have said so! One needs to meditate and over a period of time, as one evolves in the spiritual dimension, one needs to arrive at one's own conclusions via experiential knowledge of what the Buddha said/imparted, some 2600 years back! As a basis for this, in Buddha's own words -**

Yañhi taṃ, bho, sammā vadamāno vadeyya :

If anything should be rightly described as :

'svākkhāto bhagavatā dhammo sandiṭṭhiko akāliko ehipassiko opaneyyiko paccattaṃ vedītabbo viññūhi apārutā amatassa dvārā'ti idameva taṃ sammā vadamāno vadeyya.

'a teaching that's well explained by the Buddha, apparent in the present life, immediately effective, inviting inspection, relevant, so that sensible people can know it for themselves; and the doors to freedom from death are flung open,' it's this.

Svākkhāto hi, bho, bhagavatā dhammo sandiṭṭhiko, akāliko ehipassiko opaneyyiko paccattaṃ vedītabbo viññūhi apārutā amatassa dvārā.

For the teaching is well explained by the Buddha - apparent in the present life, immediately effective, inviting inspection, relevant, so that sensible people can know it for themselves - and the doors to freedom from death are flung open.

– DĪGHA NIKĀYA 18, JANAVASABHASUTTA, SATTASAMĀDHIPARIKKHĀRA (SEVEN PRE-REQUISITES OF IMMERSION)

"Alañhi vo, kālāmā, kaṅkhituṃ alaṃ vicikicchituṃ. Kaṅkhanīyeva pana vo thāne vicikicchā uppannā.

"It is enough, Kālāmas, for you to be doubting and uncertain. Doubt has come up in you about an uncertain matter.

Etha tumhe, kālāmā, mā anussavena, mā paramparāya, mā itikirāya, mā piṭakasampadānena, mā takkahetu, mā nayahetu, mā ākāraparivitakkena, mā diṭṭhijjhānakkhantiyā, mā bhabbarūpatāya, mā samaṇo no garūti.

Please, Kālāmas, **don't go by oral transmission, don't go by lineage, don't go by testament, don't go by canonical authority, don't rely on logic, don't rely on inference, don't go by reasoned train of thought, don't go by the acceptance of a view after deliberation, don't go by the appearance of competence, and don't think 'The ascetic is our respected teacher.'**

Yadā tumhe, kālāmā, attanāva jāneyyātha :

But when you know for yourselves:

'ime dhammā akusalā, ime dhammā sāvajjā, ime dhammā viñ nugarahitā, ime dhammā samattā samādinna ahitāya dukkhāya samvattanti'ti, atha tumhe, kālāmā, pajahēyyātha.

'These things are unskillful, blameworthy, criticized by sensible people, and when you undertake them, they lead to harm and suffering', then you should give them up.

– AṄGUTTARA NIKĀYA 3.65, MAHĀVAGGA, KESAMUTTISUTTA (WITH THE KĀLĀMAS OF KESAMUTTA)

In the end, by the way, i am not a scholar in Pali & Buddhist studies graduate programs and neither do i have research based interest in Pali language! One might find errors in use of spellings that might not be of EXACT precision, as demanded by Pali readers or Phd holders or those who are in academic settings @ the level of professors or otherwise. Having said this, the general context of the spirit of the meaning behind sound frequencies of the used words, should be clear to grasp and errors in the article are due to me. Later corrections of the article are possible, if and when time permits!

Keywords: Depend, Interdepend, Dependent origination, Dependently originated phenomena, Cause, Theravāda, Mahayana, Buddha.

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1 *imasmim sati idam hoti . . . , imasmim asati idam na hoti . . .*

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-

- **Pali** : *'imasmim sati idam hoti, imassuppādā idam uppajjati*, **English** : This being, that becomes; from the arising of this, that arises;
- **Pali** : *imasmim asati idam na hoti, imassa nirodhā idam nirujjhati*. - **English** : this not being, that does not become: from the ceasing of this, that ceases.

1.1 Etymology

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the link to online Pali dictionary at University of Chicago and English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhaddatta (1989), these words -

- **imasmim** - this.
- **Sati** (f.) [Vedic *smṛti*: see etym. under *sarati*2] memory, recognition, consciousness, D i.180; ii.292; Miln 77 - 80; intentness of mind, wakefulness of mind, mindfulness, alertness, lucidity of mind, self - possession, conscience, self - consciousness D i.19; iii.31, 49, 213, 230, 270 sq.; A i.95; Dhs 14; Nd1 7; Tikp 61; VbhA 91; DhsA 121; Miln 37; *upaṭṭhitā sati* presence of mind D iii.252, 282, 287; S ii.231; A ii.6, 218; iii.199; iv.232; It 120; *parimukhaṃ satim upaṭṭhāpetum* to surround oneself with watchfulness of mind M iii.89; Vin i.24, *satim paccupaṭṭhāpetum* to preserve self - possession J i.112; iv.215; *kāyagatā sati* intentness of mind on the body, realization of the impermanency of all things M iii.89; A i.43; S i.188;

Miln 248; 336; mutṭhasati forgetful, careless D iii.252, 282; maraṇasati mindfulness as to death A iv.317 sq.; J iv.216; SnA 54; PvA 61, 66. asati not thinking of, forgetfulness DhSA 241; instr. asatiyā through forgetfulness, without thinking of it, not intentionally Vin ii.2892. sati (sammā°) is one of the constituents of the 8 - fold Ariyan Path (e.g. A iii.141 sq.; VbhA 120): see magga 2.

- **hoti / hotabba / bhavati** - Bhavati [bhū to become, cp. Sk. bhūmi earth; Gr. φ ú σ ι ζ nature (physical), ú o μ α ι to grow; Lat. fui I have been, futurum=future; Oir. buith to be; Ags. būan=Goth. bauan to live, Ger. bauen, also Ags. bȳldan=to build; Lith. būti to be, būtas house DhTP 1: bhū sattāyaṃ] to become, to be, exist, behave etc. (cp. Nd2 474= sambhavati jāyati nibbattati pātu - bhavati). - I. Forms. There are two bases used side by side, viz. bhav° and (contracted) ho°, the latter especially in the (later) Gāthā style and poetry in general, also as archaic in prose, whereas bhav° forms are older. On compounds with prepositions, as regards inflection, see Geiger, P.Gr. §§1312, 1513; and cp. anubhavati, abhibhavati, abhisam°, pa ° (also pahoti, pahūta), pari°, vi °, sam°.- 1. Pres. ind. bhavāmi Sn 511 & homi J iii.260; 2nd bhavasi & hosi M iii.140; Vv 8420; 3rd bhavati freq.; Sn 36 (where Nd2 474 with v. l. BB of Sn reads bhavanti; Divy p. 294 also reads bhavanti snehāḥ as conjecture of Cowell's for MSS. bhavati); Dh 249, 375; & hoti freq.; 1st pl. homa Pv i.118; 2nd hotha J i.307; 3rd bhavanti & honti freq. - imper. 2nd sg. bhava Sn 337, 340, 701; Dh 236; Th 2, 8; bhavāhi Sn 510; hohi Sn 31; M iii.134; J i.32; PvA 89. 3rd sg. hotu Sn 224; J iii.150; PvA 13; Miln 18. pl. 1st med. bhavāmase Th 1, 1128; Sn 32; 2nd pl. bhavatha J ii.218, bhavātha Sn 692; Dh 144; hotha Dh 243; Dh ii.141; J ii.302; DhA i.57; 3rd pl. bhavantu Sn 145; hontu J ii.4. Pot. 1st sg. bhaveyyaṃ J vi.364; 2nd bhaveyyāsi Ud 91; PvA 11; 3rd bhava Sn 716, bhaveyya J ii.159; DhA i.329, & hupeyya Vin i.8 (for huveyya: see Geiger, P.Gr. §396 & 1312); pl. 1st bhaveyyāma; 2nd bhavetha Sn 1073, 3rd bhaveyyuṃ Sn 906. - ppr. bhavaṃ Sn 92, & bhavanto Sn 968; f. hontī PvA 79. - fut. 1st sg. bhavissāmi PvA 49, hessāmi Th 2, 460 (ThA 283 reads bhavissāmi), & hessaṃ Th 1, 1100; J iii.224; Pv i.105; 2nd bhavissasi PvA 16, hohisi Pv i.33; 3rd bhavissati Dh 228, 264; DhA ii.82, hessati J iii.279 & med. hessate Mhvs 25, 97, hehitī Bu ii.10=A i.4; Vv 6332; & hossati (in pahossati fr. pahoti DhA iii.254); 1st pl. bhavissāma Dh 200; 2nd hessatha S iv.179; 3rd bhavissanti freq. - Cond. 1st sg. abhavissaṃ J i.470; 2nd abhavissa J ii.11; iii.30; 3rd abhavissa It 37; Vin i.13; D ii.57; M iii.163; J i.267; ii.112 (na bhavissa=nābhavissa?); 3rd pl. abhavissaṃsu Vin i.13. 1st aor. (orig. pret. of *huvati, cp. hupeyya Pot.; see Geiger P.Gr. 1312, 1622): 1st sg. ahuvā S i.36, with by - form (see aor.) ahuvāsiṃ Vv 826; 2nd ahuvā ibid., 3rd ahuvā Vv 8124; J ii.106; iii.131; 1st pl. ahuvāma M i.93; ii.214, & ahuvamha ibid.; 2nd ahuvattha S iv.112; M i.445; DhA i.57. - 2nd aor. (simple aor., with pret. endings): 1st sg. ahuṃ Pv ii.32 (v. l. BB ahu) (=ahosiṃ PvA 83); 2nd ahu (sk. abhūḥ) Pv ii.35; 3rd ahū (Sk. abhūt) Sn 139, 312, 504 and passim; Pv i.23, & ahu Pv i.93; i.113; & bhavi DhA i.329 (pātubhavi); 1st pl. ahumhā (Sk. abhūma) Pv i.116, & ahumha J i.362; DhA i.57. - 3rd aor. (s aor.) 1st sg. ahosiṃ Th 1, 620; J i.106; VvA 321; PvA 10 (=āsīṃ); 2nd ahosi J i.107; 3rd ahosi Sn 835; Vin i.23; 1st pl. ahesumha M i.265; 3rd ahesuṃ D ii.5; Vv 744; J i.149; DhA i.327; & bhaviṃsu (Sk. abhāviṣuḥ) DhA iv.15. - Of medial forms we mention the 1st pl. pres. bhavāmahe Mhvs i.65, and the 3rd sg. pret. ahuvattha VvA 103. - Inf. bhavituṃ Sn 552, & hetuye Bu ii.10. - ger. bhavitvā Sn 56, hutvā Sn 43, & hutvāna Sn 281. - grd. bhavitabba J i.440; vi.368; hotabba Vin i.46; bhabba (Sk. bhavya); see sep.; bhuyya see cpd. abhibhuyya.

- Caus. bhāveti see sep. - pp. bhūta. Note. In compn with nouns or adjectives the final vowel of these is changed into ī, as in combn of the same with the root kṛ, e. g. bhasmībhavati to be reduced to ashes, cp. bhasmī - karaṇa s. v. bhasma, etc. - II. Meanings. In general the meaning "to become, to get" prevails, but many shades of it are possible according to context & combinations. It is impossible & unnecessary to enumerate all shades of meaning, only a few idiomatic uses may be pointed out. - 1. to happen, to occur, to befall J vi.368. - 2. The fut. bhavissati "is certainly," "must be" DhA iii.171 (sātthikā desanā bh.); Miln 40 (mātā ti pi na bh.). - 3. Imper. hotu as adv. "very well" Miln 18 (hotu bhante very well, sir). - 4. aor. in meaning and as substitute of āsim, pret. of as to be; etad ahoṣi this occurred to him DhA i.399 (assā etad ahoṣi "this thought struck her").

- **Uppāda**¹ [Sk. utpāta, ud + pat] flying up, jump; a sudden & unusual event, portent, omen D i.9 (v. l. uppāta) = Vism 30 (T. uppāta, v. l. uppāda) Sn 360; J i.374; vi. 475; Miln 178.
- **Uppāda**² [Sk. utpāda, ud + pad] coming into existence, appearance, birth Vin i.185; D i.185; S iii.39 (+ vaya); iv.14; v.30; A i.152 (+ vaya), 286, 296; ii.248 (taṇh°); iii.123 (citt° state of consciousness); iv.65 (id.); Dh 182, 194; J i.59, 107 (sat°); Vbh 303 (citt°), 375 (taṇh°); PvA 10; ThA 282. - anuppāda either "not coming into existence" D iii.270, M i.60; A i.286, 296; ii.214, 249; iii.84 sq.; Ps i.59, 66; Dhs 1367; or "not ripe" D i.12.
- **Uppajjati** [ud + pajjati of pad] to come out, to arise, to be produced, to be born or reborn, to come into existence D i.180; Sn 584; Pv ii.111 (= nibbattati PvA 71); PvA 8 (nibbattati +), 9, 20, 129 (= pātubhavati); DA i.165. - Pass. uppajjīyati Vin i.50. - ppr. uppajjanto PvA 5, 21; fut. °pajjissati PvA 5 (bhummadevesu, corresp. with niraye nibbattissati ibid.), 67 (niraye); aor. uppajji PvA 21, 50, 66; & udapādi (q. v.) Vin iii.4; J i.81; ger. °pajjivā D ii.157 = S i.6, 158 = ii.193 = J i.392 = Th 1, 1159; & uppajja J iv.24. - Caus. uppādeti (q. v.). - pp. uppanna (q. v.). See also upapajjati and upapanna.
- **Nirodha** [BSk. nirodha, to nirundhati, cp. nirujjhati & niruddha] oppression, suppression; destruction, cessation, annihilation (of senses, consciousness, feeling & being in general: sankhārā). Bdgh's expln of the word is: "ni - saddo abhāvaṃ, rodha - saddo ca cāraṃ dīpeti Vism 495. - N. in many cases is synonymous with nibbāna & parinibbāna; it may be said to be even a stronger expression as far as the active destruction of the causes of life is concerned. Therefore frequently combd with nibbāna in formula "sabbasankhāra - samatho... virāgo nirodho nibbānaṃ," e. g. S i.136; It 88. Nd2 s. nibbāna (see nibbāna iii.6). Also in combn with nibbidā, e. g. S iii.48, 223; iii.163 sq.; v.438. - The opposite of nirodha is samudaya, cp. formula "yaṃ kiñci samudaya - dhammaṃ sabban taṃ nirodha - dhammaṃ" e. g. Nd2 under sankhārā & passim. (a) Vin i.1, 10; D ii.33, 41, 57 sq., 112; iii.130 sq.
- **Nirujjhati** [Pass. of nirundhati (nirodhati) ni+rundhati] to be broken up, to be dissolved, to be destroyed, to cease, die Vin i.1; D i.180 sq., 215; ii.157; S iii.93 (aparisesaṃ); iv.36 sq., 60, 98, 184 sq.; 294, 402; v.213 sq.; A iii.165 sq. (aparisesaṃ); v.139 sq.; J i.180; Pug 64; Sdhp 606. - pp. niruddha. Cp. nirodha.

1.2 Lets try to grasp this via an example . . .

1.2.1 Arising

- **Anupassanā** (f.) [abstr. of anupassati, cf. Sk. anudarśana] looking at, viewing, contemplating, consideration, realisation S v.178 sq., Sn p. 140; Ps i.10, 20, 96; ii.37, 41 sq., 67 sq.; Vbh 194.

imasmim sati . . . or This being - Suppose you are doing Anapana meditation and in the present moment, the watch or anupassanā is on the flow of the breath, as it is (yatha-bhuta). Moment after moment, ***imasmim sati***, the anapana meditation is happening!

idam hoti . . . or that becomes , - the aftermath or the after affect of each passing breath, has a feeling of ease or release of some pattern, from the mind! This release or ease, is the becoming, of the anupassanā of the passing breath, irrespective of its quality!

imassuppādā . . . or from the arising of this , - Now suppose, you sat for an hour of Anapana meditation, so, after all moments of passing of each breath, something was released and what arose was a peaceful mind! The removal or eradication of the defilements (to a certain extent) of mind lead to the arising of a cleaner mind. At the advanced/refined stages, one can feel the cooling affect of the entire mind body complex. Thus has arisen something!

idam uppajjati . . . or that arises . Now, because of the foregoing arising, what follows is concentration of mind! The fruit of this entire process, is the arising of a concentrated mind! The concentrated mind is NOT forced. It is natural and takes affect naturally, after a sincere practice of long anapana session!

1.2.2 Cessation

So, now that there is some grasping of the arising, if i reverse the above arising, then this follows -

imasmim asati . . . or this not being - So, if i DO NOT practice Anapana meditation . . .

idam na hoti, . . . or that does not become - the release of certain defilements of mind will not happen! That becoming, will NOT come into affect!

imassa nirodhā . . . or from the ceasing of this - Further, when this practice has ceased, over a long duration (say), . . .

idam nirujjhati. . . . or that ceases . - the removal of defilements, the cooling of mind and the fruit i.e the concentration of mind DOES NOT follow through!

1.2.3 Regarding scholars . . .

Further, Jones (2022) in his manuscript, argued that modern scholars like K.N. Jayatilleke, Rhys Davidses, and Paul Williams have interpreted it as a **principle of causation, comparable to a scientific conception of causation**, while the author argues that, instead that this *imasmim sati* implied that the Buddha held that **causation is nothing more than the correlation of causes and effects, and that it commits the Buddha to a Humean regularity thesis about causation**.

In that context, Hume defines a cause to be, (as per regularity theory), as -

[a]n object precedent and contiguous to another, and where all the objects resembling the former are plac'd in like relations of priority and contiguity to those objects, that resemble the latter. (Hume 1739: book I, part III, section XIV [1978: 169])

Introductory details of the theories on causation can be found @ [Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy link!](#)

Thus, Jones (2022) concludes by presenting the argument that the *imasmim sati* formula **does not express a principle of causation but is rather a formula for the method of discovering and presenting causation as conditionality in experience**.

Now, i will *not dive deep into this subject of causation over here, however, there are a few points, i would like to state here, from my limited grasp in awareness, through meditations* -

1. • *Causation IS! in Mother nature . . .*
2. • *Based on the experiential knowledge of meditation, MAY BE, MAY BE, the Buddha expressed in a few simple words imasmim sati. That is what a sutta or sutra is! To express the experiential knowledge JAM-PACKED, in just a few words! (read about sutta/sutra below) Further, in this context, this expression captured the essence of causality, in limitation of frequencies of sound of a few words! so to speak . . . though he DID NOT FRAME it in the COLD DRY POLEMICs of ABSTRACT MATHEMATICs, of today's era! Am not sure, if, when one DOES NOT express something in dry cold polemics, is UNSCIENTIFIC, to begin with?*
3. *Modern era scholars, who have presented the dependent arising in terms of conditionality in the causal structure of subjective experience, have done a good job, HOWEVER, it DOESN'T ERASE the CONTRIBUTION of the Buddha, the fully liberated enlightened teacher, in existence!*
4. • *Hume's regularity theory, is a way to express about causation and it hold's its value in its place!*
5. • *To commit/restrict a fully liberated Buddha, to present the day Hume's theories, and PROJECT the modern day DRY COLD POLEMICs of abstract mathematics, as SUPERIOR, according to one's own view, . . . is one's own level! One needs to introspect and evaluate oneself, with respect to the Buddha. A fully liberated enlightened Buddha, is a Buddha!*

1.2.4 Sutta or Sutra

In my work Sinha (2017), a *sutta* tries to capture the un-captured absolute and gives a way to explore the deeper realms of the truth at an experiential level. What it brings to the readers is a way to study,

explore and absorb the spirit behind any spiritual injunction, by delving into a particular sutta in detail. Usually, a sutta is given or open to all in general, but how to unlock the sutta, gain insight into the spirit behind it and finally absorb the inherent knowledge at an experiential level is missing to many. Mere chanting of the sutta has its merits, but it does not help one progress on the journey. What is needed is a way to grasp how the profound knowledge that is locked or sealed in a few words can be opened up. The fact is that the highest is the simplest and sometimes it is so simple that even if it is front, one is unable to experience it. Thus, here the stress is given on deep meditations as a means of practice and then reading a sutta for theoretical purpose. Note that the individual's experiential knowledge needs a stamp or a seal of confirmation in the form of theoretical injunctions of those who have already experienced a particular knowledge and expressed it in the form of words for the help of many.

Thus, the fundamental aspect is that meditation helps in gaining experiential knowledge behind the spirit of the knowledge that is packed and transmitted in these *sutras* or *suttas*. A *sutra* or *sutta* is nothing but an expression in words (for the good of many on the spiritual path) of an experiential knowledge that has come to awareness and absorbed in the heart. One finds them across different cultures and traditions. So if one reads any spiritual knowledge, be careful of not reading it as a novel or for that matter to pass time. Meditate, read and contemplate.

Let the meditation clear the deeper impressions in the mind so that the bowl like mind becomes transparent and in awareness the essence of the spirit behind the knowledge unfolds itself. Here nature reveals the deeper secrets of the way to progress. Then, that which comes spontaneously and naturally in awareness belongs to you forever!

Any sutra or sutta will open up to a being who has acquired the merits in her/his heart. Thus it is imperative that one protects the merits of ones life and develops merits. The meditations and heart felt service to others is an important aspect. Finally, it is good to have knowledge of many sutras, but far better is to have an experiential knowledge of one sutra which will take carry you through to the respective goal in a spiritual journey. One can win many debates based on the theoretical knowledge of the vast compendium of sutras, but whether it will lead to *nirvana* is not known. Your practices are of greatest value. Your heart is clean and you have the merits, then nature will open the knowledge of any sutra for you. It is just a matter of time. So practice is important and be aware not to fall in the trap of collecting all the theoretical knowledge there is while no experiential knowledge dawns in you.

Pariyatti or theoretical knowledge - There is a way to read the scriptures that records the teachings of the ancient ones, be it any path. First one meditates. Say you meditated for a 5 days. Then the next two days you pick up a text that you want to acquire knowledge from. After you have read a few pages, then again meditate. In the stillness of awareness and the depths of the meditation the essence of the knowledge written in words might appear in your awareness and your being might absorb that knowledge. This is a long process. There are 3 stages of acquiring knowledge in the higher dimensions of truth & the spiritual realm, i.e - (1) *Suta-maya-panna or knowledge/wisdom acquired by listening*. Listening can be through any of the senses. (2) *Cinta-maya-panna or knowledge/wisdom acquired via mental chewing of the knowledge*. As you chew the chewing gum, so also your mind starts chewing the knowledge, yet the knowledge/wisdom is not completely absorbed. (3) Finally, *Bhavana-maya-panna or knowledge/wisdom is absorbed in your being*. That knowledge settles in your heart also, firmly. So you move from *pariyatti (theory)*, to *patipatti (practice)* to *pa-tivedha (attainment)*. One has to continue on this whole life, as one meditates, contemplates and reads, again and again and again and . . . **Fools study voraciously to amass as much information**

as possible, whether it gets digested or not is not the issue, and will vomit it out in front of everyone to show something. Spiritual debates have the characteristics where one party tries to debate with the other and defeat the other party. Not that it is not useful, but whether knowledge has settled in a being is a vastly different matter. It takes long time to grasp the truths from the abstract dimension . . .

The Buddha himself stressed on the personal experiential knowledge through deep meditations. Even after full liberation, he used to sit and meditate with those who used to learn from him. Those who trained with him, used to meditate and then after sustained period of meditations over a long period of time, they would themselves arrive at the conclusion regarding the truths that the Buddha expounded in words. **There is an incidence in the life of the Buddha. An ascetic came to him and asked - "what is it that you have acquired, please share?" The Buddha said - "Sit with me." And then they both immersed in deep meditation. The experiential knowledge was transmitted between the two just by sitting together in meditation, in silence. After the experience, the ascetic was full of tears of joy for the experience that was shared or transmitted, in silence in deep meditation. Neither the Buddha said a word and nor the ascetic said anything. As if the Buddha and the ascetic had aligned in oneness, in existence and what had to be shared was shared, in meditation.** Thus, through experiential knowledge one moves and evolves and this is a time taking and natural process. **To hit the point**, in . . .

Poṭṭhīlattheravatthu, Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada, Maggavagga, Pañcasatabhikkhuvatthu, it is said -

- **Pali** : *Yogā ve jāyati bhūri*, **English** : From meditation springs wisdom,
- **Pali** : *Etaṃ dvedhāpathaṃ nātvā*, **English** : without meditation, wisdom ends.
- **Pali** : *bhavāya vibhavāya ca*; **English** : Knowing these two paths -
- **Pali** : *Tathāttānaṃ niveseyya*, **English** : of progress and decline -
- **Pali** : *yathā bhūri pavaḍḍhati*. **English** : you should conduct yourself so that wisdom grows.

Further, in the Dīgha Nikāya, Mahāparinibbānasutta, The Great Discourse on the Buddha's Extinguishment, it says -

- **Pali** : *Yo imasmim dhammavinaye*, **English** : Whoever meditates diligently,
- **Pali** : *appamatto vihassati*; **English** : in this teaching and training,
- **Pali** : *Pahāya jātsamsāraṃ*, **English** : giving up transmigration through rebirths,
- **Pali** : *dukkhassantaṃ karissati*”ti. **English** : will make an end to suffering.”
- **Pali** : *'ye te, bhante, ahesum atītamaddhānaṃ arahanto sammāsambuddhā, sabbe te bhagavanto pañca nīvaraṇe pahāya cetaso upakkilese paññāya dubbalīkaṇe catūsu satipatṭhānesu supatitṭhitacittā sattabojjhaṅge yathābhūtaṃ bhāvetvā anuttaraṃ sammāsambodhiṃ abhisambujjhimsu*. **English** : 'All the perfected ones, fully awakened Buddhas - whether past, future, or present - give up the five hindrances, corruptions of the heart that weaken wisdom. Their mind is firmly established in the four kinds of mindfulness meditation. They correctly develop the seven awakening factors. And they wake up to the supreme perfect awakening.'

1.2.5 Who is a scholar? . . .

In the Majjhima Nikāya 91, (Middle Discourses), Brahmāyusutta, with Brahmāyu -

Atha kho brahmāyu brāhmaṇo bhagavantam gāthāhi ajjhabhāsi : So Brahmāyu addressed the Buddha in verse :

- **Pali** : ”Katham kho brāhmaṇo hoti, **English** : “How do you become a brahmin?
- **Pali** : *katham bhavati vedagū*; **English** : And how do you become a knowledge master?
- **Pali** : *Tevijjo bho katham hoti*, **English** : How a master of the three knowledges?
- **Pali** : *sotthiyo kinti vuccati*. **English** : And how is one called a scholar?
- **Pali** : *Araham bho katham hoti*, **English** : How do you become a perfected one?
- **Pali** : *katham bhavati kevalī*; **English** : And how a consummate one?
- **Pali** : *Muni ca bho katham hoti*, **English** : How do you become a sage?
- **Pali** : *buddho kinti pavuccatī*”ti. **English** : And how is one declared to be awakened?”

Atha kho bhagavā brahmāyuraṃ brāhmaṇam gāthāhi paccabhāsi : Then the Buddha replied to Brahmāyu in verse :

- **Pali** : “Pubbenivāsam yo vedi, **English** : “One who knows their past lives,
- **Pali** : *saggāpāya ca passati*; **English** : sees heaven and places of loss,
- **Pali** : *Atho jātikkhayam patto*, **English** : and has attained the end of rebirth:
- **Pali** : *abhiññā vosito muni*. **English** : such a sage has perfect insight.
- **Pali** : *Cittam visuddham jānāti*, **English** : They know their mind is pure,
- **Pali** : *muttam rāgehi sabbaso*; **English** : completely freed from greed;
- **Pali** : *Pahīnajātīmaraṇo*, **English** : they’ve given up birth and death,
- **Pali** : *brahmacariyassa kevalī*; **English** : and have completed the spiritual journey.
- **Pali** : *Pāragū sabbadhammānam*, **English** : Gone beyond all things,
- **Pali** : *buddho tādī pavuccatī*”ti. **English** : such a one is declared to be awakened.”

Regarding the 2nd foregoing point, in the words of the Buddha himself, in the Dhammapada 1.19 -

- **Pali** : *Bahum-pi ce sahitam bhāsamāno, na takkaro hoti naro pamatto, gopo va gāvo gaṇayam paresam, na bhāgavā sāmāññassa hoti*.
- **English** : Even though reciting abundant scriptures, the heedless fellow, who does not do (what they say), like a cowboy counting other’s cattle, does not partake of the ascetic life.

and in Dhammapada 1.20 -

- **Pali** : *Appam-pi ce sahitaṃ bhāsamāno, Dhammassa hoti anudhammacārī, rāgañ-ca dosañ-ca pahāya mohañ, sammappajāno suvimuttacitto, anupādiyāno idha vā hurañ vā, sa bhāgavā sāmāññassa hoti.*
- **English** : Even though reciting but few scriptures, but living righteously in accordance with Dhamma, abandoning greed, hate and delusion, understanding aright, with mind well-released, that one, unattached here and hereafter, (surely) partakes of the ascetic life.

2 Etymology

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the [link to online Pali dictionary at University of Chicago](#) and English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989), these words, have meanings that connote the word depend / interdepend / cause -

2.1 word 'Depend' in . . .

the English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989), these words, depict *depend* and *appears @ 3 different places* -

1. **Depend** : v.i. nissayati; avalambati; avassayati. p.p. nissita; avalambita; avassita. **able** : **adj.** avassayitabba. **ing on** : nissāya; upādāya; paṭicca. **on** : upajīvati; anujīvati.
2. **Dependant** : (adj.) nissita; parādhīna; parāyatta. (m.) upajīvī; anujīvī. **origination** : (m.) paṭiccasamuppāda.
3. **Dependence** : (nt.) nissaya; avalambana. (f.) paravasatā. **ency** : (m.) parādhīnadesa.

the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the [link to online Pali dictionary at University of Chicago](#), *appears @ 32 different places*, which are as follows -

1. **Añña** (pron.) [Vedic anya, with compar. suff. ya; Goth. anpar; Ohg. andar; formation with n analagous to those with l in Gr. α' λ λ ο ς (α' λ j o ς), Lat. alius (cp. alter), Goth. aljis Ags. elles = E. else. From demonstr. base *eno, see na1 and cp. a3] another etc. - A. By itself: 1. other, not the same, different, another, somebody else (opp. oneself) Vin iii.144 (aññena, scil. maggena, gacchati to take a different route); Sn 459, 789, 904; Dh 158 (opp. attānaṃ), 165; J i.151 (opp. attano); ii.333 (aññaṃ vyākāroti give a diff. answer). - 2. another one, a second; nt. else, further Sn 1052 (= uttarim nt. Nd2 17); else J i.294. aññaṃ kiñci (indef.) anything else J i.151. yo añño every other, whoever else J i.256. - 3. aññe (pl.) (the) others, the rest Sn 189, 663, 911; Dh 43, 252, 355; J i.254. - B. del. in correlation: 1. copulative. añña . . añña the one . . the other (. . the third etc.); this, that & the other; some . . some Vin i.15; Miln 40; etc. - 2. reciprocative añño aññaṃ, aññamaññaṃ, aññoññaṃ one another, each other, mutually, reciprocally (in ordinary construction & declension of a noun or adj. in sg.; cp. Gr. α λ λ λ η λ ω ν, α λ λ η λ ο u ς in pl.). (a.) aññ o aññaṃ Dh 165. (b.) aññamañña (cp. BSk. añyamañya M Vastu ii.436), as pron.: n'ālaṃ aññamaññaṃ sukhāya vā dukkhāya vā D i.56 = S iii 211. n'aññamaññaṃ dukkhaṃ iccheyya do not wish evil to each other

- Sn 148. daṇḍehi aññamaññaṃ upakkamanti (approach each other) M i.86 = Nd2 199. °m agāravo viharati A iii.247. dve janā °m ghātayimsu (slew each other) J i.254. aññamaññaṃ hasanti J v.111; °m musale hantvā J v.267. °m daṇḍābhigātena PvA 58; or adj.: aññamaññaṃ veram bandhimsu (established mutual enmity) J ii.353; °m piyasamvāsam vasimsu J ii.153; aññamaññaṃ accayaṃ desetvā (their mutual mistake) DhA i.57; or adv. dvepi aññamaññaṃ paṭibaddha citta ahesuṃ (in love with each other) J iii.188; or ° - : aññamañña - paccaya mutually dependent, interrelated Ps ii.49, 58. - (c.) aññoñña (°-) J v.251 (°nissita); Dāvs v.45 (°bhinna). - 3. disjunctive añña . . añña one . . the other, this one . . . that one, different, different from aññaṃ jīvaṃ . . aññaṃ sarīraṃ one is the soul . . the other is the body, i. e. the soul is different from the body D i.157; M i.430; A v.193; añña va sañña bhavissati añño attā D i.187. Thus also in phrase aññena aññaṃ opposite, the contrary, differently, contradictory (lit. other from that which is other) Vin ii.85 (paṭicarati make counter - charges); D i.57 (vyākāsi gave the opposite or contradictory reply); Miln 171 (aññaṃ kayiramānaṃ aññaṃ sambharati). - anañña (1) not another, i. e. the same, self - same, identical M i.256 (= ayaṃ). - (2) not another, i. e. alone, by oneself, oneself only Sn 65 (°posin; opp. paraṃ) = Nd 4, cp. Nd2 36. - (3) not another, i. e. no more, only, alone Sn p. 106 (dve va gatiyo bhavanti anañña: and no other or no more, only two). See also under cpds. - **Sita dependent** or relying on others Sn 825. **Sita**² [pp. of sayati²] 1. (lit.) stuck in or to: hadaya° salla Sn 938; Nd1 412. - 2. (fig.) reclining, resting, depending on, attached, clinging to D i.45, 76; ii.255; M i.364; Cp. 100; J v.453; Sn 229, 333, 791, 944, 1044. See also asita².
2. **Ativasa** (adj.) [ati + vasa fr. vas] being under somebody's rule, **dependent** upon (c. gen.) Dh 74 (= vase vattati DhA ii.79).
 3. **Adhīna** (adj.) (-°) [cp. Sk. adhīna] subject, **dependent** D i.72 (atta° & para°); J iv.112; DA i.217; also written ādhīna J v.350. See also under para.
 4. **Anuyanta** at A v.22 is doubtful reading (v.l. anuyutta). The meaning is either "inferior to, **dependent** on, a subject of, a vassal" or "attending on". The explanation may compare Sk. anuyātaṃ attendance [anu + yā, cp. anuyāyin] or Sk. yanṭṛ ruler [yam], in which latter case anu - yanṭṛ would be "an inferior ruler" and P. yanta would represent the n. a.g. yantā as a - stem. The v. l. is perhaps preferable as long as other passages with anuyanta are not found (see anuyutta 2).
 5. **Aparapaccaya** (adj.) [a + para + paccaya] not **dependent** or relying on others Vin i.12 (vesārajja- ppatta +); D i.110 (id.); M ii 41; M i.491; S iii.83; DA i.278 (= nāssa paro paccayo).
 6. **Apasseti** [Sk. apāśrayati, apa + ā + sri] to lean against, have a support in (acc.), to **depend** on. - 1. (lit.) lean against Vin ii.175 (bhitti apassetabbo the wall to be used as a head - rest). - 2. (fig.) mostly in ger. apassāya **dependent** upon, **depending** on, trusting in (loc. or acc. or - °) Vin iii.38; J i.214; PvA 189. - pp. apassita (q. v.). - See also avasseti.
 7. **Abhicetasika** (adj.) [abhi + ceto + ika] **dependent** on the clearest consciousness. On the spelling see ābhi° (of jhāna) M i.33, 356; iii.11; S ii.278; A ii.23; v.132. (Spelt. ābhi° at M i.33; A iii.114; Vin v.136). See Dial. iii.108.

8. **Asahāya** (adj.) [a + sahāya] one who is without friends; who is *dependent* on himself Miln 225.
9. **Asayaṃvasin** (adj.) [a + sayam + vasim] not under one's own control, i. e. *dependent* D ii.262; J i.337.
10. **Assita** (adj.) [Sk. aśrita, ā + pp. of śri] *dependent* on, relying, supported by (acc.); abiding, living in or on D ii.255 (tad°); Vv 5016 (siho va guhaṃ a.); Th 1, 149 (janaṃ ev assito jano); Sdhp 401.
11. **Āyatta** [Sk. āyatta, pp. of ā + yat]. - 1. striving, active, ready, exerted J v.395 (°mana = ussukkamana C.). - 2. striven after, pursued J i.341. - 3. *dependent* on Vism 310 (assāsa - passāsa°); Nett 194; Sdhp 477, 605.
12. **Upanissayati** [upa + ni°] to *depend* or rely on (acc.) Miln 240 (attānaṃ). - ger.°nissāya (q. v.); - pp. °nissita (q. v.).
13. **Upanissāya** (adv.) [ger. of upanissayati, cp. nissayati in same use & meaning] near, close by (with acc.); *depending* on, by means of (acc) M ii.3; S ii.269; Sn 867 (taṃ), 901 (tāpa°), 978, PvA 9 (Rājagahaṃ), 67 (id.); VvA 63 (Rājagaha - seṭṭhim "with"). Cp. BSk. upanissāya also a ger. formation, in same meaning, e. g. at Divy 54, 207, 505.
14. **Upanibandha** [upa + ni + bandh] 1. close connection, *dependence* Vism 19 (°gocara). - 2. (adj. - °) connected with, *dependent* on Vism 235 (jīvitam assāsa - passāsa° etc).
15. **Upādi°** [the compn. - from of upādāna, derived fr. upādā in analogy to nouns in °a & °ā which change their a to i in compn. with kṛ & bhū; otherwise a n. formation fr. dā analogous to °dhi fr. dhā in upadhi] = upādāna, but in more concrete meaning of "stuff of life", substratum of being, khandha; only in combn. with °sesa (adj.) having some fuel of life (= khandhas or sub-stratum) left, i. e. still *dependent* (on existence), not free, materially determined S v.129, 181; A iii.143; It 40; Vism 509. More frequently neg. an-upādi-sesa (nibbāna, nibbānadhātu or parinibbāna, cp. similarly BSk. anupādi - vimukti M Vastu i.69) completely emancipated, free, without any (material) substratum Vin ii.239 (nibbāna - dhātu); D iii.135; M i.148 (parinibbāna); A ii.120; iv.75 sq., 202, 313; J i.28, 55; Sn 876; It 39, 121 (nibbāna - dhātu); Ps. i.101; Vism 509; DhA iv.108 (nibbāna); VvA 164, 165. Opp. saupādisesa A iv.75 sq., 378 sq.; Sn 354 (opp. nibbāyi); Vism 509; Nett 92. See further ref. under nibbāna & parinibbāna.
16. **Ūpaka** (also read as °upaka, °ūpaga; °upaga; for ūpaga, see Trenckner, P.M. 62, n. 16; cp. kulopaka Divy 307) frequenting a family, *dependent* on a (or one & the same) family (for alms, etc.); a friend, an associate. Freq. in formula kulū-pako hoti bahukāni kulāni upasankamati, e. g. Vin iii.131, 135; iv.20. - Vin i.192, 208; iii.84, 237; v.132; S ii.200 sq.; A iii.136, 258 sq.; Pv iii.85; Vism 28; DA i.142 (rāja°); PvA 266. f. kulūpikā (bhikkhunī) Vin ii.268; iv.66;
17. **Paṭibaddha** (adj.) [paṭi+baddha, pp. of bandh] bound to, in fetters or bonds, attracted to or by, *dependent* on D i.76; Vin iv.302 (kāya°); A v.87 (para°); Dh 284; Miln 102 (āvajjana°); PvA 134 (°jīvika *dependent* on him for a living). - Freq. in cpd.° citta affected, enamoured,

one's heart bound in love Vin iii.128; iv.18; Sn 37 (see Nd2 385), 65; PvA 46, 145 (°tā f. abstr.), 151, 159 (rañño with the king).

18. **Khandha** [Sk. skandha] - I. Crude meaning: bulk, massiveness (gross) substance. A. esp. used (a) of an elephant: the bulk of the body, i. e. its back S i.95; vāraṇassa J iii.392; hatthi - khandha - vara - gata on the back of the state elephant J i.325; PvA 75. Also with ref. to an elephant (hatthināga) sañjāta° "to whom has grown bulk=a large back" Sn 53, expl. SnA 103 by susaṅṅhitakkhandho "well endowed with bulk." - (b) of a person: the shoulder or back: nangalaṃ khandhe karitvā S i.115 appl. to Māra; Vism 100; DhA iv.168 (ohita° - bhāra the load lifted off his shoulder). - - (c) of a tree: the trunk. rukkhassa PvA 114, also as rukkha° J i.324; tāla° the stem of a palm PvA 56; nigrodhassa khandhaja (see cpds.) S i.207=Sn 272; mūlaṃ atikkamma kh° ṃ sāraṃ pariye- sitabbaṃ "one must go beyond the root and search the trunk for sweetness" S iv.94. - (d) as t.t. in exegetical literature: section, chapter, lit. material as collected into uniform bulk; freq. in postscripts to Texts and Commentaries. See also khandhaka. - B. More general as denoting bulk (- °); e. g. aggi° a great mass of fire M ii.34, 41; J iv.139; udaka° a mass of water (i. e. ocean) A iii.336; S iv.179; J i.324; PvA 62; puñña° a great accumulation of merit A iii.336=S v.400; bhoga° a store of wealth A v.84; J i.6; maṇi° an extraordinarily large jewel (possessing magic power) J ii.102 sq. - II. Applied meaning. - A. (-°) the body of, a collection of, mass, or parts of; in collective sense "all that is comprised under"; forming the substance of. - (a) dukkha° all that is comprised under "dukkha," all that goes to make up or forms the substance, the idea of "ill." Most prominent in phrase ke- valassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudaya and nirodha (the origin & destruction of all that is suffering) with ref. to the paṭic- casamuppāda, the chain of causal existence (q. v.) Vin i.1; S ii.95; iii.14; A i.177; v. 184 & passim. Similarly: samudaya Vbh 135 sq. nirodha Nett 64; antakiriya A i.147; vyādhi- maraṇatunnānaṃ dukkhakkhandhaṃ vyapānudi Th 2, 162. - (b) lobha° dosa° moha° the three ingredients or integrations of greed, suffering and bewilderment, lit. "the big bulk or mass of greed" (see also under padāleti), S v.88 (nibbijjhati through the satta bojjhangā). - (c) vayo° a division of age, part of age, as threefold: purima°, majjhima°, pacchima° Nd2 in def. of sadā. - (d) sīla (etc.) kh° the 3 (or 5) groups or parts which constitute the factors of right living (dhamma), viz. (1) sīla° the group dealing with the practice of morality; (2) samādhi° that dealing with the development of concentration; (3) paññā° that dealing with the development of true wisdom. They are also known under the terms of sīla - sampadā, citta °, paññā° D i.172 sq.; see sīla. - D i.206; Nett 64 sq.; 126. tīhi dhammehi samannāgato "possessed of the three qualities," viz. sīla - kkhandhesu, etc. It 51; cp. A i.291; v.326. tīhi khandhehi . . . aṅṅhangiko maggo sangahito M i.301; sīlakkhandhaṃ, etc. paripūreti "to fulfil the sīla - group" A i.125; ii.20, iii.15 sq. These 3 are completed to a set of 5 by (4) vimutti° the group dealing with the attainment of emancipation and (5) vimutti - nāṇa - dassana° the group dealing with the realization of the achievement of emancipation. As 1 - 4 only at D iii.229 (misprintpuñña for paññā); cp. A i.125. As 5 at S i.99=A i.162; S v.162; A iii.134, 271; v.16 (all loc.=S i.99); It 107, 108; Nd2 under sīla. B. (absolute) in individual sense: constituent element, factor, substantiality. More especially as khandhā (pl.) the elements or substrata of sensory existence, sensorial aggregates which condition the appearance of life in any form. Their character according to quality and value of life and body is evanescent, fraught with ills & leading to rebirth. Paraphrased by Bdgh. as rāsi, heap, e. g. Asl. 141; Vibh A 1 f.; cf. B. Psy. 42. 1. Unspecified. They are usually enumerated in the foll.

stereotyped set of 5: rūpa° (material qualities), vedanā (feeling), saññā (perception), sankhārā (coefficients of con- sciousness), viññāṇa (consciousness). For further ref. see rūpa; cp. also Mrs. Rh. D. Dhs trsl. pp. 40 - 56. They are enumerated in a different order at S i.112, viz. rūpaṃ vedayitaṃ saññaṃ viññāṇaṃ yañ ca sankhataṃ n'eso 'ham asmi. Detailed discussions as to their nature see e. g. S iii.101 (=Vbh 1 - 61); S iii.47; iii.86. As being comprised in each of the dhātus, viz. kāma° rūpa° arūpa - dhātu Vbh 404 sq. (a) As factors of existence (cp. bhava). Their rôle as such is illustrated by the famous simile: "yathā hi angasambhārā hoti saddo ratho iti evaṃ khandhesu santesu hoti satto ti sammuti" "just as it is by the condition precedent of the co - existence of its various parts, that the word G chariot' is used, just so it is that when the skandhas are there, we talk of a G being' " (Rh. D.) (cp. Hardy, Man. Buddh. p. 425) S i.135=Miln 28. Their connotation "khandha" is discussed at S iii.101 =M iii.16: "kittāvataṃ nu kho khandhānaṃ khandhādhivacanaṃ? rūpaṃ (etc.) atītānāgatappaccuppannaṃ ajjhataṃ vā bahiddhāvā oḷārikaṃ," etc.: i.e. material qualities are equivalent terms for the kh. What causes the manifestation of each kh.? cattāro mahābhūtā . . . paccayo rūpa - khandhassa paññāpanāya; phasso . . . vedana°, saññā°, sankhārā°, etc.; nā-marūpaṃ . . . viññāṇa°: the material elements are the cause of rūpa, touch is that of vedanā, saññā, sankhārā, name and shape that of viññāṇa (S iii.101); cp. M i.138 sq., 234 sq. On the same principle rests their division in: rūpa - kāyo rūpakkhandho nāmakāyo cattāro arūpino khandhā "the material body forms the material factor (of existence), the individualized body the 4 immaterial factors" Nett 41; the rūpakkhandha only is kāmadhātu - pariyāpanno: Vbh 409; the 4 arūpino kh° discussed at Ps ii.74, also at Vbh 230, 407 sq. (grouped with what is apariyāpanna) - Being the "substantial" factors of existence, birth & death *depend* on the khandhas. They appear in every new conjuncture of individuality concerning their function in this paṭisandhi - kkhane; see Ps ii.72 - 76. Thus the var. phases of life in transmigration are defined as - (jāti:) ya tesaṃ tesaṃ sattānaṃ tamhi tamhi satta - nikāye jāti sañjāti okkanti abhinibbatti khandhānaṃ pātubhāvo āyatanānaṃ paṭilābho Nd2 on Sn 1052; cp. jāti dvīhi khandhehi sangahitā ti VvA 29; khandhānaṃ pā- tubhāvo jāti S ii.3; Nett 29; khandhānaṃ nibbatti jāti Vism 199. - (maraṇaṃ:) yā tesaṃ tesaṃ sattānaṃ . . . cuti cavanatā bhedo antaradhānaṃ maccu maraṇaṃ kālakiriyā khandhānaṃ bhedo kalevarassa nikkhepo M i.49=Vbh 137=S ii.3, 42. - vivaṭṭa - kkhanda (adj.) one whose khandhas have revolved (passed away), i. e. dead S i.121=iii.123. - kh°anaṃ udaya - vyaya (or udayabbaya) the rising and passing of the kh., transmigration Dh 374=Th 1, 23, 379=It 120=KhA 82; Ps i.54 sq. - (b) Their relation to attachment and craving (kāma): sattisūlūpamā kāma khandhānaṃ adhikuṭṭanaṃ S i.128=Th 2, 58, 141 (ThA 65: natthi tesaṃ adhik°?); craving is their cause & soil: hetupaṭicca sambhūtā kh. S i.134; the 4 arūpino kh. are based on lobha, dosa, moha Vbh 208. - (c) their annihilation: the kh. remain as long as the knowledge of their true character is not attained, i. e. of their cause & removal: yaṃ rūpaṃ, etc . . . n' etaṃ mama n' eso 'ham asmi na m' eso attā ti; evaṃ etaṃ yathābhūtaṃ sammappaññāya passati; evaṃ kho jānato passato . . . ahankāramamankāra - mānānusayā na honti ti S iii.103; - pañca - kkhandahe pariññāya S iii.83; pañca - kkhandahe pariññātā tiṭṭhanti chinnaṃlakā Th 2, 106. See also S i.134. - (d) their relation to dhātu (the physical elements) and āyatana (the elements of sense - perception) is close, since they are all *dependent* on sensory experience. The 5 khandhas are frequently mentioned with the 18 dhātuyo & the 12 āyatanāni: khandhā ca dh° cha ca āyatanā ime hetuṃ paṭicca sambhūtā hetubhangā nirujjhare S i.134; kh° dh° - āyatanāṃ sankhataṃ jātimūlaṃ Th 2, 472; dhammaṃ adesesi khandh' - āyatana - dhātuyo Th 2, 43 (cp. ThA

49). Enumerated under sabba - dhammā Ps i.101=ii.230; under dhammā (states) Dhs 121, as lokuttara - kkhandhā, etc. Dhs 358, 528, 552. - khandhānaṃ khandhaṭṭho abhiññeyyo, dhātūnaṃ dhātuṭṭho, etc. Ps i.17; cp. i.132; ii.121, 157. In def. of kāmāvacarā bhūmi Ps i.83. In def. of dukkha and its recognition Nett 57. In def. of arahanto khīṇāsavā Nd2 on sankhāta - dhammā ("kh. sankhātā," etc.), on tiṇṇa ("khandha - (etc.) pariyante thitā"), & passim. - (e) their valuation & their bearing on the "soul" - conception is described in the terms of namama (na tumhākaṃ), anattā, aniccaṃ and dukkhaṃ (cp. upādānakkh^o infra and rūpa) rūpaṃ (etc.) . . . aniccaṃ, dukkhaṃ, n' eso 'ham asmi, n' eso me attā "material qualities (etc. kh. 2 - 5) are evanescent, bad, I am not this body, this body is not my soul" Vin i.14=S iv.382. n' eso 'ham asmi na m' eso attā S i.112; iii.103, 130 & passim; cp. kāyo na tumhākaṃ (anattā rūpaṃ) S ii.65; Nd2 680; and rūpaṃ na tumhākaṃ S iii.33 M i.140=Nd2 680. - rūpaṃ, etc. as anattā: Vin i.13; S iii.78, 132 - 134; A i.284= ii.171; 202; cp. S iii.101; Vin i.14. - as aniccaṃ: S iii.41, 52, 102, 122, 132 sq., 181 sq., 195 sq., 202 - 224, 227; A iv.147 (aniccānupassī dukkhānupassī); anicca dukkha roga, etc., Ps ii.238 sq.; Vbh 324. - 2. Specified as panc' upādāna-kkhandhā the factors of the fivefold clinging to existence. Defined & discussed in detail (rūpūpadāna - kkhandha, etc.) S iii.47; 86 - 88; also Vin i.10; S iii.127 sq. Specified S iii.58 iii.100=M iii.16; S iii.114, 158 sq.; v.52, 60; A iv.458; Vism 443 sq. (in ch. xiv: Khandha - niddesa), 611 sq. (judged aniccato, etc.). - Mentioned as a set exemplifying the number 5: Kh iii.; Ps i.22, 122. Enumerated in var. connections S i.112; D iii.233; M i.190; A v.52; Kh iv. (expld KhA 82=A v.52); Miln 12 (var. references concerning the discussion of the kh. in the Abhidhamma). - What is said of the khandhas alone - see above 1 (a) - (e) - is equally applied to them in connection with upādāna. - (a) As regards their origin they are characterized as chandamūlakā "rooted in desire, or in wilful desire" S iii.100; cp. yo kho . . . pañcas' upādānakkhandhesu chandarāgo taṃ tattha upādānaṃ ti M i.300, 511. Therefore the foll. attributes are characteristic: kummo pañcann' etaṃ upād^o ānaṃ adhivacanaṃ M i.144; bhārā have pañcakkh^oā S iii.26; pañcavadhakā paccatthikā pañcann' . . . adhivacanaṃ S iv.174; pañc' upād^o . . . sakkāyo vutto M i.299= S iv.259. - (b) their contemplation leads to the recognition of their character as dukkha, anicca, anattā: na kiñci attānaṃ vā attaniyaṃ vā pañcasu upādānakkhandhesu S iii.128; rogato, etc. . . . manasikātabbā pañc^o S iii.167; pañcasu upād^oesu aniccānupassī "realizing the evanescence in the 5 aggregates of attachment" A v.109; same with udayavyayānupassī S iii.130; A ii.45, 90; iii.32; iv.153; and dhammānupassī M i.61. Out of which realization follows their gradual destruction: pañc' . . . khandhānaṃ samudayo atthangamo assādo, etc. S iii.31, 160 sq.; A ii.45, 90; iv.153; Nd2 under sankhārā. That they occupy a prominent position as determinants of dukkha is evident from their rôle in the exposition of dukkha as the first one of the noble truths: sankhittena pañc' upādānakkhandhā pi dukkhā "in short, the 5 kh. are associated with pain" Vin i.10=M i.48=A i.177=S v.421; Ps i.37, 39; Vbh 101 & passim; cp. katamaṃ dukkham ariyasaccaṃ? pañc' upād^o ā tissa vacanīyaṃ, seyyathidaṃ . . . S iii.158=v.425; khandhādisā dukkhā Dh 202 (& expl. DhA iii.261). - 3. Separately mentioned: °viññāṇa - kh^o (the skandha of discriminative consciousness) in Def. of manas: manindriyaṃ viññāṇaṃ viññ^o - khandho tājā manoviññāṇadhātu Nd2 on Sn 1142=Dhs 68.

19. **Go** (m. - f.) [Vedic go, Lat. bos, Gr. βούς, Ohg. chuo, Ags. cū=E. cow] a cow, an ox, bull, pl. cattle. For f. cp. gāvī; see also gava^o for cpds. - Sg. nom. go (Sn 580, also in composition, cp. aja - go - mahisādi PvA 80=pasū); gen. gavassa (M i.429); instr. gavena, gāvena; acc.

gavaṃ, gāvan; abl. gavamhā, gavā (D i.201=A ii.95= Pug 69); loc. gavamhi, gāvimhi (SnA 323), gave (Sn 310). - Pl. nom. gāvo (D i.141; M i.225; A i.205; ii.42 sq.; Sn 20, 296, 307; J i.295); gen. gonam A ii.75 (cp. Vedic gonām), gavaṃ (J iv.172, cp. gavaṃ pati), gunnam (A i.229, ii.75; v.271; J i.194; iii.112; iv.223); instr. gohi (Sn 33); acc. gāvo (M i.225; A i.205; Sn 304; Dh 19, 135); abl. gohi; loc. gosu, gavesu. - See also gava, gavesati, goṇa. **cara** I. Lit. A. (noun - m.) pasture, lit. "a cow's grazing," search after food; fodder, food, subsistence (a) of animals: J i.221; iii.26; Dh 135 (daṇḍena gopālo gāvo pāceti gocaraṃ: with a stick the cowherd drives the cattle to pasture). Sīho gocarāya pakkamati "the lion goes forth for his huut" A ii.33= iii.121; gocarāya gacchati to go feeding, to graze Sn 39; J i.243; gocare carati to go feeding, to feed J i.242. - (b) metaph. of persons, esp. the bhikkhu: pucchitabba gocara (and agocara) "enquiries have to be made concerning the fitness or otherwise of his pasturage (i. e. the houses in which he begs for food)" Vin ii.208; samaṇo gocarato nivatto an ascetic returned from his "grazing" Pv iv.142: Similarly at Vism 127, where a suitable g. - gama ranks as one of the 7 desiderata for one intent on meditation. - B. (adj.) (-°) feeding on or in, living in; metaph. dealing with, mixing with. vana° living in the woods Pv ii.65; vāri° (in water) Sn 605; jala° (id.) J ii.158 (opp. thala°). Vesiyā° (etc.) associating with v. Vin i.70. - II. Applied. A. (noun- m. or nt.) a "field" (of sense perception, etc.), sphere, object; - ° food for, an object of (a) psychologically indriyānaṃ nānāgocarāni various spheres of sense - perception S v.218; sense - object (=ārammaṇam) Ps i.180; ii.97; 150 sq.; DhA 314, 315 (sampatta° physical contact with an object, gandha° smell - contact, i. e. sensation); indriya° Sdhp 365. - (b) ethically: ariyānaṃ gocare ratā "finding delight in the pasture of the good," walking in the ways of the good Dh 22; vimokho yesam gocarō "whose pasture is liberty" Dh 92=Th 1, 92. Esp. in phrase ācāra - go-cara - sampanna "pasturing in the field of good conduct" D i.63=It 118; M i.33; S v.187; It. 96; analysed as Dvandva cpd. at Vbh 246, 247, but cp. pāpācāra - gocara Sn 280, 282. This phrase (ācāra - gocara) is also discussed in detail at Vism 19, where 3 kinds of gocarā are distinguished, viz. upanissaya°, ārakkha°, upanibandha°. So also in contrast w. agocara, an unfit pasture, or an unfit, i. e. bad, sphere of life, in gocare & agocare carati to move in a congenial or uncongenial sphere A iii.389; iv.345 sq.; D iii.58=77; S v.147; Vbh 246, 247 (expl. w. vesiyā° etc., cp. above=having bad associations). - B. (adj.) - °: belonging to, **dependent** on, falling to the share of: eta° **dependent** on this M i.319; sattasaddhamma°, moving in the sphere of the seven golden rules S iii.83; rūpa° to be perceived by sight J i.396; Nibbāna° belonging to N. Sdhp 467. - °kusala (adj.) skilled in (finding proper) food; clever in right living - °behaving properly in, exercising properly M i.220=A v.347 (of a cowherd driving out his cattle); S iii.266 sq. (samādhi°); A iii.311 (do.) v.352 sq. (w. ref. to cattāro satipatṭhānā); - °gahaṇa the taking of food, feeding J i.242; - °gāma a village for the supply of food (for the bhikkhus) PvA 12, 42; - °ṭṭhāna pasturage J iii.52; - °pasuta intent on feeding J iii.26; - °bhūmi pasturage, a common DhA iii.60; - °visaya (the sphere of) an object of sense S v.218; Vbh 319;

20. **Ṭhāyin** (adj. - n.) [from ṭṭhati] standing, being in, being in a state of (-°), staying with, **dependent** on (with gen.) : pariyutṭhatṭhāyin "being in a state of one to whom it has arisen," i. e. one who has got the idea of . . . or one who imagines S iii.3 sq.; arūpa - ṭṭhāyin It 62; Yamassa ṭhāyino being under the rule of Yama Pv i.119.

21. **Ṭhitika** (adj.) [Der. fr. ṭhiti] standing, lasting, enduring; existing, living on (-°), e. g. āhāra **dependent** on food Kh iii. (see āhāra); nt. adv. ṭhitikaṃ constantly VvA 75.

22. **Dīpa** the firm ground or footing of the Dh. (usually combd with *atta* - *dīpa*: having oneself as one's refuge, self - *dependent*) D ii.100; iii.58, 77; S v.154; **Dīpa**¹ [Ved. *dīpa* to Ved. *dī*, *dīpyate*; Idg. **deiGā* to shine (see *dibba*, *deva*); cp. Gr. $\delta \iota \alpha \lambda \omicron \varsigma$, $\delta \eta \lambda \omicron \varsigma$; see also *jotati*] a lamp J ii.104 (°*m jāleti* to light a l.); DhA ii.49 (id.), 94 (id.) -*acci* the flame of a lamp ThA 154; -*āloka* light of a l. J i.266; vi.391; DhA i.359; VvA 51; - (°*m*)*kara* making light, shining, illuminating Nd2 399 (=pabham *kara* Sn 1136; but cp. Dh 236 under *dīpa*2); Vism 203. -*tittira* a decoy partridge (cp. *dīpaka*°) J iii.64; -*rukkha* lit. lamp - tree, the stand of a lamp, candlestick DhA iv.120; -*sikhā* the flame (lit. crest) of a l. Vism 171; DhA ii.49. **Dīpa**² (m. & nt.) [Ved. *dvīpa*=*dvi*+*ap* (**sp.*) of *āpa* water, lit. "double - watered," between (two) waters] an island, continent (*mahā*°, always as 4); terra firma, solid foundation, resting - place, shelter, refuge (in this sense freq. combd w. *tāṇa lena* & *saraṇa* & expl. in Com. by *paṭiṭṭhā*) - (a) lit. island: S v.219; J iii.187; VvA 19; Mhvs vii.7, 41. - continent: *cattāro mahādīpā* S v.343; Vv 2010 (=VvA 104); VvA 19; PvA 74 etc. Opp. the 2000 *paritta* - *dīpā* the smaller islands KhA 133. - (b) fig. shelter, salvation etc. (see also *tāṇa*): S iii.42 (*atta*°+*attasaraṇa* etc., not with S Index to *dīpa*¹); v.154, 162 (id.) iv.315 (*maṇ*°, not to *dīpa*¹), 372; A i.55 sq. (+*tāṇa* etc.); Sn 501 (*atta*° selfreliant, self - supported, not with Fausböhl to *dīpa*¹), 1092, 1094, 1145 (=Sattāhā); Nd2 303; Dh 236 (°*m karohi*=*paṭiṭṭhā* PvA 87); Pv iii.19 (id. PvA 174); J v.501=vi.375 (*dīpaṇ* ca *parāyaṇaṇ*); Miln 84, 257 (*dhamma* - *dīpa*, *Arahantship*).
23. **Niṭṭha** (adj.) [Sk. *niṣṭha*, *ni*+°*tha*; cp. *niṭṭhā*1] *dependent* on, resting on, intent upon S iii.13 (*accanta*°); Nd1 263 (*rūpa*°).
24. **Adhīna** (adj.) (-°) [cp. Sk. *adhīna*] subject, *dependent* D i.72 (*atta*° & *para*°); J iv.112; DA i.217; also written *ādhīna* J v.350. See also under *para*.
25. **Dattūpajīvin** living on what is given by others, *dependent* on another's gift Sn 217; Miln 294.
26. **Paccaya** [fr. *paṭi*+*i*, cp. Ved. *pratyaya* & P. *pacceti*, *paṭicca*] lit. resting on, falling back on, foundation; cause, motive etc. See on term as t.t. of philosophy *Tikapattāhāna* I, foreword; J.P.T.S. 1916, 21 f.; Cpd. 42 sq. & esp. 259 sq. - 1. (lit.) support, requisite, means, stay. Usually with ref. to the 4 necessities of the *bhikkhu*'s daily life, viz. *cīvara*, *piṇḍapāta*, *senāsana*, (*gilānapaccaya* -) *bhesajja*, i. e. clothing, food as alms, a dwelling - place, medicine: see under *cīvara*. Sn 339 (*paccaya*=*gil*'na - *paccaya* SnA 342); Miln 336; Mhvs 3, 15. - 2. (applied) reason, cause, ground, motive, means, condition M i.259 (*yaṃ yad eva paccayaṃ paṭicca* by whatever cause or by whichever means); S ii.65; Nett 78 sq.; DA i.125; PvA 104. The four-fold cause (*catubbidho paccayo*) of *rūpa* (material form) consists of *kamma*, *citta*, *utu*, *āhāra*: Vism 600. Var. *paccayas* discussed at VbhA 166 sq. (twofold, with ref. to *paṭisandhi*), 183 (eightfold), 202, 205 sq. 254 (4). *sappaccaya* founded, having a reason or cause S v.213 sq.; A i.82; Nd2 *mūla*; Dhs 1084, 1437. - *yathā paccayaṃ karoti* do as he likes Nd2 p. 280=S iii. 33. Often coupled with *hetu*, e. g. at S iv.68 sq.; A. i.66; iv.151 sq.; D iii.284; Nd2 under *mūla*; Ps ii.116 sq., *paccaya* came to be distinguished from *hetu* as the genus of which *hetu* was the typical, chief species. I. e. *paccaya* became synonymous with our "relation," understood in a causal sense, *hetu* meaning condition, causal antecedent, and 23 other relations being added as special modes of causal-ity. Later still these 24 were held reducible to 4 *Tikp* 1 f. (and foreword); Cpd. 197. Cp. *Paṭṭhāna*. - Abl. *paccayā* as adv. by means of, through, by reason of, caused by D i.45 (*vedanā* °*taṇhā* etc., see *paṭicca* - *samuppāda*); M i.261 (*jātipaccayā*

- jarāmarañam); Pv i.52 (kamma°); iv.150 (tap°); PvA 147 (kamma°). - 3. ground for, belief, confidence, trust, reliance J i.118, 169; अपरा° without relying on anyone else S iii.83, 135; A iv.186, 210; PvA 226. - resting, relying, or *dependent* on someone else Nd1 321; usually neg. a° independent of another Vin i.12, 181 and passim.
27. **Bhoja** [lit. grd. of bhuñjati², to be sorted out, to be raised from slavery; thus also meaning "dependence," "training," from bhuj, to which belongs bhujissa] one who is getting trained, *dependent*, a freed slave, villager, subject. Only in cpds. like bhojisīyam [bhoja+isi+ ya=issariya] mastery over *dependence*, i. e. independence S i.44, 45; bhojāñīya a well - trained horse, a thoroughbred J i.178, 179; bhojaputta son of a villager J v.165; bhojarājā head of a village (- district) a subordinate king Sn 553=Th 1, 823. - In the latter phrase however it may mean "wealthy" kings, or "titled" kings (khattiyā bh - r., who are next in power to and serve on a rājā cakkavatti). The phrase is best taken as one, viz. "the nobles, royal kings." It may be a term for "vice - kings" or substitute - kings, or those who are successors of the king. The expln at SnA 453 takes the three words as three diff. terms and places bhojā= bhogiyā as a designation of a class or rank (=bhogga). Neumann in his trsln of Sn has "Königstämme, kühn and stolz," free but according to the sense. The phrase may in bhoja contain a local designation of the Bhoja princes (N. of a tribe), which was then taken as a special name for "king" (cp. Kaiser>Caesar, or Gr. β α σ ι λ ε ú ς). With the wording "khattiyā bhoja - rājāno anuyuttā bhavanti te" cp. M iii.173: "paṭirājāno te rañño cakkavattissa anuyuttā bhavanti," and A v.22: "kuḍḍarājāno" in same phrase. - Mrs. Rh. D. at Brethren, p. 311, trsls "nobles and wealthy lords."
28. **Vasa** (m. & nt.) [cp. Vedic vaśa; vaś to be eager, to desire] power, authority, control, influence S i.43, 240 (kodho vo vasam āyātu: shall be in your power; vasa=āñāpavattana K.S. i.320); M i.214 (bhikkhu cittam vasam vatteti, no ca cittassa vasena vattati: he brings the heart under his control, but is not under the influence of the heart); Sn 297, 315, 578, 586, 968; Sdhp 264. - The instr. vasena is used as an adv. in meaning "on account of, because" e. g. mahaggha - vasena mahāraha "costly on account of its great worth" PvA 77; cp. J i.94; PvA 36 (putta°); Mhvs 33, 92 (paṭisanthāra°). - Freq. in phrase vase (loc.) vattati to be in somebody's power J v.316 (te vase vattati), cp. M i.214 (cittassa vasena vattati) & 231 (vatteti te tasmim vaso have you power over that?); trs. vase vatteti to get under control, to get into one's power J iv.415 (attano vase vattetvā); v.316 (rājāno attano v. v.); DhA ii.14 (rājānam attano v. v.), cp. M i.214 (vasan vatteti) & PvA 89 (vasam vattento). - Note. The compn form in connection with kṛ and bhū is vasī° (q. v.). **ānuga** being in somebody's power, *dependent*, subjected, obedient Sn 332, 1095; J iii.224 (=vasavattin C.); Th 2, 375 (=kinkāra - paṭissāvin ThA 252); Sdhp 249.
29. **Samsita**² [pp. of sam+āri] *dependent* Sdhp 306.
30. **Sevaka** serving, following; a servant, *dependent* J ii.12, 125, 420; SnA 453. See vipakkha°.
31. **Nissita** (adj.) [Sk. nisṛita, pp. of nissayati, corresp. in meaning to Sk. āārita] hanging on, *dependent* on, inhabiting; attached to, supported by, living by means of, relying on, being founded or rooted in, bent on. As - ° often in sense of a prep.=by means of, on account of, through, esp. with pron. kim° (=why, through what) Sn 458; tam° (therefore, on acct. of this) S iv.102. - For combn with var. synonyms see Nd2 s. v. & cp. Nd1 75, 106. - S ii.17

(dvayam; cp. iii.134); iv.59, 365; v.2 sq., 63 sq.; A iii.128; Dh 339 (rāga °); Sn 752, 798, 910; J i.145; Nd1 283; Pv i.86 (sokaṃ hadaya° lying in); ii.66 (paṭhavi° supported by); Vbh 229; Nett 39 (° citta); Miln 314 (inhabiting); PvA 86 (māna °). - anissita unsupported, not attached, free, emancipated Sn 66, 363, 753, 849, 1069 (unaided); J i.158; Miln 320, 351. - Cp. apassita.

32. **Paṭicca-samuppāda** [p.+samuppāda, BSk. prāṭīya-samutpāda, e. g. Divy 300, 547] "arising on the grounds of (a preceding cause)" happening by way of cause, working of cause & effect, causal chain of causation; causal genesis, *dependent* origination, theory of the twelve causes. - See on this Mrs. Rh. D. in Buddhism 90 f., Ency. Rel. & Ethics, s. v. & KS ii., preface. Cpd. p. 260 sq. with diagram of the "Wheel of Life"; Pts. of Controversy, 390 f. - The general formula runs thus: Imasmiṃ sati, idaṃ hoti, imass' uppādā, idaṃ uppajjati; imasmiṃ asati, idaṃ na hoti; imassa nirodhā, idaṃ nirujjhati. This being, that becomes; from the arising of this, that arises; this not becoming, that does not become: from the ceasing of this, that ceases M ii.32; S ii.28 etc. The term usually occurs applied to dukkha in a famous formula which expresses the Buddhist doctrine of evolution, the respective stages of which are conditioned by a preceding cause & constitute themselves the cause of resulting effect, as working out the next state of the evolving (shall we say) "individual" or "being," in short the bearer of evolution. The respective links in this chain which to study & learn is the first condition for a "Buddhist" to an understanding of life, and the cause of life, and which to know forward and backward (anuloma - paṭilomaṃ manas' ākāsi Vin i.1) is indispensable for the student, are as follows. The root of all, primary cause of all existence, is avijjā ignorance; this produces sankhārā: karma, dimly conscious elements, capacity of impression or predisposition (will, action, Cpd.; synergies Mrs. Rh. D.), which in their turn give rise to viññāṇa thinking substance (consciousness, Cpd.; cognition Mrs. Rh. D.), then follow in succession the foll. stages: nāmarūpa individuality (mind & body, animated organism Cpd.; name & form Mrs. Rh. D.), saḷāyatana the senses (6 organs of sense Cpd.; the sixfold sphere Mrs. Rh. D.), phassa contact, vedanā feeling, taṅhā thirst for life (craving), upādāna clinging to existence or attachment (dominant idea Cpd.; grasping Mrs. Rh. D.), bhava (action or character Cpd.; renewed existence Mrs. Rh. D.), jāti birth (rebirth conception Cpd.), jarāmaraṇa (+soka - parideva - dukkhadomanass' ūpāyāsā) old age & death (+tribulation, grief, sorrow, distress & despair). The BSk. form is prāṭīya - samutpāda, e. g. at Divy 300, 547. The Paṭicca - samuppāda is also called the Nidāna ("basis," or "ground," i. e. cause) doctrine, or the Paccay' ākāra ("related - condition"), and is referred to in the Suttas as Ariya-nāya ("the noble method or system"). The term paccay' ākāra is late and occurs only in Abhidhamma - literature. - The oldest account is found in the Mahāpadāna Suttanta of the Dīgha Nikāya (D ii.30 sq.; cp. Dial. ii.24 sq.), where 10 items form the constituents of the chain, and are given in backward order, reasoning from the appearance of dukkha in this world of old age and death towards the original cause of it in viññāṇa. The same chain occurs again at S ii.104 sq. - A later development shows 12 links, viz. avijjā and sankhārā added to precede viññāṇa (as above). Thus at S ii.5 sq.- A detailed exposition of the P. - s. in Abhidhamma literature is the exegesis given by Bdhgh at Vism xvii. (pp. 517 - 586, under the title of Paññā - bhūmi - niddesa), and at VbhA 130 - 213 under the title of Paccayākāra - vibhanga. - Some passages selected for ref.: Vin i.1 sq.; M i.190, 257; S i.136; ii.1 sq., 26 sq., 42 sq., 70, 92 sq., 113 sq.; Ai.177; v.184; Sn. 653; Ud 1 sq.; Ps i.50 sq.; 144; Nett 22, 24, 32, 64 sq.; DA i.125, 126.

2.2 word 'Interdependence' in . . .

the English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989), these words, depict *interdepend*(ence / ent) - aññamaññāvalambana and aññamaññāvalambī.

the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the [link to online Pali dictionary at University of Chicago](#), *appears @ 3 different places*, which are as follows -

1. **Alaṃ** (indecl.) [Vedic araṃ. In meaning 1. alaṃ is the expanded continuation of Vedic araṃ, an adv. acc. of ara (adj.) suitable; fitly, aptly rightly fr. ṛ Cp. aṇṇava, appeti, ara. In meaning 2. alaṃ is the same as are] emphatic particle 1. in affirmative sentences: part. of assurance & emphasis = for sure, very much (so), indeed, truly. Note. In connection with a dat. or an infin. the latter only apparently depend upon alaṃ, in reality they belong to the syntax of the whole sentence (as dat. or inf. absolute). It is customary however (since the practice of the Pāli grammarians) to regard them as *interdependent* and interpret the construction as "fit for, proper" (= yuttaṃ Pāli Com.), which meaning easily arises out of the connotation of alaṃ, e.g. alaṃ eva kātum to be sure, this is to be done = this is proper to be done. In this sense (c. dat.) it may also be compd. with Vedic araṃ c. dat. - (a) (abs.) only in combn. with dat. or inf. (see c. & Note above). - (b.) (°-) see cpds. - (c.) with dat. or infin.: alaṃ antarāyāya for certain an obstacle M i.130 (opp. nālaṃ not at all); alaṃ te vipphaṣārāya you ought to feel sorry for it Vin ii.250; alaṃ vacanāya one says rightly S ii.18; alaṃ hitāya untold happiness DhA ii.41. - ito ce pi so bhavaṃ Gotamo yojana sate viharati alaṃ eva . . . upasankamitum even if he were 100 miles from here, (surely) even so (i. e. it is fit or proper even then) one must go to him D i.117 (expld. at DA i.288 by yuttam eva = it is proper); alaṃ eva kātum kalyāṇaṃ indeed one must do good = it is appropriate to do good Pv ii.923 (= yuttaṃ PvA 122); alaṃ puññāni kātave "come, let us do meritorious works" Vv 4415 (= yuttaṃ VvA 191). - 2. in negative or prohibitive sentences: part. of disapprobation reproach & warning; enough! have done with! fie! stop! alas! (etc. see are). - (a) (abs.) enough: nālaṃ thutum it is not enough to praise Sn 217; te pi na honti me alaṃ they are not enough for me Pv i.63. - (b) with voc.: alaṃ Devadatta mā te rucchi sanghabhedo "look out D. or take care D. that you do not split up the community" Vin ii.198; alaṃ Vakkali kin te iminā pūtikāyena diṭṭhena . . . S iii.120. - (c) enough of (with instr.): alaṃ ettakena enough of this, so much of that Miln 18; alaṃ me Buddhena enough for me of the Buddha = I am tired of the B. DhA ii.34.
2. **Ponobbhavikā** (causing rebirth) S iii.26; Ps ii.147, etc.; as a link in the chain of *interdependent* causation (see paṭiccasamuppāda): vedanā - paccayā taṇhā, taṇhā - paccayā upādānaṃ Vin i.1, 5; D ii.31, 33, 56, etc.;
3. **Dukkha** (adj. - n.) [Sk. duḥkha fr. duḥ - ka, an adj. formation fr. prefix duḥ (see du). According to others an analogy formation after sukha, q. v.; Bdgh (at Vism 494) expls dukkha as du+kha, where du=duḥ and kha=ākāsa. See also def. at Vism 461.] A. (adj.) unpleasant, painful, causing misery (opp. sukha pleasant) Vin i.34; Dh 117. Lit. of vedanā (sensation) M i.59 (°m vedanaṃ vediyamāna, see also below iii.1 e); A ii.116=M. i.10 (sarīrikāhi vedanāhi dukkhāhi). - Fig. (fraught with pain, entailing sorrow or trouble) of kāmā D i.36 (=paṭipīḷan - aṭṭhena DA i.121); Dh 186 (=bahudukkha DhA iii.240); of jāti M i.185 (cp. ariyasacca, below B I.); in combn dukkhā paṭipadā dandhābhīññā D iii.106; Dhs 176; Nett 7, 112 sq., cp. A ii.149 sq. ekanta° very painful, giving much pain S ii.173; iii.69. dukkhaṃ (adv.) with difficulty, hardly J i.215. B. (nt.; but pl. also dukkhā, e. g. S i.23; Sn 728; Dh 202, 203,

221. Spelling dukha (after sukha) at Dh 83, 203). There is no word in English covering the same ground as Dukkha does in Pali. Our modern words are too specialised, too limited, and usually too strong. Sukha & dukkha are ease and dis-ease (but we use disease in another sense); or wealth and illth from well & ill (but we have now lost illth); or wellbeing and ill-ness (but illness means something else in English). We are forced, therefore, in translation to use half synonyms, no one of which is exact. Dukkha is equally mental & physical. Pain is too predominantly physical, sorrow too exclusively mental, but in some connections they have to be used in default of any more exact rendering. Discomfort, suffering, ill, and trouble can occasionally be used in certain connections. Misery, distress, agony, affliction and woe are never right. They are all much too strong & are only mental (see Mrs. Rh. D. Bud. Psy. 83 - 86, quoting Ledi Sadaw). I. Main Points in the Use of the Word. - The recognition of the fact of Dukkha stands out as essential in early Buddhism. In the very first discourse the four so-called Truths or Facts (see *saccāni*) deal chiefly with dukkha. The first of the four gives certain universally recognised cases of it, & then sums them up in short. The five groups (of physical & mental qualities which make an individual) are accompanied by ill so far as those groups are fraught with āsavas and grasping. (*Pañc' upādānakkhandhā pi dukkhā*; cp. S iii.47). The second Sacca gives the cause of this dukkha (see *Taṇhā*). The third enjoins the removal of this *taṇhā*. And the fourth shows the way, or method, of doing so (see *Magga*). These *ariyasaccāni* are found in two places in the older books Vin i.10=S v.421 (with addition of *soka - parideva . . .* etc. [see below] in some MSS). Comments on this passage, or part of it, occur S iii.158, 159; with expln of each term (+*soka*) D i.189; iii.136, 277; M i.185; A i.107; Sn p. 140; Nd2 under *sankhārā*; It 17 (with *dukkhassa atikkama* for *nirodha*), 104, 105; Ps i.37; ii.204, 147; Pug 15, 68; Vbh 328; Nett 72, 73. It is referred to as *dukkha, samudaya, nirodha, magga* at Vin i.16, 18, 19; D iii.227; Nd2 304iib; as *āsavānaṃ khaya - ñāṇa* at D i.83; Vin iii.5; as *sacca* No. 1+*paṭiccasamuppāda* at A i.176 sq. (+*soka*^o); in a slightly diff. version of No. 1 (leaving out *appiyehi & piyehi*, having *soka*^o instead) at D ii.305; and in the formula *catunnaṃ ariyasaccānaṃ ananubodhā* etc. at D ii.90=Vin i.230. II. Characterisation in Detail. - 1. A further specification of the 3rd of the Noble Truths is given in the *Paṭicca-samuppāda* (q.v.), which analyses the links & stages of the causal chain in their *interdependence* as building up (anabolic=samudaya) &, after their recognition as causes, breaking down (katabolic=nirodha) the dukkha - synthesis, & thus constitutes the Metabolism of kamma; discussed e. g. at Vin 1; D ii.32 sq. =S ii.2 sq.; S ii.17, 20, 65=Nd2 680i.c; S iii.14; M i.266 sq.; ii.38; A i.177; mentioned e. g. at A i.147; M i.192 sq., 460; It 89 (=dukkhassa *antakiriya*). - 2. Dukkha as one of the 3 qualifications of the *sankhārā* (q. v.), viz. *anicca, d., anattā, evanescence, ill, nonsoul*: S i.188; ii.53 (*yad aniccaṃ taṃ dukkhaṃ*); iii.112 (id.) iii.67, 180, 222; iv.28, 48, 129 sq.; 131 sq. - *rūpe anicc' ānupassī* (etc. with *dukkh' & anatt'*) S iii.41. *anicca - saññā, dukkha*^o etc. D iii.243; A iii.334, cp. iv.52 sq. - *sabbe sankhārā aniccā* etc. Nd2 under *sankhārā*. - 3. Specification of Dukkha. The *Niddesa* gives a characteristic description of all that comes under the term dukkha. It employs one stereotyped explanation (therefore old & founded on scholastic authority) (Nd2 304i.), & one expln (304iii.) peculiar to itself & only applied to Sn 36. The latter defines & illustrates dukkha exclusively as suffering & torment incurred by a person as punishment, inflicted on him either by the king or (after death) by the guardians of purgatory (*niraya - pālā*; see detail under *niraya*, & cp. below III. 2 b). - The first expln (304i.) is similar in kind to the definition of d. as long afterwards given in the *Sāṅkhya* system (see *Sāṅkhya - kārikā - bhāṣya* of *Gauḍapāda* to stanza 1) & classifies

the various kinds of dukkha in the foll. groups: (a) all suffering caused by the fact of being born, & being through one's kamma tied to the consequent states of transmigration; to this is loosely attached the 3 fold division of d. as dukkha°, sankhāra°, vipariṇāma° (see below III. 1 c); - (b) illnesses & all bodily states of suffering (cp. ādhyātmikam dukkham of Sāṅkhya k.); - (c) pain & (bodily) discomfort through outward circumstances, as extreme climates, want of food, gnat - bites etc. (cp. ādhibhautikam & ādhidaivikam d. of Sk.); - (d) (Mental) distress & painful states caused by the death of one's beloved or other misfortunes to friends or personal belongings (cp. domanassa). - This list is concluded by a scholastic characterisation of these var. states as conditioned by kamma, implicitly due to the afflicted person not having found his "refuge," i. e. salvation from these states in the 8 fold Path (see above B I.). III. General Application, & various views regarding dukkha. - 1. As simple sensation (: pain) & related to other terms: (a) principally a vedanā, sensation, in particular belonging to the body (kāyika), or physical pain (opp. cetasika dukkha mental ill: see domanassa). Thus defined as kāyikam d. at D ii.306 (cp. the distinction between śarīram & mānasam dukkham in Sāṅkhya philosophy) M i.302; S v.209 (in def. of dukkhindriya); A ii.143 (sarīrikā vedanā dukkhā); Nett 12 (duvidham d.: kāyikam=dukkham; cetasikam= domanassam); Vism 165 (twofold), 496 (dukkhā aññam na bādhakam), 499 (seven divisions), 503 (kāyika); SnA 119 (sukham vā dukkham vā Sn 67=kāyikam sātāsātam). Bdgh. usually paraphrases d. with vaṭṭadukkhā, e. g. at SnA 44, 212, 377, 505. - (b) Thus to be understood as physical pain in combn dukkha+ domanassa "pain & grief," where d. can also be taken as the gen. term & dom° as specification, e. g. in cetasikam dukkham domanassam paṭisaṃvedeti A i.157, 216; iv.406; S ii.69; rāgajan d°m dom°m paṭisaṃvedeti A ii.149; kāmūpasamhitam d°m dom°m A iii.207; d°m dom°m paṭisaṃvediyati S iv.343. Also as cpd. dukkhadomanassānam atthangamāya A iii.326, & freq. in formula soka - parideva - d° - domanass - upāyāsā (grief & sorrow, afflictions of pain & misery, i. e. all kinds of misery) D i.36 (arising fr. kāmā); M ii.64; A v.216 sq.; It 89 etc. (see above B I. 4). Cp. also the combn dukkhī dummano "miserable and dejected" S ii.282. - (c) dukkha as "feeling of pain" forms one of the three dukkhatā or painful states, viz. d. - dukkhatā (painful sensation caused by bodily pain), sankhāra° id. having its origin in the sankhāra, vipariṇāma°, being caused by change S iv.259; v.56; D iii.216; Nett 12. (d) Closely related in meaning is ahita "that which is not good or profitable," usually opposed to sukha & hita. It is freq. in the ster. expression "hoti dīgharatta, ahitāya dukkhāya" for a long time it is a source of discomfort & pain A i.194 sq.; M i.332 D iii.157; Pug 33. Also in phrases anattāya ahitāya dukkhāya D iii.246 & akusalam . . . ahitāya dukkhāya samvattati A i.58. - (e) Under vedanā as sensation are grouped the 3: sukham (or sukhā ved.) pleasure (pleasant sensation), dukkham pain (painful sens.), adukkham-asukham indifference (indifferent sens.), the last of which is the ideal state of the emotional habitus to be gained by the Arahant (cp. upekhā & nibbidā). Their rôle is clearly indicated in the 4th jhāna: sukhassa pahānā dukkhassa pahānā pubbe va somanassadomanassānam atthangamā adukkham - asukham upekhā parisuddhim catuttham jhānam upasampajja viharati (see jhāna). - As contents of vedanā: sukham vediyati dukkham v. adukkham - asukham v. tasmā vedanā ti S iii.86, 87; cp. S ii.82 (vedayati). tisso vedanā: sukha, d°, adukkham - asukhā° D iii.275; S ii.53; iv.114 sq., 207, 223 sq., cp. M i.396; A i.173; iv.442; It 46, 47. yaṃ kiñc' āyam purisa - puggalo paṭisaṃvedeti sukham vā d°m vā a°m vā sabban tam pubbe katahetū ti=one's whole life - experience is caused by one's former kamma A i.173=M ii.217. - The combn (as complementary pair) of sukha+dukkha is very freq. for expressing the varying fortunes of life & personal experience as pleasure

& pain, e. g. n' âlam aññamaññassa sukhāya vā dukkhāya vā sukhadukkhāya vā D i.56=S iii.211. Thus under the 8 "fortunes of the world" (loka dhammā) with lābha (& a°), yasa (a°), pasamsā (nindā), sukha (dukkha) at D iii.260; Nd2 55. Regarded as a thing to be avoided in life: puriso jīvitukāmo . . . sukhakāmo dukkha - paṭikkūlo S iv.172, 188. - In similar contexts: D i.81≈; iii.51,109, 187; S ii.22, 39; iv.123 sq.; A ii.158 etc. (cp. sukha). 2. As complex state (suffering) & its valuation in the light of the Doctrine: (a) any worldly sensation, pleasure & experience may be a source of discomfort (see above, I.; cp. esp. kāma & bhava) Ps i.11 sq. (specified as jāti etc.); dukkham=mahabbhayaṃ S i.37; bhārādānaṃ dukkham loke bhāra - nikkhepanaṃ sukham (pain is the great weight) S iii.26; kāmānaṃ adhivacanaṃ A iii.310; iv.289; cp. A iii.410 sq. (with kāmā, vedanā, saññā, āsavā, kamma, dukkham). - (b) ekanta° (extreme pain) refers to the suffering of sinful beings in Niraya, & it is open to conjecture whether this is not the first & orig. meaning of dukkha; e. g. M i.74; A ii.231 (vedanaṃ vediyati ekanta - d°m seyyathā pi sattānerayikā); see ekanta. In the same sense: . . . upenti Roruvam ghoram cirarattam dukkham anubhavanti S i.30; niraya - dukkha Sn 531; pecca d°m nigacchati Sn 278, 742; anubhonti d°m kaṭuka - pphalāni Pv i.1110(=āpāyikaṃ d°m PvA 60); PvA 67; mahādukkham anubhavati PvA 43, 68, 107 etc. atidukkham PvA 65; dukkhato pete mocetvā PvA 8. - (c) to suffer pain, to experience unpleasantness etc. is expressed in foll. terms: dukkham anubhavati (only w. ref. to Niraya, see b); anveti Dh 1 (=kāyikaṃ cetasikaṃ vipāka - dukkham anugacchati DhA i.24), upeti Sn 728; carati S i.210; nigacchati M i.337; Sn 278, 742; paṭisaṃvedeti M i.313 (see above); passati S i.132 (jāto dukkhāni passati: whoever is born experiences woe); vaḍḍheti S ii.109; viharati A i.202; ii.95; iii.3; S iv.78 (passaddhiyā asati d°m v. dukkhino cittaṃ na samādhiyati); vedayati, vediyati, vedeti etc. see above III. 1 e; sayati A i.137. - (d) More specific reference to the cause of suffering & its removal by means of enlightenment: (a) Origin (see also above I. & II. 1): dukkhe loko patiṭṭhito S i.40; yaṃ kiñci dukkham sambhoti sabbaṃ sankhāra - paccayā Sn 731; ye dukkham vaḍḍhenti te na parimuccanti jātiyā etc. S ii.109; d°m ettha bhiiyo Sn 61, 584; yo paṭhavī - dhātuṃ abhinandati dukkham so abhin° Si i.174; taṇhā d°ssa samudayo etc. Nett 23 sq.; as result of sakkāyadiṭṭhi S iv.147, of chanda S i.22 of upadhi S ii.109, cp. upadhīnidānā pabhavanti dukkhā Sn 728; d°m eva hi sambhoti d°m tiṭṭhati veti ca S i.135. - (β) Salvation from Suffering (see above I.): katham dukkhā pamuccati Sn 170; dukkhā pamuccati S i.14; iii.41, 150; iv.205; v.451; na hi putto pati vā pi piyo d°ā pamocaye yathā saddhamma - savanaṃ dukkhā moceti paṇinaṃ S i.210; na appatvā lokantaṃ dukkhā atthi pamocanaṃ A ii.49. Kammakkhaya . . . sabbaṃ d°m nijjiṇṇam bhavissati M ii.217, cp. i.93. kāme pahāya . . . d°m na sevettha anattasamhitam S i.12=31; rūpaṃ (etc.) abhijānaṃ bhabbo d°kkhaya S iii.27; iv.89; d°m pariññāya sakhettavatthum Tathāgato arahati pūraḷāsam Sn 473. pajahati d°m Sn 789, 1056. dukkhassa samudayo ca atthangamo ca S ii.72; iii.228 sq.; iv.86, 327. - dukkhass' antakaro hoti M i.48; A iii.400 sq.; It 18; antakarā bhavāmasa Sn 32; antam karisanti Satthu sāsana - kāriṇo A ii.26; d°parikkhīṇam S ii.133; akiñcanaṃ nānupatanti dukkhā S i.23; sankhārānaṃ nirodhena n' atthi d°assa sambhavo Sn 731. - muniṃ d°assa pārayum S i.195=Nd2 136v; antagū 'si pāragū d°assa Sn 539. - sang' ātiko maccujaho nirūpadhi pahāya d°m apunabbhavāya S iv.158; ucchinnaṃ mūlaṃ d°assa, n' atthi dāni punabbhavo Vin i.231=D ii.91.

3 The Buddha, on depend / interdepend . . .

3.1 **imasmim sati, in . . . Bahudhātukasutta (Many Elements), Majjhima Nikāya (115 Middle Discourses)**

3.1.1 On foolishness & astuteness . . .

- **Pali** : ”*Yāni kānici, bhikkhave, bhayāni uppajjanti sabbāni tāni bālato uppajjanti, no paṇḍitato;* **English** : “Whatever dangers there are, all come from the foolish, not from the astute.
- **Pali** : *ye keci upaddavā uppajjanti sabbe te bālato uppajjanti, no paṇḍitato;* **English** : Whatever perils there are, all come from the foolish, not from the astute.
- **Pali** : *ye keci upasaggā uppajjanti sabbe te bālato uppajjanti, no paṇḍitato.* **English** : Whatever hazards there are, all come from the foolish, not from the astute.
- **Pali** : *Seyyathāpi, bhikkhave, naḷāgārā vā tiṇāgārā vā aggi mutto kūṭāgārānipi dahati ul-littāvalittāni nivātāni phusitaggaḷāni pihitavātapānāni;* **English** : It’s like a fire that spreads from a hut made of reeds or grass, and burns down even a bungalow, plastered inside and out, draft-free, with doors fastened and windows shuttered.
- **Pali** : *evameva kho, bhikkhave, yāni kānici bhayāni uppajjanti sabbāni tāni bālato uppajjanti, no paṇḍitato;* **English** : In the same way, whatever dangers there are, all come from the foolish, not from the astute.
- **Pali** : *ye keci upaddavā uppajjanti sabbe te bālato uppajjanti, no paṇḍitato;* **English** : Whatever perils there are, all come from the foolish, not from the astute.
- **Pali** : *ye keci upasaggā uppajjanti sabbe te bālato uppajjanti, no paṇḍitato.* **English** : Whatever hazards there are, all come from the foolish, not from the astute.
- **Pali** : *Iti kho, bhikkhave, sappatibhayo bālo, appatibhayo paṇḍito;* **English** : So, the fool is dangerous, but the astute person is safe.
- **Pali** : *saupaddavo bālo, anupaddavo paṇḍito;* **English** : The fool is perilous, but the astute person is not.
- **Pali** : *saupasaggo bālo, anupasaggo paṇḍito.* **English** : The fool is hazardous, but the astute person is not.
- **Pali** : *Natthi, bhikkhave, paṇḍitato bhayaṃ, natthi paṇḍitato upaddavo, natthi paṇḍitato upasaggo.* **English** : There’s no danger, peril, or hazard that comes from the astute.
- **Pali** : *Tasmātiha, bhikkhave, ‘paṇḍitā bhavissāma vīmaṃsakā’ti :* **English** : So you should train like this: ‘We shall be astute, we shall be inquirers.’”
- **Pali** : *evañhi vo, bhikkhave, sikkhitabban’ti.* **English** : Thus, mendicants, one should train like this.

3.1.2 qualification to be called 'astute, an inquirer'? : skill in the elements in the ∅ sense fields, ∅ dependent origination, and ∅ the possible & the impossible

- **Pali** : *Evam vutte, āyasmā ānando bhagavantam etadavoca;*; **English** : When he said this, Venerable Ānanda said to the Buddha,
- **Pali** : *"kittāvatā nu kho, bhante, paṇḍito bhikkhu 'vīmaṃsako'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?"*; **English** : "Sir, how is a mendicant qualified to be called 'astute, an inquirer'?"
- **Pali** : *"Yato kho, ānanda, bhikkhu dhātukusalo ca hoti, āyatanakusalo ca hoti, paṭiccasamuppādakusalo ca hoti, ṭhānāṭhānakusalo ca hoti -* **English** : *"Ānanda, it's when a mendicant is skilled in the elements, in the sense fields, in dependent origination, and in the possible and the impossible.*
- **Pali** : *ettāvatā kho, ānanda, paṇḍito bhikkhu 'vīmaṃsako'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *That's how a mendicant is qualified to be called 'astute, an inquirer'."*

3.1.3 qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'? ∅ 18 elements of consciousness

- **Pali** : *"Kittāvatā pana, bhante, 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?"*; **English** : "But sir, how is a mendicant qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'?"
- **Pali** : *"Aṭṭhārasa kho imā, ānanda, dhātuyo -* **English** : "There are, Ānanda, these eighteen elements:
- **Pali** : *cakkhudhātu, rūpadhātu, cakkhaviññāṇadhātu;* **English** : the elements of the *eye, sights, and eye consciousness;*
- **Pali** : *sotadhātu, saddadhātu, sotaviññāṇadhātu;* **English** : the *ear, sounds, and ear consciousness;*
- **Pali** : *ghānadhātu, gandhadhātu, ghānaviññāṇadhātu;* **English** : the *nose, smells, and nose consciousness;*
- **Pali** : *jivhādhātu, rasadhātu, jivhāviññāṇadhātu;* **English** : the *tongue, tastes, and tongue consciousness;*
- **Pali** : *kāyadhātu, phoṭṭhabbhadhātu, kāyaviññāṇadhātu;* **English** : the *body, touches, and body consciousness;*
- **Pali** : *manodhātu, dhammadhātu, manoviññāṇadhātu.* **English** : the *mind, ideas, and mind consciousness.*
- **Pali** : *Imā kho, ānanda, aṭṭhārasa dhātuyo yato jānāti passati -* **English** : *When a mendicant knows and sees these eighteen elements,*
- **Pali** : *ettāvatāpi kho, ānanda, 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *they're qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'."*

3.1.4 qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'? Ø 6 elements

- **Pali** : “*Siyā pana, bhante, aññopi pariyāyo, yathā 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?*
English : ”But sir, could there be another way in which a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'?”
- **Pali** : ”*Siyā, ānanda.* **English** : ”There could, Ānanda.
- **Pali** : *Chayimā, ānanda, dhātuyo* - **English** : There are these six elements -
- **Pali** : *pathavīdhātu, āpodhātu, tejodhātu, vāyodhātu, ākāśadhātu, viññāṇadhātu.* **English** : the elements of *earth, water, fire, air, space, and consciousness.*
- **Pali** : *Imā kho, ānanda, cha dhātuyo yato jānāti passati* - **English** : *When a mendicant knows and sees these six elements,*
- **Pali** : *ettāvatāpi kho, ānanda, 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *they're qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'.*”

3.1.5 qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'? Ø another 6 elements

- **Pali** : ”*Siyā pana, bhante, aññopi pariyāyo, yathā 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?*
English : ”But sir, could there be another way in which a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'?”
- **Pali** : ”*Siyā, ānanda.* **English** : ”There could, Ānanda.
- **Pali** : *Chayimā, ānanda, dhātuyo* - **English** : There are these six elements:
- **Pali** : *sukhadhātu, dukkhadhātu, somanassadhātu, domanassadhātu, upekkhādhātu, avijjādhātu.*
English : the elements of *pleasure, pain, happiness, sadness, equanimity, and ignorance.*
- **Pali** : *Imā kho, ānanda, cha dhātuyo yato jānāti passati* - **English** : *When a mendicant knows and sees these six elements,*
- **Pali** : *ettāvatāpi kho, ānanda, 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *they're qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'.*”

3.1.6 qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'? Ø another 6 elements

- **Pali** : “*Siyā pana, bhante, aññopi pariyāyo, yathā 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?*
English : ”But sir, could there be another way in which a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'?”
- **Pali** : ”*Siyā, ānanda.* **English** : ”There could, Ānanda.
- **Pali** : *Chayimā, ānanda, dhātuyo* - **English** : There are these six elements:
- **Pali** : *kāmadhātu, nekkhammadhātu, byāpādadhātu, abyāpādadhātu, vihiṃsādhātu, avihimsādhātu.*
English : the elements of *sensuality and renunciation, malice and good will, and cruelty and harmlessness.*

- **Pali** : *Imā kho, ānanda, cha dhātuyo yato jānāti passati* - **English** : *When a mendicant knows and sees these six elements,*
- **Pali** : *ettāvatāpi kho, ānanda, dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *they're qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'.*

3.1.7 qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'? Ø 3 elements

- **Pali** : *"Siyā pana, bhante, aññopi pariyāyo, yathā 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?"*
English : *"But sir, could there be another way in which a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'?"*
- **Pali** : *"Siyā, ānanda.* **English** : *"There could, Ānanda.*
- **Pali** : *Tisso imā, ānanda, dhātuyo* - **English** : *There are these three elements:*
- **Pali** : *kāmadhātu, rūpadhātu, arūpadhātu.* **English** : *the elements of the sensual realm, the realm of luminous form, and the formless realm.*
- **Pali** : *Imā kho, ānanda, tisso dhātuyo yato jānāti passati* - **English** : *When a mendicant knows and sees these three elements,*
- **Pali** : *ettāvatāpi kho, ānanda, 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *they're qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'.*
- **Pali** : *"Siyā pana, bhante, aññopi pariyāyo, yathā 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?"*
English : *"But sir, could there be another way in which a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'?"*

3.1.8 qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'? Ø 2 elements

- **Pali** : *"Siyā pana, bhante, aññopi pariyāyo, yathā 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?"*
English : *"But sir, could there be another way in which a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'?"*
- **Pali** : *"Siyā, ānanda.* **English** : *"There could, Ānanda.*
- **Pali** : *Dve imā, ānanda, dhātuyo* - **English** : *There are these two elements:*
- **Pali** : *saṅkhatādhātu, asaṅkhatādhātu.* **English** : *the conditioned element and the unconditioned element.*
- **Pali** : *Imā kho, ānanda, dve dhātuyo yato jānāti passati* - **English** : *When a mendicant knows and sees these two elements,*
- **Pali** : *ettāvatāpi kho, ānanda, 'dhātukusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *they're qualified to be called 'skilled in the elements'.*

3.1.9 qualified to be called 'skilled in the sense fields'?

- **Pali** : “*Kittāvatā pana, bhante, ’āyatanakusalo bhikkhū’ti alamvacanāyā*”*ti*? **English** : ”But sir, how is a mendicant qualified to be called ‘skilled in the sense fields’?”
- **Pali** : ”*Cha kho panimāni, ānanda, ajjhattikabāhirāni āyatanāni* - **English** : ”There are these six interior and exterior sense fields:
- **Pali** : *cakkhu ceva rūpā ca sotañca saddā ca ghānañca gandhā ca jivhā ca rasā ca kāyo ca phoṭṭhabbā ca mano ca dhammā ca*. **English** : the *eye and sights, the ear and sounds, the nose and smells, the tongue and tastes, the body and touches, and the mind and ideas*.
- **Pali** : *Imāni kho, ānanda, cha ajjhattikabāhirāni āyatanāni yato jānāti passati* - **English** : When a mendicant knows and sees these six interior and exterior sense fields,
- **Pali** : *ettāvatā kho, ānanda, ’āyatanakusalo bhikkhū’ti alamvacanāyā*”*ti*. **English** : they’re qualified to be called ‘skilled in the sense fields’.”

3.1.10 qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination'?

- **Pali** : ”*Kittāvatā pana, bhante, ’paṭiccasamuppādakusalo bhikkhū’ti alamvacanāyā*”*ti*? **English** : “But sir, how is a mendicant qualified to be called ‘skilled in dependent origination’?”
- **Pali** : ”*Idhānanda, bhikkhu evaṃ pajānāti* : **English** : ”It’s when a mendicant understands:
- **Pali** : *’imasmiṃ sati idaṃ hoti, imassuppādā idaṃ uppajjati*, **English** : ’When this exists, that is; due to the arising of this, that arises.
- **Pali** : *imasmiṃ asati idaṃ na hoti, imassa nirodhā idaṃ nirujjhati, yadidaṃ* - **English** : When this doesn’t exist, that is not; due to the cessation of this, that ceases. *That is* :
- **Pali** : *avijjāpaccayā saṅkhārā*, **English** : Ignorance is a condition for impressions.
- **Pali** : *saṅkhārapaccayā viññānaṃ*, **English** : Impressions are conditions for consciousness.
- **Pali** : *viññānapaccayā nāmarūpaṃ*, **English** : Consciousness is a condition for name and form.
- **Pali** : *nāmarūpapaccayā saḷāyatanāṃ*, **English** : Name and form are conditions for the six sense fields.
- **Pali** : *saḷāyatanapaccayā phasso*, **English** : The six sense fields are conditions for contact.
- **Pali** : *phassapaccayā vedanā*, **English** : Contact is a condition for feeling.
- **Pali** : *vedanāpaccayā taṇhā*, **English** : Feeling is a condition for craving.
- **Pali** : *taṇhāpaccayā upādānaṃ*, **English** : Craving is a condition for grasping.
- **Pali** : *upādānapaccayā bhavo*, **English** : Grasping is a condition for continued existence.
- **Pali** : *bhavapaccayā jāti*, **English** : Continued existence is a condition for rebirth.

- **Pali** : *jātipaccayā jarāmarañam sokaparidevadukkhadomanassūpāyāsā sambhavanti.* **English** : Rebirth is a condition for old age and death, sorrow, lamentation, pain, sadness, and distress to come to be.
- **Pali** : *Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti.* **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering originates.
- **Pali** : *Avijjāya tveva asesavirāganirodhā saṅkhāranirodho,* **English** : When ignorance fades away and ceases with nothing left over, choices cease.
- **Pali** : *saṅkhāranirodhā viññāṇanirodho,* **English** : When choices cease, consciousness ceases.
- **Pali** : *viññāṇanirodhā nāmarūpanirodho,* **English** : When consciousness ceases, name and form cease.
- **Pali** : *nāmarūpanirodhā saḷāyatananirodho,* **English** : When name and form cease, the six sense fields cease.
- **Pali** : *saḷāyatananirodhā phassanirodho,* **English** : When the six sense fields cease, contact ceases.
- **Pali** : *phassanirodhā vedanānirodho,* **English** : When contact ceases, feeling ceases.
- **Pali** : *vedanānirodhā taṇhānirodho,* **English** : When feeling ceases, craving ceases.
- **Pali** : *taṇhānirodhā upādānanirodho,* **English** : When craving ceases, grasping ceases.
- **Pali** : *upādānanirodhā bhavanirodho,* **English** : When grasping ceases, continued existence ceases.
- **Pali** : *bhavanirodhā jātinirodho,* **English** : When continued existence ceases, rebirth ceases.
- **Pali** : *jātinirodhā jarāmarañam sokaparidevadukkhadomanassūpāyāsā nirujjhanti.* **English** : When rebirth ceases, old age and death, sorrow, lamentation, pain, sadness, and distress cease.
- **Pali** : *Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa nirodho hoti.* **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering ceases.
- **Pali** : *Ettāvatā kho, ānanda, 'paṭiccasamuppādakusalo bhikkhū'ti alamvacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *That's how a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination'.*

3.1.11 qualified to be called 'skilled in the possible and impossible'?

- **Pali** : *"Kittāvatā pana, bhante, 'ṭhānāṭhānakusalo bhikkhū'ti alamvacanāyā'ti?"* **English** : "But sir, how is a mendicant qualified to be called 'skilled in the possible and impossible'?"
- **Pali** : *"Idhānanda, bhikkhu 'aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ diṭṭhisampanno puggalo kañci saṅkhāraṃ niccato upagaccheyya, netam ṭhānam vijjati'ti pajānāti; 'ṭhānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puthujjano kañci saṅkhāraṃ niccato upagaccheyya, ṭhānametaṃ vijjati'ti pajānāti* **English** : "It's when a mendicant understands : 'It's impossible for a person accomplished in

view to take any condition as permanent. That is not possible. But it's possible for an ordinary person to take some condition as permanent. That is possible.'

- **Pali** : 'aṭṭhānametaṃ anavaḷāso yaṃ diṭṭhisampanno puggalo kañci saṅkhāraṃ sukhato upagaccheyya, netāṃ thānaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti; 'thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puthujjano kañci saṅkhāraṃ sukhato upagaccheyya, thānametaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti; **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a person accomplished in view to take any condition as pleasant. But it's possible for an ordinary person to take some condition as pleasant.'
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavaḷāso yaṃ diṭṭhisampanno puggalo kañci dhammaṃ attato upagaccheyya, netāṃ thānaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti, 'thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puthujjano kañci dhammaṃ attato upagaccheyya, thānametaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a person accomplished in view to take anything as self. But it's possible for an ordinary person to take something as self.'
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavaḷāso yaṃ diṭṭhisampanno puggalo mātaraṃ jīvitā voropeyya, netāṃ thānaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti; 'thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puthujjano mātaraṃ jīvitā voropeyya, thānametaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a person accomplished in view to murder their mother. But it's possible for an ordinary person to murder their mother.'
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavaḷāso yaṃ diṭṭhisampanno puggalo pitaraṃ jīvitā voropeyya . . . pe . . . arahantaṃ jīvitā voropeyya, thānametaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti; **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a person accomplished in view to murder their father . . . or murder a perfected one. But it's possible for an ordinary person to murder their father . . . or a perfected one.'
- **Pali** : 'aṭṭhānametaṃ anavaḷāso yaṃ diṭṭhisampanno puggalo duṭṭhacitto tathāgatassa lohitāṃ uppādeyya, netāṃ thānaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti; 'thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puthujjano duṭṭhacitto tathāgatassa lohitāṃ uppādeyya, thānametaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a person accomplished in view to injure a Realized One with malicious intent. But it's possible for an ordinary person to injure a Realized One with malicious intent.'
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavaḷāso yaṃ diṭṭhisampanno puggalo saṅghaṃ bhindeyya, netāṃ thānaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti; 'thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puthujjano saṅghaṃ bhindeyya, thānametaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a person accomplished in view to cause a schism in the Saṅgha. But it's possible for an ordinary person to cause a schism in the Saṅgha.'
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavaḷāso yaṃ diṭṭhisampanno puggalo aññaṃ satthāraṃ uddiseyya, netāṃ thānaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti; 'thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puthujjano aññaṃ satthāraṃ uddiseyya, thānametaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a person accomplished in view to dedicate themselves to another teacher. But it's possible for an ordinary person to dedicate themselves to another teacher.'
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavaḷāso yaṃ ekissā lokadhātuyā dve arahanto sammāsambuddhā apubbaṃ acarimaṃ uppajjeyyūṃ, netāṃ thānaṃ vijjati' ti pajānāti; 'thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ ekissā lokadhātuyā eko arahaṃ sammāsambuddho uppajjeyya, thānametaṃ vijjati' ti

pajānāti. English : They understand: 'It's impossible for two perfected ones, fully awakened Buddhas to arise in the same solar system at the same time. But it is possible for just one perfected one, a fully awakened Buddha, to arise in one solar system.'

- **Pali** : '*Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ ekissā lokadhātuyā dve rājāno cakkavattino apubbaṃ acarimam uppajjeyyurū, netam thānam vijjati*'ti pajānāti; '*thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ ekissā lokadhātuyā eko rājā cakkavattī uppajjeyya, thānametaṃ vijjati*'ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for two wheel-turning monarchs to arise in the same solar system at the same time. But it is possible for just one wheel-turning monarch to arise in one solar system.'
- **Pali** : '*Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ itthī araham assa sammāsambuddho, netam thānam vijjati*'ti pajānāti; '*thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puriso araham assa sammāsambuddho, thānametaṃ vijjati*'ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a woman to be a perfected one, a fully awakened Buddha. But it is possible for a man to be a perfected one, a fully awakened Buddha.'
- **Pali** : '*Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ itthī rājā assa cakkavattī, netam thānam vijjati*'ti pajānāti; '*thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puriso rājā assa cakkavattī, thānametaṃ vijjati*'ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a woman to be a wheel-turning monarch. But it is possible for a man to be a wheel-turning monarch.'
- **Pali** : '*Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ itthī sakkattam kareyya . . . mārattam kareyya . . . brahmattam kareyya, netam thānam vijjati*'ti pajānāti; '*thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ puriso sakkattam kareyya . . . mārattam kareyya . . . brahmattam kareyya, thānametaṃ vijjati*'ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a woman to perform the role of Sakka, Māra, or the Divinity. But it is possible for a man to perform the role of Sakka, Māra, or the Divinity.'
- **Pali** : '*Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ kāyaduccaritassa iṭṭho kanto manāpo vipāko nibbatteyya, netam thānam vijjati*'ti pajānāti; '*thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ kāyaduccaritassa aniṭṭho akanto amanāpo vipāko nibbatteyya, thānametaṃ vijjati*'ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for a likable, desirable, agreeable result to come from bad conduct of body, speech, and mind. But it is possible for an unlikable, undesirable, disagreeable result to come from bad conduct of body, speech, and mind.'
- **Pali** : '*Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ vacīduccaritassa . . . pe . . . yaṃ manoduccaritassa iṭṭho kanto manāpo vipāko nibbatteyya, netam thānam vijjati*'ti pajānāti; '*thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ vacīduccaritassa . . . pe . . . yaṃ manoduccaritassa aniṭṭho akanto amanāpo vipāko nibbatteyya, thānametaṃ vijjati*'ti pajānāti. **English** :
- **Pali** : '*Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ kāyasucaritassa aniṭṭho akanto amanāpo vipāko nibbatteyya, netam thānam vijjati*'ti pajānāti; '*thānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ kāyasucaritassa iṭṭho kanto manāpo vipāko nibbatteyya, thānametaṃ vijjati*'ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible for an unlikable, undesirable, disagreeable result to come from good conduct of body, speech, and mind. But it is possible for a likable, desirable, agreeable result to come from good conduct of body, speech, and mind.'

- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ vacīsucaritassa . . . pe . . . yaṃ manosucaritassa aniṭṭho akanto amanāpo vipāko nibbatteyya, netam̐ ṭhānam̐ vijjati'ti pajānāti; 'ṭhānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ vacīsucaritassa . . . pe . . . yaṃ manosucaritassa iṭṭho kanto manāpo vipāko nibbatteyya, ṭhānametaṃ vijjati'ti pajānāti. **English** :
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ kāyaduccaritasamaṅgī taṃnidānā tappaccayā kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā sugatim̐ saggam̐ lokam̐ upapajjeyya, netam̐ ṭhānam̐ vijjati'ti pajānāti; 'ṭhānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ kāyaduccaritasamaṅgī taṃnidānā tappaccayā kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā apāyam̐ duggatim̐ vinipātam̐ nirayam̐ upapajjeyya, ṭhānametaṃ vijjati'ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible that someone who has engaged in bad conduct of body, speech, and mind, could for that reason alone, when their body breaks up, after death, be reborn in a good place, a heavenly realm. But it is possible that someone who has engaged in bad conduct of body, speech, and mind could, for that reason alone, when their body breaks up, after death, be reborn in a place of loss, a bad place, the underworld, hell.'
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ vacīduccaritasamaṅgī . . . pe . . . yaṃ manoduccaritasamaṅgī taṃnidānā tappaccayā kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā sugatim̐ saggam̐ lokam̐ upapajjeyya, netam̐ ṭhānam̐ vijjati'ti pajānāti; 'ṭhānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ vacīduccaritasamaṅgī . . . pe . . . yaṃ manoduccaritasamaṅgī taṃnidānā tappaccayā kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā apāyam̐ duggatim̐ vinipātam̐ nirayam̐ upapajjeyya, ṭhānametaṃ vijjati'ti pajānāti. **English** :
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ kāyasucaritasamaṅgī taṃnidānā tappaccayā kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā apāyam̐ duggatim̐ vinipātam̐ nirayam̐ upapajjeyya, netam̐ ṭhānam̐ vijjati'ti pajānāti; 'ṭhānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ kāyasucaritasamaṅgī taṃnidānā tappaccayā kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā sugatim̐ saggam̐ lokam̐ upapajjeyya, ṭhānametaṃ vijjati'ti pajānāti. **English** : They understand: 'It's impossible that someone who has engaged in good conduct of body, speech, and mind could, for that reason alone, when their body breaks up, after death, be reborn in a place of loss, a bad place, the under world, hell. But it is possible that someone who has engaged in good conduct of body, speech, and mind could, for that reason alone, when their body breaks up, after death, be reborn in a good place, a heavenly realm.'
- **Pali** : 'Aṭṭhānametaṃ anavakāso yaṃ vacīsucaritasamaṅgī . . . pe . . . yaṃ manosucaritasamaṅgī taṃnidānā tappaccayā kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā apāyam̐ duggatim̐ vinipātam̐ nirayam̐ upapajjeyya, netam̐ ṭhānam̐ vijjati'ti pajānāti; 'ṭhānañca kho etaṃ vijjati yaṃ vacīsucaritasamaṅgī . . . pe . . . yaṃ manosucaritasamaṅgī taṃnidānā tappaccayā kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā sugatim̐ saggam̐ lokam̐ upapajjeyya, ṭhānametaṃ vijjati'ti pajānāti. **English** :
- **Pali** : *Ettāvatā kho, ānanda, 'ṭhānāṭhānakusalo bhikkhū'ti alam̐vacanāyā'ti.* **English** : *That's how a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in the possible and impossible'.*

3.1.12 remember this exposition of the teaching as 'The Many Elements', or else 'The Four Rounds', or else 'The Mirror of the Teaching', or else 'The Drum of Freedom From Death', or else 'The Supreme Victory in Battle'

- **Pali** : *Evam̐ vutte, āyasmā ānando bhagavantam̐ etadavoca :* **English** : When he said this, Venerable Ānanda said to the Buddha,
- **Pali** : *"acchariyam̐, bhante, abbhutam̐, bhante.* **English** : *"It's incredible, sir, it's amazing!*

- **Pali** : *Konāmo ayaṃ, bhante, dhammapariyāyo*”ti? **English** : What is the name of this exposition of the teaching?”
- **Pali** : ”*Tasmātiha tvaṃ, ānanda, imaṃ dhammapariyāyaṃ ’bahudhātuko’tipi naṃ dhārehi, ’catuparivaṭṭo’tipi naṃ dhārehi, ’dhammādāso’tipi naṃ dhārehi, ’amatadundubhī’tipi naṃ dhārehi, ’anuttaro saṅgānavijayo’tipi naṃ dhārehi*”ti. **English** : ”Well then, Ānanda, you may *remember this exposition of the teaching as ’The Many Elements’, or else ’The Four Rounds’, or else ’The Mirror of the Teaching’, or else ’The Drum of Freedom From Death’, or else ’The Supreme Victory in Battle’.*”
- **Pali** : *Idamavoca bhagavā.* **English** : That is what the Buddha said.

3.2 **imasmim sati, in . . . Assutavāsutta (Unlearned), Mahāvagga, Saṃyutta Nikāya 12.61**

- **Pali** : ”*assutavā, bhikkhave, puthujjano imasmim cātumahābhūtikasmim kāyasmim nibbindeyyapi virajjeyyapi vimucceyyapi.* **English** : ”Mendicants, when it comes to this body made up of the four principal states, an unlearned ordinary person might become disillusioned, dispassionate, and freed.
- **Pali** : *Taṃ kissa hetu?* **English** : Why is that?
- **Pali** : *Dissati, bhikkhave, imassa cātumahābhūtikassa kāyassa ācayopi apacayopi ādānampi nikkhepanampi.* **English** : This body made up of the four principal states is seen to accumulate and disperse, to be taken up and laid to rest.
- **Pali** : *Tasmā tatrāssutavā puthujjano nibbindeyyapi virajjeyyapi vimucceyyapi.* **English** : That’s why, when it comes to this body, an unlearned ordinary person might become disillusioned, dispassionate, and freed.
- **Pali** : *Yañca kho etaṃ, bhikkhave, vuccati cittaṃ itipi, mano itipi, viññāṇaṃ itipi, tatrāssutavā puthujjano nālaṃ nibbindituṃ nālaṃ virajjituṃ nālaṃ vimuccituṃ.* **English** : But when it comes to that which is called ’mind’ and also ’sentience’ and also ’consciousness’, an unlearned ordinary person is unable to become disillusioned, dispassionate, or freed.
- **Pali** : *Taṃ kissa hetu?* **English** : Why is that?
- **Pali** : *Dīgharattañhetāṃ, bhikkhave, assutavato puthujjanassa ajjhositāṃ mamāyitaṃ parāmaṭṭhaṃ* : **English** : Because for a long time they’ve been attached to it, thought of it as their own, and mistaken it :
- **Pali** : *’etaṃ mama, esohamasmi, eso me attā’*ti. **English** : ’This is mine, I am this, this is my self.’
- **Pali** : *Tasmā tatrāssutavā puthujjano nālaṃ nibbindituṃ nālaṃ virajjituṃ nālaṃ vimuccituṃ.* **English** : That’s why, when it comes to this mind, an unlearned ordinary person is unable to become disillusioned, dispassionate, and freed.

- **Pali** : *Varam, bhikkhave, assutavā puthujjano imam cātumahābhūtikam kāyam attato upagaccheyya, na tveva cittaṃ.* **English** : But an unlearned ordinary person would be better off taking this body made up of the four principal states to be their self, rather than the mind.
- **Pali** : *Taṃ kissa hetu?* **English** : Why is that ?
- **Pali** : *Dissatāyam, bhikkhave, cātumahābhūtikā kāyo ekampi vassam tiṭṭhamāno dvepi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno tīṇipi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno cattāripi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno pañcapi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno dasapi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno viṣatipi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno tiṃsampi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno cattārisampi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno paññāsampi vassāni tiṭṭhamāno vassasatampi tiṭṭhamāno, bhīyyopi tiṭṭhamāno.* **English** : This body made up of the four principal states is seen to last for a year, or for two, three, four, five, ten, twenty, thirty, forty, fifty, or a hundred years, or even longer.
- **Pali** : *Yañca kho etaṃ, bhikkhave, vuccati cittaṃ itipi, mano itipi, viññāṇam itipi, taṃ rattiya ca divasassa ca aññadeva uppajjati aññaṃ nirujjhati.* **English** : But that which is called 'mind' and also 'sentience' and also 'consciousness' arises as one thing and ceases as another all day and all night.
- **Pali** : *Seyyathāpi, bhikkhave, makkhaṇo araṇṇe pavane caramāno sākhaṃ gaṇhati, taṃ muñcivā aññaṃ gaṇhati, taṃ muñcivā aññaṃ gaṇhati;* **English** : It's like a monkey moving through the forest. It grabs hold of one branch, lets it go, and grabs another; then it lets that go and grabs yet another.
- **Pali** : *evameva kho, bhikkhave, yamidaṃ vuccati cittaṃ itipi, mano itipi, viññāṇam itipi, taṃ rattiya ca divasassa ca aññadeva uppajjati aññaṃ nirujjhati.* **English** : In the same way, that which is called 'mind' and also 'sentience' and also 'consciousness' arises as one thing and ceases as another all day and all night.
- **Pali** : *Tatra, bhikkhave, sutavā ariyasāvako paṭiccasamuppādamyeva sādhucaṃ yoniso manasi karoti* : **English** : In this case, a learned noble disciple carefully and rationally applies the mind to dependent origination itself :
- **Pali** : *'iti imasmim sati idaṃ hoti, imassuppādā idaṃ uppajjati; imasmim asati idaṃ na hoti, imassa nirodhā idaṃ nirujjhati - yadidaṃ avijjāpaccayā saṅkhārā; . . .* **English** : 'When this exists, that is; due to the arising of this, that arises. When this doesn't exist, that is not; due to the cessation of this, that ceases. That is: Ignorance is a condition for choices . . .
- **Pali** : . . . **English** : . . .
- **Pali** : *evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa nirodho hoti'ti.* **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering ceases.'
- **Pali** : *Evaṃ passam, bhikkhave, sutavā ariyasāvako rūpasmiṃpi nibbindati, vedanāyapi nibbindati, saññāyapi nibbindati, saṅkhāresupi nibbindati, viññāṇasmimpi nibbindati;* **English** : Seeing this, a learned noble disciple grows disillusioned with form, feeling, perception, choices, and consciousness.
- **Pali** : *nibbindam virajjati, virāgā vimuccati, vimuttasmim vimuttamiti ñāṇam hoti.* **English** : Being disillusioned, desire fades away. When desire fades away they're freed. When they're freed, they know they're freed.

- **Pali** : 'K^hīⁿā j^ātī, vusita^m brahmacariya^m, kata^m karaⁿīya^m, nāpara^m itthattāyā'ti pajānā^{tī}'ti.
English : They understand : "Rebirth is ended, the spiritual journey has been completed, what had to be done has been done, there is nothing further for this place."

3.3 **imasmim sati, in . . . Ariyasāvakasutta (A Noble Disciple), Gahapativagga, Saṃyutta Nikāya 12.49**

- **Pali** : "Na, bhikkhave, sutavato ariyasāvakassa eva^m hoti : 'ki^m nu kho - kismi^m sati ki^m hoti, kissuppā^dā ki^m uppajjati? **English** : "Mendicants, a learned noble disciple doesn't think : 'When what exists, what is? Due to the arising of what, what arises?"
- **Pali** : Kismi^m sati saⁿkhā^rā honti, kismi^m sati viⁿñāⁿa^m hoti, kismi^m sati nāmarūpa^m hoti, kismi^m sati sa^lāya^tana^m hoti, kismi^m sati phassa hoti, kismi^m sati vedanā hoti, kismi^m sati taⁿhā hoti, kismi^m sati upā^dāna^m hoti, kismi^m sati bhavo hoti, kismi^m sati jā^ti hoti, kismi^m sati jarāma^raⁿa^m hoti'ti? **English** : When what exists do name and form come to be? When what exists do the six sense fields . . . contact . . . feeling . . . craving . . . grasping . . . continued existence . . . rebirth . . . old age and death come to be?
- **Pali** : Atha kho, bhikkhave, sutavato ariyasāvakassa aparappaccayā nāⁿamevettha hoti : **English** : Rather, a learned noble disciple has only knowledge about this that is independent of others :
- **Pali** : 'i^masmim sati ida^m hoti, imassuppā^dā ida^m uppajjati. **English** : 'When this exists, that is; due to the arising of this, that arises.
- **Pali** : Avijjāya sati saⁿkhā^rā honti; **English** : When ignorance exists choices come to be.
- **Pali** : saⁿkhā^resu sati viⁿñāⁿa^m hoti; **English** : When choices exist consciousness comes to be.
- **Pali** : viⁿñāⁿe sati nāmarūpa^m hoti; **English** : When consciousness exists name and form come to be.
- **Pali** : nāmarūpe sati sa^lāya^tana^m hoti; **English** : When name and form exist the six sense fields come to be.
- **Pali** : sa^lāyatane sati phassa hoti; **English** : When the six sense fields exist contact comes to be.
- **Pali** : phasse sati vedanā hoti; **English** : When contact exists feeling comes to be.
- **Pali** : vedanāya sati taⁿhā hoti; **English** : When feeling exists craving comes to be.
- **Pali** : taⁿhāya sati upā^dāna^m hoti; **English** : When craving exists grasping comes to be.
- **Pali** : upā^dāne sati bhavo hoti; **English** : When grasping exists continued existence comes to be.
- **Pali** : bhavo sati jā^ti hoti; **English** : When continued existence exists rebirth comes to be.

- **Pali** : *jātiyā sati jarāmarañam hotī'ti*. **English** : When rebirth exists old age and death come to be.'
- **Pali** : *So evaṃ pajānāti: 'evamayaṃ loko samudayati'ti*. **English** : They understand : 'This is the origin of the world.'
- **Pali** : *Na, bhikkhave, sutavato ariyasāvakassa evaṃ hoti* : **English** : A learned noble disciple doesn't think :
- **Pali** : *'kiṃ nu kho - kismiṃ asati kiṃ na hoti, kissa nirodhā kiṃ nirujjhati?* **English** : 'When what doesn't exist, what is not? Due to the cessation of what, what ceases?'
- **Pali** : *Kismiṃ asati saṅkhārā na honti, kismiṃ asati viññāṇam na hoti, kismiṃ asati nāmarūpaṃ na hoti, kismiṃ asati saḷāyatanaṃ na hoti, kismiṃ asati phasso na hoti, kismiṃ asati vedanā na hoti, kismiṃ asati taṇhā na hoti, kismiṃ asati upādānaṃ na hoti, kismiṃ asati bhavo na hoti, kismiṃ asati jāti na hoti, kismiṃ asati jarāmarañam na hotī'ti?* **English** : When what doesn't exist do choices not come to be? When what doesn't exist do name and form not come to be? When what doesn't exist do the six sense fields . . . contact . . . feeling . . . craving . . . grasping . . . continued existence . . . rebirth . . . old age and death not come to be?'
- **Pali** : *Atha kho, bhikkhave, sutavato ariyasāvakassa aparappaccayā ñāṇamevettha hoti* : **English** : Rather, a learned noble disciple has only knowledge about this that is independent of others :
- **Pali** : *'imasmim asati idaṃ na hoti, imassa nirodhā idaṃ nirujjhati*. **English** : 'When this doesn't exist, that is not; due to the cessation of this, that ceases.'
- **Pali** : *Avijjāya asati saṅkhārā na honti*; **English** : When ignorance doesn't exist choices don't come to be.
- **Pali** : *saṅkhāresu asati viññāṇam na hoti*; **English** : When choices don't exist consciousness doesn't come to be.
- **Pali** : *viññāṇe asati nāmarūpaṃ na hoti*; **English** : When consciousness doesn't exist name and form don't come to be.
- **Pali** : *nāmarūpe asati saḷāyatanaṃ na hoti . . . pe . . .* **English** : When name and form don't exist the six sense fields don't come to be . . .
- **Pali** : *bhavo na hoti . . .* **English** : continued existence doesn't come to be . . .
- **Pali** : *jāti na hoti . . .* **English** : rebirth doesn't come to be . . .
- **Pali** : *jātiyā asati jarāmarañam na hotī'ti*. **English** : When rebirth doesn't exist old age and death don't come to be.'
- **Pali** : *So evaṃ pajānāti* : **English** : They understand :
- **Pali** : *'evamayaṃ loko nirujjhati'ti*. **English** : 'This is the cessation of the world.'

- **Pali** : *Yato kho, bhikkhave, ariyasāvako evaṃ lokassa samudayañca atthaṅgamañca yathābhūtaṃ pajānāti, ayaṃ vuccati, bhikkhave, ariyasāvako diṭṭhisampanno itipi . . . pe . . .* **English** : A noble disciple comes to understand the world, its origin, its cessation, and the practice that leads to its cessation. Such a noble disciple is one who is called 'one accomplished in view', 'one accomplished in vision', 'one who has come to the true teaching', 'one who sees this true teaching', 'one endowed with a trainee's knowledge', 'one who has entered the stream of the teaching', 'a noble one with penetrative wisdom', and also 'one who stands knocking at the door to freedom from death'."

3.4 **imasmim sati, in . . . Dasabalasutta (The Ten Powers), Dasabalavagga Saṃyutta Nikāya 12.21**

- **Pali** : *"Dasabalasamannāgato, bhikkhave, tathāgato catūhi ca vesārajjehi samannāgato āsabhaṃ thānaṃ paṭijānāti, parisāsu sīhanādaṃ nadati, brahmacakkaā pavatteti -* **English** : "Mendicants, a Realized One has ten powers and four kinds of self-assurance. With these he claims the bull's place, roars his lion's roar in the assemblies, and turns the divine wheel.
- **Pali** : *iti rūpaṃ iti rūpassa samudayo iti rūpassa atthaṅgamo,* **English** : Such is form, such is the origin of form, such is the ending of form.
- **Pali** : *iti vedanā iti vedanāya samudayo iti vedanāya atthaṅgamo,* **English** : Such is feeling, such is the origin of feeling, such is the ending of feeling.
- **Pali** : *iti saññā iti saññāya samudayo iti saññāya atthaṅgamo,* **English** : Such is perception, such is the origin of perception, such is the ending of perception.
- **Pali** : *iti saṅkhārā iti saṅkhārānaṃ samudayo iti saṅkhārānaṃ atthaṅgamo,* **English** : Such are choices, such is the origin of choices, such is the ending of choices.
- **Pali** : *iti viññāṇaṃ iti viññāṇassa samudayo iti viññāṇassa atthaṅgamo.* **English** : Such is consciousness, such is the origin of consciousness, such is the ending of consciousness.
- **Pali** : *Iti imasmim sati idaṃ hoti, imassuppādā idaṃ uppajjati.* **English** : When this exists, that is; due to the arising of this, that arises.
- **Pali** : *Imasmim asati idaṃ na hoti, imassa nirodhā idaṃ nirujjhati. Yadidaṃ :* **English** : When this doesn't exist, that is not; due to the cessation of this, that ceases. That is :
- **Pali** : *avijjāpaccayā saṅkhārā;* **English** : Ignorance is a condition for choices.
- **Pali** : *saṅkhārapaccayā viññāṇaṃ . . . pe . . .* **English** : Choices are a condition for consciousness. . . .
- **Pali** : *evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti.* **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering originates.
- **Pali** : *Avijjāya tveva asesavirāganirodhā saṅkhāranirodho;* **English** : When ignorance fades away and ceases with nothing left over, choices cease.

- **Pali** : *saṅkhāranirodhā viññāṇanirodho . . . pe . . .* **English** : When choices cease, consciousness ceases. . . .
- **Pali** : *evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa nirodho hotī”ti.* **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering ceases.”

3.5 Paccayasutta (Conditions), Āhāravagga, Saṃyutta Nikāya 12.20

3.5.1 paṭicca samuppādo or dependent origination

- **Pali** : *”Paṭiccasamuppādañca vo, bhikkhave, desessāmi paṭiccasamuppanne ca dhamme.* **English** : “Mendicants, I will teach you dependent origination and dependently originated phenomena.
- **Pali** : *Taṃ suṇātha, sādhu kaṃ manasi karotha, bhāssissāmi”ti; ”Evaṃ, bhante”ti kho te bhikkhū bhagavato paccassosum̐ : Bhagavā etadavoca :* **English** : Listen and apply your mind well, I will speak.”; ”Yes, sir,” they replied!; The Buddha said this :
- **Pali** : *”Katamo ca, bhikkhave, paṭiccasamuppādo”?* **English** : ”And what is dependent origination?”
- **Pali** : *Jātipaccayā, bhikkhave, jarāmarañam̐.* **English** : Rebirth is a condition for old age and death.
- **Pali** : *Uppādā vā tathāgatānaṃ anuppādā vā tathāgatānaṃ, t̐hitāva sā dhātu dhammaṭṭhitatā dhammaniyāmatā idappaccayatā.* **English** : Whether Realized Ones arise or not, this law of nature persists, this regularity of natural principles, this invariance of natural principles, specific conditionality.
- **Pali** : *Taṃ tathāgato abhisambujjhati abhisameti. Abhisambujjhitvā abhisamtvā ācikkhati deseti paññāpeti paṭṭhapeti vivarati vibhajati uttānīkaroti.* **English** : A Realized One understands this and comprehends it, then he explains, teaches, asserts, establishes, clarifies, analyzes, and reveals it.
- **Pali** : *’Passathā’ti cāha :* **English** : ’Look,’ he says,
- **Pali** : *’jātipaccayā, bhikkhave, jarāmarañam̐’; Bhavapaccayā, bhikkhave, jāti . . . pe . . . upādānapaccayā, bhikkhave, bhavo . . . taṇhāpaccayā, bhikkhave, upādānam̐ . . . vedanāpaccayā, bhikkhave, taṇhā . . . phassapaccayā, bhikkhave, vedanā . . . saḷāyatanapaccayā, bhikkhave, phasso . . . nāmarūpapaccayā, bhikkhave, saḷāyatanaṃ . . . viññāṇapaccayā, bhikkhave, nāmarūpaṃ . . . saṅkhārapaccayā, bhikkhave, viññāṇam̐ . . . avijjāpaccayā, bhikkhave, saṅkhārā.* **English** : ’Rebirth is a condition for old age and death’; Continued existence is a condition for rebirth . . . Grasping is a condition for continued existence . . . Craving is a condition for grasping . . . Feeling is a condition for craving . . . Contact is a condition for feeling . . . The six sense fields are a condition for contact . . . Name and form are conditions for the six sense fields . . . Consciousness is a condition for name and form . . . Choices are a condition for consciousness . . . Ignorance is a condition for choices.

- **Pali** : *uppādā vā tathāgatānaṃ anuppādā vā tathāgatānaṃ, ̥hitāva sā dhātu dhammaṭṭhitatā dhammaniyāmatā idappaccayatā.* **English** : Whether Realized Ones arise or not, this law of nature persists, this regularity of natural principles, this invariance of natural principles, specific conditionality.
- **Pali** : *Taṃ tathāgato abhisambujjhati abhisameti; Abhisambujjhitvā abhisamtvā ācikkhati deseti paññāpeti paṭṭhapeti vivarati vibhajati uttānīkaroti.* **English** : A Realized One understands this and comprehends it, then he explains, teaches, asserts, establishes, clarifies, analyzes, and reveals it
- **Pali** : *'Passathā'ti cāha:* **English** : 'Look,' he says,
- **Pali** : *'avijjāpaccayā, bhikkhave, saṅkhārā'.* **English** : 'Ignorance is a condition for choices.'
- **Pali** : *Iti kho, bhikkhave, yā tatra tathatā avitathatā anaññathatā idappaccayatā -* **English** : So the fact that this is real, not unreal, not otherwise; the specific conditionality of it:
- **Pali** : *ayaṃ vuccati, bhikkhave, paṭiccasamuppādo.* **English** : *this is called dependent origination.*

3.5.2 paṭicca samuppannā dhammā or dependently originated phenomena

- **Pali** : *Katame ca, bhikkhave, paṭiccasamuppannā dhammā?* **English** : And what are the dependently originated phenomena?
- **Pali** : *Jarāmaṇaṃ, bhikkhave, aniccaṃ saṅkhataṃ paṭiccasamuppannaṃ khayadhammaṃ vayadhammaṃ virāgadhammaṃ nirodhadhammaṃ.* **English** : Old age and death are impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *Jāti, bhikkhave, aniccā saṅkhataṃ paṭiccasamuppannā khayadhammā vayadhammā virāgadhammā nirodhadhammā.* **English** : Rebirth is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *Bhavo, bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo.* **English** : Continued existence is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *Upādānaṃ bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo.* **English** : Grasping is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *taṇhā, bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo.* **English** : Craving is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *vedanā, bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo.* **English** : Feeling is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.

- **Pali** : *phasso, bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo* **English** : Contact is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *saḷāyatanāṃ, bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo* **English** : The six sense fields is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *nāmarūpaṃ, bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo* **English** : Name and form is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *viññāṇaṃ, bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo* **English** : Consciousness is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *saṅkhārā, bhikkhave, anicco saṅkhato paṭiccasamuppanno khayadhammo vayadhammo virāgadhammo nirodhadhammo* **English** : Choices is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *avijjā, bhikkhave, aniccā saṅkhatā paṭiccasamuppannā khayadhammā vayadhammā virāgadhammā nirodhadhammā.* **English** : Ignorance is impermanent, conditioned, dependently originated, liable to end, vanish, fade away, and cease.
- **Pali** : *Ime vuccanti, bhikkhave, paṭiccasamuppannā dhammā.* **English** : *These are called the dependently originated phenomena.*

3.5.3 What happens when one sees or grasps the teachings of paṭicca samuppādo or dependent origination & paṭicca samuppannā dhammā or dependently originated phenomena

- **Pali** : *Yato kho, bhikkhave, ariyasāvakaṃsa 'ayaṅca paṭiccasamuppādo, ime ca paṭiccasamuppannā dhammā' yathābhūtaṃ sammappañāya sudittā honti, so vata pubbantaṃ vā paṭidhāvissati :* **English** : When a noble disciple has clearly seen with right wisdom this dependent origination and these dependently originated phenomena as they are, it is quite impossible for them to turn back to the past, thinking :
- **Pali** : *'ahosiṃ nu kho ahaṃ atītamaddhānaṃ, nanu kho ahosiṃ atītamaddhānaṃ, kiṃ nu kho ahosiṃ atītamaddhānaṃ, kathaṃ nu kho ahosiṃ atītamaddhānaṃ, kiṃ hutvā kiṃ ahosiṃ nu kho ahaṃ atītamaddhānaṃ'ti;* **English** : 'Did I exist in the past? Did I not exist in the past? What was I in the past? How was I in the past? After being what, what did I become in the past?'
- **Pali** : *aparantaṃ vā upadhāvissati :* **English** : Or to turn forward to the future, thinking :
- **Pali** : *'bhavissāmi nu kho ahaṃ anāgatamaddhānaṃ, nanu kho bhavissāmi anāgatamaddhānaṃ, kiṃ nu kho bhavissāmi anāgatamaddhānaṃ, kathaṃ nu kho bhavissāmi anāgatamaddhānaṃ, kiṃ hutvā kiṃ bhavissāmi nu kho ahaṃ anāgatamaddhānaṃ'ti;* **English** : 'Will I exist in the future? Will I not exist in the future? What will I be in the future? How will I be in the future? After being what, what will I become in the future?'

- **Pali** : *etarahi vā paccuppannaṃ addhānaṃ ajjhataṃ kathaṅkathā bhavissati* : **English** : Or to be undecided about the present, thinking :
- **Pali** : *'ahaṃ nu khoṃsi, no nu khoṃsi, kiṃ nu khoṃsi, kathaṃ nu khoṃsi, ayaṃ nu kho satto kuto āgato, so kuhiṃ gamissatī'ti* - **English** : 'Am I? Am I not? What am I? How am I? This sentient being - where did it come from? And where will it go?'
- **Pali** : *netam thānaṃ vijjati. Tam kissa hetu ?* **English** : Why is that ?
- **Pali** : *Tathā hi, bhikkhave, ariyasāvakaṃ ayaṅca paṭiccasamuppādo ime ca paṭiccasamuppannā dhammā yathābhūtaṃ sammappaññāya sudīṭhā'ti.* **English** : Because that noble disciple has clearly seen with right wisdom this dependent origination and these dependently originated phenomena as they are."

4 The scientific experiment by Ben C. L. Yu (PhD in Psychology), Winnie W. S. MAK (with clinical training fellowship, Ph.D. in Clinical Psychology and postdoctoral training in clinical services research) and Floria H. N. Chio (Phd in Psychology), in Yu et al. (2020)

4.1 Before we begin . . .

Winnie W. S. Mak, the corresponding author of this manuscript, according to her CUHK webpage, is the director the of Diversity and Well-Being Laboratory and currently a Professor at the Department of Psychology, the Chinese University of Hong Kong. With a clinical training fellowship from the Minority Fellowship Program of the American Psychological Association, she obtained her Ph.D. in Clinical Psychology in 2000. Her predoctoral appointment of one year at the Florida Mental Health Institute at Tampa, for clinical internship was pivotal to her future directions in research and later she obtained postdoctoral training in clinical services research under the National Institute of Health National Research Service Award Postdoctoral Fellowship until 2002. These have led her to build research foundations in • Stigma and well-being of social minorities; • Stigma reduction; and • Promotion of mental health.

Further, co-authors **Ben C. L. Yu** and **Floria H. N. Chio** have obtained Phd in Psychology.

4.2 This work beginnings with . . .

some important list of articles that have been published regarding Mindfulness, which has found attention for scientific study, beginning with the work of Jon Kabat-Zinn, who introduced program called Mindfulness Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) which is a meditation therapy originally designed for stress management, while also being used for treating illnesses like depression, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, anxiety, chronic pain, cancer, skin and immune disorders, as reported in Niazi and Niazi (2011). A recent article by Landau and Jones (2021) concludes that secular Mindfulness-Based Programs (MBPs) appear to increase spirituality; these effects endure beyond the end of the MBP and they cannot wholly be attributed to non-specific therapeutic factors and provide limitations of the study!

As a further note, Jon Kabat-Zinn, in his own work in Kabat-Zinn (2017) states -

I would say that the same is true of the mainstreaming of mindfulness in the world as both a practice and a way of being. **In terms of the work of MBSR (mindfulness-based stress reduction), to say it right off the bat, since it is increasingly questioned by people unfamiliar with it in practice, the mainstreaming of mindfulness in the world has always been anchored in the ethical framework that lies at the very heart of the original teachings of the Buddha** (Crane et al. (2013)). Sila, meaning "virtue" or "moral conduct" in the Pali language, is represented by the third, fourth, and fifth factors of the **Eightfold Path (the fourth of the Four Noble Truths):** wise/right speech, wise/right action, and wise/right livelihood. **While MBSR does not, nor should it, explicitly address these classical foundations in a clinical context with patients, the Four Noble Truths have always been the soil in which the cultivation of mindfulness via MBSR and other mindfulness-based programs (MBPs) is rooted, and out of which, it grows through ongoing practice.** More on this to follow, in terms of the both Hippocratic Oath and the Bodhisattva Vow. **Parenthetically, MBSR was also designed from the beginning as a vehicle of right livelihood for the people who would be drawn to become MBSR instructors** (Crane et al. (2017)).

Finally, in their book by Kathirasan and Rai (2023), the authors present the often-neglected Asian roots of Mindfulness and justify how secular Mindfulness, as has been imparted by Jon Kabat-Zinn, is influenced by multiple wisdom traditions as opposed to it being a solely Buddhist practice and state that **his practice of Vipassanā, hatha yoga, and appreciation of the teachings of Advaita Vedanta and Soto Zen, led him to integrate their teachings with scientific findings.**

Lastly, Jon Kabat-Zinn is one of the Founding Steward, who along with Dalai Lama, opened the Mind & Life Institute, which is a US-registered, not-for-profit 501(c)(3) organization founded in 1991 to establish the field of contemplative sciences.

This background should be sufficient enough for anyone to know about any scientific study of Mindfulness, which is based on Buddhist teachings.

4.3 On interconnectedness . . .

The authors state that Interconnectedness is a central tenet underlying all Buddhist teachings and state the translation of Nanamoli and Bodhi (1995), on page 655 -

When there is this, that comes to be; with the arising of this, that arises. When there is not this, that does not come to be; with the cessation of this, that ceases

which in the Majjhima Niāya (115), Bahudhātukasutta (Many Elements), the Buddha said (and according to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago) -

- **Pali** : *'imasmim sati idam hoti, imassuppādā idam uppajjati,* **English** : This being, that becomes; from the arising of this, that arises;
- **Pali** : *imasmim asati idam na hoti, imassa nirodhā idam nirujjhati.* - **English** : this not being, that does not become: from the ceasing of this, that ceases.

To explain this, the authors provides an example of a growth of an apple tree which requires the right conditions of suitable climate, adequate sunshine, moisture, and nutrients from the soil in order to grow and bear fruit. Any condition missing or not in the appropriate amount may lead to a different outcome and simply having a seed cannot bear fruit to an apple tree.

My limited grasp - It is because of the Teacher the Buddha, after his appearance in existence and his work during his life time and after his extinguishment, of what was recorded . . . it is there that is why all this present day research work is happening. The Teacher the Buddha, is the cause of my writing this article . . . If the Teacher the Buddha, was not there at all in existence, in the first place, at some point in time and space . . . this article which i have drafted might not have become! So, if i take the extracts of the above sutta, '*imasmiñ sati idaṃ hoti, imassuppādā idaṃ uppajjati*, This being, that becomes; from the arising of this, that arises; *imasmiñ asati idaṃ na hoti*, - this not being, that does not become: . . . MAY BE . . . HOLDs!

4.4 On clinging, attachment and mindfulness . . .

Next the authors give a range of references that point to the fact that according to traditional Buddhist teachings, suffering arises when people cling to matters, be it experiences, self-images, objects, events, or people that are desirable to them.

Further, the authors point to the work of Sik (2010) which talks about the alleviation of suffering via the realization of interconnectedness, which brings people to the awareness that all phenomena are coalescence of different causes and conditions that are subject to change as there is no intrinsic existence of an entity or an actual "self", in the words of Yu et al. (2020).

Further, Yu et al. (2020) state the following -

With this awareness, people understand that objects *do not exist permanently* per se and therefore be freed from any form of clinging including the attachment to one's sense of self. By such, interconnectedness can have the potential to reduce both individual suffering and promoting social equalities by reducing people's tendency to crave for matters that are favorable to themselves and reject matters that are undesirable to themselves. In other words, interconnectedness could facilitate individual and collective well-being through the reduction of clinging.

In a preprint, titled - **Grasping the principles of anicca (impermanence), dukkha (sorrow/misery), anattā (non-self), suññatā (emptiness) & tathāgata (the one who has gone by as it is or yathābhūta) via ānāpāna : From pariyatti (theory), to paṭipatti (practice) to paṭivedha (attainment)**, available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/x7djz>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i have tried to clear some points on anicca (impermanence), dukkha (sorrow/misery), anattā (non-self), suññatā (emptiness) & tathāgata (the one who has gone by as it is or yathābhūta) via ānāpāna). To maintain the flow of this work, i here briefly quote the abstract of my preprint as follows -

Ānāpāna or the observation of the flow of the natural breath, is a fundamental step, before entering the field of *Vipassanā*, as the Buddha imparted. In this article, i share limited grasp of what has come to awareness, in meditations, over a small period of 10/12 years now, regarding the principles of anicca (impermanence), dukkha (sorrow/misery),

anattā (non-self), suññatā (emptiness) & tathāgata (the one who has gone by as it is or yathābhūta) through the practice of ānāpāna. This article can/should be read along with the article titled **ĀNĀPĀNA (OBSERVING THE FLOW OF NATURAL BREATH) & ESTABLISHING IN THE PRESENT MOMENT** available at <https://osf.io/v562c>. In the Dhajagga Paritta Chant from ? (under [Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0](#)), the following is quoted - *Pali* : *Svākkhāto bhagavatā dhammo, Sandiṭṭhiko akāliko ehipassiko, Opanayiko paccattaṃ veditabbo viññūhīti* (English : The Dhamma is well-expounded by the Blessed One, to be seen here and now, timeless, inviting all to come and see, pertinent, to be seen by the observant for themselves).

Secondly, the authors also relate to nonattachment, that has been demonstrated to be conducive to better well-being and they bolster the support of this demonstration via reference to some published articles in this area.

Finally, the authors mention of mindfulness, which also shares close theoretical relationship with nonattachment. The authors quote Thera (1960), whose work deals with mindfulness of breathing or the anapana-sati, as a basis for further development of samatha and vipassana, which leads to nonattachment to free people from suffering. Further, diving deeper, the authors point to Martin (1997), who considered nonattachment as one of the characteristics of mindfulness, but later, Sahdra et al. (2016) demonstrated that mediation models showed that nonattachment substantially mediated the links between the mindfulness facets and the outcome variables of satisfaction with life and life effectiveness, thus showing empirically that nonattachment is an outcome of mindfulness practice. Also, in the same study, Sahdra et al. (2016) found that the total effects of describing and nonre-activity, which are the dimensions of mindfulness operationalized in the Five Facets Mindfulness Questionnaire (FFMQ) by Baer et al. (2006), on both life satisfaction and life effectiveness were substantially accounted for by nonattach- ment.

4.4.1 My limited grasp on cling (/ing) ⊕ āsajjati; allīyati; laggati; nivasati; āsatta; allīna; lagga; nivitta; /sajjana; laggana; visatta; pagiddha . . . as in English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989)

In a preprint, titled - **Upādāna (grip/clinging) leads to dukkha (misery) and its paññāya (realization) leads to vimutti (release)**, available @ <https://osf.io/je9k6>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i have tried to clear some points on grip or clinging. To maintain the flow of this work, i here briefly quote the abstract of my preprint as follows -

Upādāna or clinging, is one of the 12 nidāna or links/causes, in the paṭicca-samuppāda Sutta or the causal genesis/dependent origination, that the Buddha expounded, which leads to samudaya or arising/bursting forth of khandha or bulks/chunks of dukkha or misery/sorrow in the flow of life. In this article, i try to convey whatever limited has come to awareness, regarding how upādāna leads to dukkha and its paññāya leads to vimutti. More specifically, we go through the theory of paticca-samuppāda sutta in context of upadana and how through vipassanā meditation, paññāya happens about the essence of upadana, which leads to vimutti. Thus, in a pedagogical manner, i try to take the reader from pariyatti or theoretical study to paṭipatti or practice. This theoretical

study involves insights that came to my limited grasp in meditations and the teachings of the Buddha, as has been documented in Pali. Regular, sustained, long term personal paṭipatti or practice, leads one to paṭivedha or piercing/penetrating the theory by experiential knowledge of the truth behind what is being stated, which is bhāvanā or developing by means of meditation - maya or accomplished by culture practice - pañña or wisdom/insight, i.e wisdom born through the practice of meditation. Finally, in this article the first three sections are essence, i could grasp and the next two sections contains the documentations of the Buddha's teachings.

4.4.2 My limited grasp on nonattachment 𑖀 nissaṅga, alaggana, arati . . . as in English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989))

One step further, when there is nonattachment, then only renunciation can happen. But first, nonattachment also means dispassion (Pali - *Vairāgya*).

The word *Dispassion*, according to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, appears in *Virāga* (Page 703), *Viratta* (Page 702), *Nekkhamma-dhātu* (Page 421), *Nibbidā* (Page 408), *Nibbāna-nekkhamma* (Page 406), *Anicchā* (Page 40); while in *English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989)*, depicts these words on Page 149 as *dispassion* : (m.) *virāga*. (f.) *nirāsā*. *dispassionate* : (adj.) *viratta*; *upekkhaka*. *dispassionately* : (adv.) *virattākārena*.

In this context, in a preprint, titled - **Vairāgya (dispassion) and its mechanics**, available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/9ng2q>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i have mentioned about the dispassion and its mechanics. To maintain the flow of this work, i here briefly quote the abstract of my preprint as follows -

Vairāgya (dispassion), the most hated by the materialistically minded or the *Sāmsārika* and the most valued by those in the spiritual realm or the *Adhyātmika*. *Vairāgya* comes from *Virāga*, where *Vi* means "without" and *rāga* means "passion". The Digital Dictionaries of South Asia (hosted at [Link to DSAL](#)) defines *Virāga* as • change of disposition, disaffection, discontent, dissatisfaction, • aversion, disinclination or • indifference to worldly attachments, freedom from passion. Here, i try to share my limited insights into • *Vairāgya*, possibly its mechanics; • How *Vairāgya* gives immense happiness? and • a few references in the existing treatise on the teachings of the Buddha, the *Yoga-Vasistha* and the *Patanjali Yog Sutras*.

The word *Renunciation*, according to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, appears in *Vilokana* (page 705), *Mahā-abhinikkhamāṇa* (page 584), *Pariccāga* (page 473), *Paṭinissagga* (page 441), *Nekkhamma* (page 421), *Nikkhamati* (page 395), *Cāga* (page 297), *Kāma* (page 229), *Kaḍḍhana* (page 201) and *Abhinikkhamana* (page 76); while in *English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989)*, depicts these words on Page 441 as *renounce* : (v.t.) *pajahati*; *pariccajati*; *nissajati*; *paccakkhāti*; *alan ti vadati*. (pp.) *pajahita*; *pariccatta*; *nissatṭha*; *paccakkhāta*; *alan ti vutta*; *renouncement* : (nt.) *paccakkhāna*. (m.) *paṭinissagga*.

Regrading renunciation - Just observe the grip of samsara, this nature, including your own mind, body, intellect, ego, on the life within you. The ability to let go of the grip/feverishness of the samsara, nature, storms in mind/body complex, in awareness, is renunciation. As soon as things arise in awareness, we are caught up in storm. But as we observe patiently, the grip/feverishness loosens its affect on the life and the mind/body complex cools down and there is peace. And it is not only the storms that arise in mind/body complex. There are patterns and modifications in mind also which disturb us from time to time. Renunciation is letting go of that grip/feverishness in mind/body.

Now often it is quoted that Siddhartha renounced everything, went to the forest and he searched for the truths of life, while living a life of an ascetic and devoted to meditations. Giving this example, lives of many people in evolution are compared to that of the Buddha. You see the final life of Siddhartha in which he attained the state of the Buddha, but you fail to see the long countless lives he passed through in evolution, many a times practicing renunciation both in mind and physically, as much as he could, depending on the capacity of his mind and body, in a particular life time. To say, that one should renounce immediately in mind and body and go to a forest and live that kind of life, is impractical and immature. The first thing is, you will get badly hurt at mental level, if you cannot renounce mentally; the physical renunciation is the after affect, but can you renounce mentally, in the first instance? It is not about wanting! Can you let go in the mind in the first instance? Siddhartha acquired a lot of things in a lot of lives, in the hope that what he had acquired would give him lasting peace; however, his heart did not find fulfilment in each life he lived, before the final life as a Buddha. See there has to be fulfilment in the heart; there has to be contentment in the heart; that yes, i have done everything i had to, in the best possible manner i could. Then renunciation happens by itself, naturally, in heart and mind. The ability of a being to let go, of things in awareness, as and when it is needed, requires practice as well as maturity in heart and mind. And this develops over lifetimes. The Jataka or stories of the Buddha's former births [Vol 1 to 3] By Professor Cowell et al. (1895-1907); has recorded stories of past lives of Siddhartha, when many a times, after fulfilling the duties of life, he renounced and choose to live a life of a reclusive ascetic. In those lives, when he was not a Buddha, his heart had still recognised that there was misery in life, and to find solace and peace, he had renounced after fulfilling his duties in life. He had practiced renunciation life after life, to develop his mind and body to absorb and experience the knowledge of the higher dimensions of the absolute truth. It is like the leaf in a tree that becomes ripe and then drops of automatically without force. This is effortless. However, there are other leaves which remain intact and do not ripe. They fall of because of some force of nature or the other. So renunciation happens naturally. Phenomena / events, material things and beings, grip our heart s and minds and minds, and we cannot let go! That is not renunciation.

Many have this conception of becoming an all powerful Buddha. This is ok and might be a wonderful aim. However, in my limited grasp, Siddhartha as the Buddha never wished to exist perennially for aeons, after crossing the stage of full liberation. Siddhartha knew that his journey in existence was over as the Buddha. He asked Ananda indirectly 3 times, if he should exist or not, but Ananda remained silent. Thus the Buddha realised that his time had come and in moments of death, he renounced everything, even Godhead or God's power and willingly gave up the choice of existence and merged into the absolute truth of Shunyata, in Parinirvana. This is the highest renunciation, that is, to willingly be erased in absolute truth and not keep one's limited identity and entity in existence. The closure of the journey and the final quenching. Then, only the absolute truth is ... For deeper insights, read article on Parinirvana @ <https://osf.io/q56dj>.

Finally, in Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada, Buddhavagga, Māradhitaravatthu, Devorohaṇavatthu

Ye jhānapasutā dhirā, nekkhammūpasame ratā, devā pi tesam pihayanti, sambuddhānam satimataṃ.

Those wise ones intent on meditation, who delight in the peace of renunciation, even the gods are envious of them, the Sambuddhas, the ones who are mindful.

4.4.3 My limited grasp on mind (/ cognition / ful / fully / fulness / less / made) ⊖ citta; mana; mānasa; saṅkappa; cinteti; manasikaroti; avekkhati; cintita; manasikata; avekkhita; / manoviññāṇa / satimantu; sāvadhāna; sampajāna / sāvadhānam / appamāda; satisampajāṇṇa / anavadhāna; pamatta; / manomaya . . . as in English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989)

The word **Mind**, according to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago), appears in Sara⁴-saṅkappa (Page 772), Sammā²-sati (Page 770), Sati-maraṇasati / ādhīpateyya / indriya / paṭṭhāna / saṁvara / sampajāṇṇa / sammosa & Satitā (Page 745), Vipavāsa (Page 697), Saṁvara (Page 728), Muṭṭha (Page 595), Micchā-sati (Page 591), Maraṇa-ānussati / sati (Page 582), Magga (Page 569), Bojjhanga-sati / dhamma-vicaya / viriya / pīti / passaddhi / samādhī / upekkhā (Page 545), Buddha²-ānussati (Page 544), Parimukha (Page 480), Paṭissati (Page 448), Paṭṭhāna-sati^o (Page 449), Paṭisankhāna (Page 446), Dhāraṇatā (Page 382), Ogha (Page 186), Upekkhā & Upekkhā (Page), Abhiññā¹ (Page 74) and Anussati (Page 53).

Mind Full - The funny part - There is a story! Once a man went to a wise man or master and started gloating over his knowledge that he had acquired in front of the wise man/master. The master kept listening and then suddenly broke in between and quipped - "Would you like to have some tea?" The man said - Yes! The master then started pouring tea into the empty cup! However, the master did not stop. Kept on pouring the tea into the cup, even when the cup was full! The man for some time looked at the master and said to him - Are you mad or what? Can't you see that the cup is already full long time back and everything is getting wasted or flowing down? The master stopped and said - EXACTLY! Your cup or mind is ALREADY filled to the brim! What will enter in your mind when you are just GLOATING over what is already there? There is NO ROOM for anything! And you will never grasp anything with a mind which is FULL!

In that context, in a preprint, titled - **Prajna-Paramita-Hridaya/the Heart Sutra: Bhagavati, the Heart of Transcendental Knowledge**, by Sinha (2017) available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/6zpsv>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i have mentioned something that is recorded in the Tibetan text. To maintain the flow of this work, i here briefly quote the section of my preprint as follows -

subsection - **T. Di ke dak gi to pa du chik na/**

T. Thus have i heard at one time :

N. "Thus have i heard ..." - **Who can hear?** The one whose mind is empty. If the mind is filled with all sorts of information and impressions, then the cup is already filled up.

If one pours more water in it then what is being poured will only overflow. Thus the need for emptiness is a necessary to in order to hear.

Regarding Mindfulness - Again, in this context, in a preprint, titled - **The afflictions of mind and a way out**, available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/8zth7>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i have mentioned about the afflictions of the mind. To maintain the flow of this work, i here briefly quote the abstract of my preprint as follows -

The mind (*chitta*), though cannot be seen, is there. It has thought processes and it gallops on those thought processes. Matter (or material), beings and events (or phenomena) affects the mind from time to time. One is bombarded by the affects these have on the mind and the thoughts that come out as a reaction as well as passing thoughts either of past or future, makes the mind run. Thus there is a constant run. And if that is not the case, previous impressions (*sankhara*) in the mind, makes one follow a particular line of thought. Patterns of mind form, that can remain for life time. Apart from these the deeper afflictions of mind include delusion, doubts, deception, trauma, anxiety, anger, frustration, fear, wickedness, lust for sex, money, fame, power, progeny, to name a few. In summary, this brings sorrow (*dukkha*) in the long run, due to the afflictions in the mind. However, there is a way out. In this article, we go through some of these aspects and see what is a way out of them. Here, I would like to make a note, some material in this article have been written after personal experiences through deep meditations, while other material are references from Buddha's teachings.

Further, in a preprint, titled - **Anapana (observing the flow of natural breath) & establishing in the present moment**, available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/v562c>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i have mentioned about the how anapana might help in the removing the patterns and miseries of mind. To maintain the flow of this work, i here briefly quote the abstract of my preprint as follows -

Anapana or the observation of the flow of the natural breath, is a fundamental step, before entering the field of *Vipassana*, as the Buddha imparted. In this article, over a small period of 10 years of practice of *Anapana* (and still continuing), with intermittent failures of inability to sit through the meditations, i document my personal observations based on what little was reflected in the STILLNESS OF AWARENESS during these meditations. Note, that the experiences are personal and the reader is advised not to start looking for and developing craving for such experiences. However, the contents of the article can give a glimpse of what happens when *Anapana* is practised over a long period of time. Further, i cannot give you a tangible proof of what has been experienced in the mind-body complex after a practice spread over a long period of time and the best way to test the veracity of *Anapana*, is by self/personal practice. In the Dhajagga Paritta Chant from ? (under [Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0](#)), the following is quoted - *Pali : Svakkhato bhagavata dhammo, Sanditthiko akaliko ehipassiko,*

Opanayiko paccattam veditabbo vinnuhiti (English : The Dhamma is well-expounded by the Blessed One, to be seen here and now, timeless, inviting all to come and see, pertinent, to be seen by the observant for themselves).

Further, in a preprint, titled - **Chapter # 1 : Watch the river flow in the stillness of awareness • Technical details of Anapana and Vipassana**, available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/tgw2c>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i have mentioned about the technical details of how to practice Anapana and Vipassana. To maintain the flow of this work, i here briefly quote the abstract of my preprint as follows -

Anapana or the observation of the flow of the natural breath, is a fundamental step, before entering the field of *Vipassana*, as the Buddha imparted. These methods have existed and with stood the test of time for past 2600 years, since the passing of the Buddha. In this article, i document steps to practice the Anapana and Vipassana meditations, which i had the opportunity to practice and observe in my own mind-body complex. As the meditations continued, i was able to grasp of the few issues and have it up in the form of steps. Explanations of these steps are separately mentioned on my webpages @ [Link to Anapana process](#) and [Link to Vipassana process](#), respectively. However, here i have consolidated the contents of the two webpages and have also added slightly additional information, necessary to go through the details. In my limited grasp, i think these might be helpful for those who wish to practice at home, also. IT HAS BEEN HEARD : In the Dhajagga Paritta Chant from ? (under [Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0](#)), the following is quoted - *Pali : Svakkhato bhagavata dhammo, Sanditthiko akaliko ehipassiko, Opanayiko paccattam veditabbo vinnuhiti* (English : The Dhamma is well-expounded by the Blessed One, to be seen here and now, timeless, inviting all to come and see, pertinent, to be seen by the observant for themselves).

Based on this practice which incorporates Anapana and Vipassana, mainly chittanupaschayana, lead to practice of mindfulness!

4.5 The basis of the study by the authors . . .

The authors state this in their work on Page 1240, column 1, 3rd paragraph, quoted here for ease -

In Buddhism, conceptually, mindfulness and recognition of interconnectedness are part of the eightfold paths wherein each path mutually supports one another to relieve people from suffering through promotion of nonattaching attitudes with reference to Bhikkhu Bodhi (2010), titled - *The noble eightfold path: The way to the end of suffering*. However, empirical research has yet to investigate and compare the effect of both mindfulness and interconnectedness on well - being promotion through nonattachment.

Taking this as a hypothesis, as a theoretical resemblance of interconnectedness and mindfulness in terms of their mechanism on well-being promotion, the authors purport that investigation on the relationship between interconnectedness, nonattachment, and mindfulness, might enable one to understand the potential value of interconnectedness in the mindfulness literature. Further, they claim that it facilitates to replicate previous findings on the mediating role of nonattachment in relationship between mindfulness and well-being, to examine the underlying mechanism of interconnectedness on wellbeing promotion, and to empirically investigate and compare the theoretical significance of mindfulness and interconnectedness on well-being promotion through nonattachment.

4.6 The experiments by the authors . . .

In summary, their work describes the construction and validation of the Interconnectedness Scale and showcases initial evidence to support the incremental value of interconnectedness over mindfulness and nonattachment through 3 studies, namely -

- Study # 1 includes the construction of scale items and establishment of its factor structure through principal component analyses and confirmatory factor analyses.
- Study # 2 examined the construct validity of the Interconnectedness Scale via investigation of its associations with various indicators related to psychological distress, individual well-being, secularized Buddhist-derived concepts and social justice ideologies. In this study, they hypothesized that interconnectedness would (+ / -)tively correlate with variables related to individual well-being, social justice ideologies, and Buddhist-derived concepts / with psychological distress, respectively.
- Study # 3 investigates the incremental value of interconnectedness to both mindfulness and nonattachment on various types of well-being included in study 2. Further, they attempted to find whether nonattachment was a possible mediator of both mindfulness and interconnectedness in the promotion of individual well-being and social justices' ideologies as well as the reduction of psychological distress.

4.7 The results of the experiments by the authors . . .

In short, the results can be summarized as follows, in the author's words -

- Interconnectedness Scale had good psychometric properties and showed correlations with variables representing individual and social justice ideologies and psychological distress in the expected directions
- Mindfulness and interconnectedness might promote individual well-being and social justices' ideologies and reduce psychological distress through nonattachment
- Incremental value of interconnectedness over nonattachment and mindfulness, especially on social justice ideologies, highlighting the potential contribution of interconnectedness to the Buddhist psychology literature.
- Consistent with their hypotheses, the authors found that people who had higher levels of interconnectedness experienced better individual well-being, less psychological distress, and to be more willing to endorse social justice ideologies in studies 2 and 3.

- In their 3rd study, their results highlighted that nonattachment is a possible mechanism of both interconnectedness and mindfulness in the promotion of individual well-being and social justice ideologies and the reduction of psychological distress. Further, they provide references which indicate that their results replicated existing studies and consolidated the evidence that nonattachment mediated the effect of mindfulness on well-being and supported that nonattachment can be beneficial to the promotion of other-focused concern.
- provided new evidence that mindfulness could be beneficial to the promotion of social justices' ideologies through facilitation of nonattachment and supported their hypothesis that interconnectedness might be able to promote social equality through nonattaching from one's sense of self.
- highlighted the potential of both mindfulness and interconnectedness in promoting social equality.

5 Something on . . . Cause

5.1 word 'Cause' in

the English-Pali Dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989), *appears @ 4 different places* -

- **Cause** (/ less / lessly / way) kāraṇa; niḍāna; ṭhāna. hetu, paccaya; janeti; uppādeti; kārapeti; ussukkāpeti, janita; uppādita; kārita; ussukkāpeti. / ahetuka; heturahita; appatitṭha / ahetukam; appatitṭham / ussāpita-magga, padikavedikā
- **Causing** (/ attachment / disunion / injury / remorse) samuṭṭhāpaka / ratikara; madanīya / bhedakara / veyyābādhika / upatāpaka
- **Causat** (ion / ive / tive verb) hetuvāda; janakatta; phaluppādana / hetubhūta; samuppādaka; (in grammar :) hevatthaka / hetvatthakriyā
- **Causal** (/ ity / ly) hetusambhūta; paccayāyatta / sahetukatā / hetusoṭṭhānaso

5.2 Cause, in . . . Mahānidānasutta (The Great Discourse on Causation), Dīgha Nikāya 15

- **Pali** : 'Vedanāpaccayā taṅhā'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaeyena vedītabbam, yathā vedanāpaccayā taṅhā. **English** : 'Feeling is a condition for craving' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.
- **Pali** : Vedanā ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabba.m kassaci kimhici, seyyathidam - **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no feeling for anyone anywhere.
- **Pali** : cakkhusamphassajā vedanā sotāsamphassajā vedanā ghānasamphassajā vedanā jivhāsamphassajā vedanā kāyasamphassajā vedanā manosamphassajā vedanā, sabbaso vedanāya asati vedanānirodhā api nu kho taṅhā paññāyethā'ti? **English** : That is, feeling born of contact through the eye, ear, nose, tongue, body, and mind. When there's no feeling at all, with the cessation of feeling, would craving still be found?"

- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante". **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, ese va hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo taṇhāya, ya-didaṃ vedanā. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of craving, namely feeling.
- **Pali** : *Iti kho panetaṃ, ānanda, vedanaṃ paṭicca taṇhā, taṇhaṃ paṭicca pariyesanā, pariye-sanaṃ paṭicca lābho, lābhaṃ paṭicca vinicchayo, vinicchayaṃ paṭicca chandarāgo, chan-darāgaṃ paṭicca ajjhosānaṃ, ajjhosānaṃ paṭicca pariggaho, pariggahaṃ paṭicca maccha-riyaṃ, macchariyaṃ paṭicca ārakkho.* **English** : So it is, Ānanda, that feeling is a **cause** of craving. Craving is a **cause** of seeking. Seeking is a **cause** of gaining material things. Gaining material things is a **cause** of evaluation. Evaluation is a **cause** of desire and lust. Desire and lust is a **cause** of attachment. Attachment is a **cause** of ownership. Ownership is a **cause** of stinginess. Stinginess is a **cause** of safeguarding.
- **Pali** : *Ārakkhādhikaraṇaṃ daṇḍādānasatthādānalahaviggahavivādatuvaṃtuvaṃpesuññamusāvādā aneke pāpakā akusalā dhammā sambhavanti.* **English** : Owing to safeguarding, many bad, unskillful things come to be: taking up the rod and the sword, quarrels, arguments, and disputes, accusations, divisive speech, and lies.
- **Pali** : *'Ārakkhādhikaraṇaṃ daṇḍādānasatthādānalahaviggahavivādatuvaṃtuvaṃpesuññamusāvādā aneke pāpakā akusalā dhammā sambhavanti'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṃyena veditabbaṃ, yathā ārakkhādhikaraṇaṃ daṇḍādānasatthādānalahaviggahavivādatuvaṃtuvaṃpesuññam aneke pāpakā akusalā dhammā sambhavanti.* **English** : 'Owing to safeguarding, many bad, unskillful things come to be: taking up the rod and the sword, quarrels, arguments, and dis-putes, accusations, divisive speech, and lies' - that's what I said. And this is a way to under-stand how this is so.
- **Pali** : *Ārakkho ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, sabbaso ārakkhe asati ārakkhanirodhā api nu kho daṇḍādānasatthādānalahaviggahavivādatuvaṃtuvaṃpesuññam aneke pāpakā akusalā dhammā sambhaveyyun'ti?* **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no safeguarding for anyone anywhere. When there's no safeguarding at all, with the cessation of safeguarding, would those many bad, unskillful things still come to be?"
- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante". **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, ese va hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo daṇḍādānasatthādānalahaviggahavivādatuvaṃtuvaṃpesuññam anekesaṃ pāpakānaṃ akusalānaṃ dhammānaṃ sambhavāya yadidaṃ ārakkho. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason for the origination of those many bad, unskillful things, namely safeguarding.
- **Pali** : *'Macchariyaṃ paṭicca ārakkho'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṃyena veditabbaṃ, yathā macchariyaṃ paṭicca ārakkho.* **English** : 'Stinginess is a **cause** of safeguarding' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.
- **Pali** : *Macchariyaṃ ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, sabbaso macchariye asati maccharyanirodhā api nu kho ārakkho paññāyethā'ti?* **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no stinginess for anyone anywhere. When there's no stinginess at all, with the cessation of stinginess, would safeguarding still be found?"

- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante". **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, eveda hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo ārakkhassa, yadidaṃ macchariyaṃ. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of safeguarding, namely stinginess.
- **Pali** : 'Pariggahaṃ paṭicca macchariyaṃ'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṃyena veditaṃbham, yathā pariggahaṃ paṭicca macchariyaṃ. **English** : 'Ownership is a **cause** of stinginess' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.
- **Pali** : Pariggaho ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, sabbaso pariggahe asati pariggahanirodhā api nu kho macchariyaṃ paññāyethā'ti? **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no ownership for anyone anywhere. When there's no ownership at all, with the cessation of ownership, would stinginess still be found?"
- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante" **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, eveda hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo macchariyassa, yadidaṃ pariggaho. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of stinginess, namely ownership.
- **Pali** : 'Ajjhosānaṃ paṭicca pariggaho'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṃyena veditaṃbham, yathā ajjhosānaṃ paṭicca pariggaho. **English** : 'Attachment is a **cause** of ownership' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.
- **Pali** : Ajjhosānaṃ hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, sabbaso ajjhosāne asati ajjhosānanirodhā api nu kho pariggaho paññāyethā'ti? **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no attachment for anyone anywhere. When there's no attachment at all, with the cessation of attachment, would ownership still be found?"
- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante". **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, eveda hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo pariggahassa - yadidaṃ ajjhosānaṃ. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of ownership, namely attachment.
- **Pali** : 'Chandarāgaṃ paṭicca ajjhosānaṃ'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṃyena veditaṃbham, yathā chandarāgaṃ paṭicca ajjhosānaṃ. **English** : 'Desire and lust is a **cause** of attachment' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.
- **Pali** : Chandarāgo ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, sabbaso chandarāge asati chandarāganirodhā api nu kho ajjhosānaṃ paññāyethā'ti? **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no desire and lust for anyone anywhere. When there's no desire and lust at all, with the cessation of desire and lust, would attachment still be found?"
- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante". **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, eveda hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo ajjhosānassa, yadidaṃ chandarāgo. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of attachment, namely desire and lust.

- **Pali** : 'Vinicchayaṃ paṭicca chandarāgo'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṇena vedītabbāṃ, yathā vicchayaṃ paṭicca chandarāgo. **English** : Evaluation is a **cause** of desire and lust' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.
- **Pali** : *Vinicchayo ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, sabbaso vicchaye asati vicchayanīrodhā api nu kho chandarāgo paññāyethā'ti?* **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no evaluation for anyone anywhere. When there's no evaluation at all, with the cessation of evaluation, would desire and lust still be found?"
- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante". **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, ese va hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo chandarāgassa, yadidaṃ vicchayo. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of desire and lust, namely evaluation.
- **Pali** : 'Lābham paṭicca vicchayo'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṇena vedītabbāṃ, yathā lābham paṭicca vicchayo. **English** : 'Gaining material things is a **cause** of evaluation' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.
- **Pali** : *Lābho ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, sabbaso lābhe asati lābhanīrodhā api nu kho vicchayo paññāyethā'ti?* **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no gaining of material things for anyone anywhere. When there's no gaining of material things at all, with the cessation of gaining material things, would evaluation still be found?"
- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante". **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, ese va hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo vicchayassa, yadidaṃ lābho. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of evaluation, namely the gaining of material things.
- **Pali** : 'Pariyesanaṃ paṭicca lābho'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṇena vedītabbāṃ, yathā pariyesanaṃ paṭicca lābho. **English** : 'Seeking is a **cause** of gaining material things' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.
- **Pali** : *Pariyesanā ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, sabbaso pariyesanāya asati pariyesanānīrodhā api nu kho lābho paññāyethā'ti?* **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no seeking for anyone anywhere. When there's no seeking at all, with the cessation of seeking, would the gaining of material things still be found?"
- **Pali** : "No hetam, bhante". **English** : "No, sir."
- **Pali** : "Tasmātihānanda, ese va hetu etaṃ nidānaṃ esa samudayo esa paccayo lābhassa, yadidaṃ pariyesanā. **English** : "That's why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of gaining material things, namely seeking.
- **Pali** : 'Taṇham paṭicca pariyesanā'ti iti kho panetaṃ vuttaṃ, tadānanda, imināpetam pariyaṇena vedītabbāṃ, yathā taṇham paṭicca pariyesanā. **English** : 'Craving is a **cause** of seeking' - that's what I said. And this is a way to understand how this is so.

- **Pali** : *Tañhā ca hi, ānanda, nābhavissa sabbena sabbam sabbathā sabbam kassaci kimhici, seyyathidaṃ* - **English** : Suppose there were totally and utterly no craving for anyone anywhere.
- **Pali** : *kāmatañhā bhavatañhā vibhavatañhā, sabbaso tañhāya asati tañhānirodhā api nu kho pariyesanā paññāyethā”ti?* **English** : That is, craving for sensual pleasures, craving for continued existence, and craving to end existence. When there’s no craving at all, with the cessation of craving, would seeking still be found?”
- **Pali** : *”No hetam, bhante”.* **English** : ”No, sir.”
- **Pali** : *”Tasmātihānanda, eseva hetu etaṃ nidānam esa samudayo esa paccayo pariyesanāya, yadidaṃ tañhā.* **English** : ”That’s why this is the **cause**, source, origin, and reason of seeking, namely craving.
- **Pali** : *Iti kho, ānanda, ime dve dhammā dvayena vedanāya ekasamosaraṇā bhavanti.* **English** : And so, Ānanda, these two things are united by the two aspects of feeling.

6 The response/counter article by Theravādin school trained and ordained Bhikkhu Anālayo, of Amarapura-Rāmañña Nikaya sect, in Anālayo (2021b) and its correction in Anālayo (2021a)

6.1 Before we begin . . .

Bhikkhu Anālayo, according to his [Wikipedia page link](#) (Wikipedia contributors (2025a)), temporarily ordained in 1990 in Thailand, after a meditation retreat at Wat Suan Mokkh, the monastery established by the influential 20th-century Thai monk **Ajahn Buddhadasa** and later in 1995, took pabbajja again under **Balangoda Ananda Maitreya Thero**. In 2007, he received his upasampada in the Sri Lankan Shwegyin Nikaya (belonging to the main Amarapura Nikaya), with **Pemasiri Thera** of Sumathipala Aranya as his ordination acariya. Further, **Bhikkhu Bodhi** has been Bhikkhu Anālayo’s main mentor in the study of the Pāli discourses. He has retired from long term service from being a professor of the Numata Centre for Buddhist Studies at the University of Hamburg and is the co-founder of the Āgama Research Group, a resident scholar at the Barre Center for Buddhist Studies and a member of the Numata Centre for Buddhist Studies at the University of Hamburg.

This published manuscript, appeared on November 25, 2020, in the Mindfulness journal by Springer-Nature and APPEARs to be a response/counter article to what has been published in the above by Yu et al. (2020), which appeared in the same journal on February 14, 2020. Down the line, a correction appeared in Anālayo (2021a), on August 2, 2021, which shifted the published manuscript from - published Online First without Open Access TO Open Choice and to make the article an Open Access publication under the terms of the CC-BY 4.0 Attribution International License available @ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Further, **in the acknowledgement section of this work, Bhikkhu Anālayo**, pays indebtedness to the author Yu et al. (2020), and **Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā**.

Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā, according to [Link on Bodhi College](#), went forth as a monastic in the Theravāda Buddhist tradition of Sri Lanka in 2012 and has been the co-founder (with Bhikkhu Anālayo) and director of the Āgama Research Group (established in 2012) and serves as an associate

research professor in the Department of Buddhist Studies of the Dharma Drum Institute of Liberal Arts in Taiwan. Further, she is currently a visiting professor for Buddhist Studies at the University of California at Berkeley and in 2024 Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā was appointed as a registered Buddhist minister with the Italian government through the Italian Buddhist Union.

6.2 My limited grasp on the subject . . .

Based on my few meditation periods and what i have read through Anālayo (2021b), and whatever limited could be grasped in awareness, here i present my limited views in a few words, on the exposition of Bhikkhu Anālayo. So, lets begin . . .

6.3 The abstract by the author . . .

In his abstract, Anālayo (2021b), with correction in Anālayo (2021a), the author states the following -

The Buddhist teaching on dependent arising (or dependent origination) concerns specific conditions whose presence is indispensable for something to come into existence. In the early stages of Buddhist history, the overarching concern of this doctrine was to identify the specific causes responsible for the human predicament, with a view to bringing about their cessation so as to become liberated. In later times, Buddhist exegesis developed various perspectives on causality, where in Huayan philosophy in particular the notion of interconnectedness or interdependence arose, according to which all phenomena relate to each other in one way or another. Despite its traction in the contemporary setting, this notion needs to be recognized as a later development that is by no means identical with the basic Buddhist teaching on dependent arising.

The author talks about **dependent arising or dependent origination of the Buddha's teachings** and **points to the development of the notion of interconnectedness or interdependence, as a perspective of causality, attributed to the later Chinese Huayan Buddhist school**, the starting point which is the considered most elevated, extravagant, lengthy scripture, the **Flower Ornament Sutra**, or **Avatamsaka Sutra** in Indian Sanskrit (Avatamsaka is translated as **Huayan in Chinese**, and read as **Kegon in Japanese**) or the more technical **Buddhāvataṃsaka-nāma-mahā-vaipulya-sūtra**.

According to Van Norden and Jones (2024), on Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, it records the following - Through the fusion of the ideas of the **Avatamsaka Sutra** and **Awakening of Faith in Mahayana**, **Huayan Buddhism developed a distinctive interpretation of the concepts of "emptiness" and "no-self"**. The **original Indian Buddhist view** that there are no selves **transformed into the Chinese Buddhist view** that there is no individual self, but there is a sort of transpersonal self (One Mind) of which all the transient and ontologically interdependent aspects of reality are parts. Dushun held the posthumous honor of being known as the first patriarch of the Huayan School and was active as a monk during the **Sui (581-618)** and early **Tang (618-907)** dynasties. He authored only a handful of texts, the chief among these was **Discernments of the Dharmadhatu of Avatamsaka**, works of which are interspread in several commentaries, one of which is the first english translations of **Buddhāvataṃsaka-nāma-mahā-vaipulya-sūtra**, were

presented by Cleary (1984), under the title - **The Flower Ornament Scripture: A Translation of the Avatamsaka Sūtra.**

Now, based on the claims made by Anālayo (2021b), that this notion of causality needs to be recognized as a later development, i.e. the Huayan philosophy in particular, . . . in which the notion of interconnectedness or interdependence arose, . . . is by no means identical with the basic Buddhist teaching on dependent arising, . . . if we look at the Pali wordings of cause, in section 5 above . . . in Mahānidānasutta (The Great Discourse on Causation), Dīgha Nikāya 15, am NOT sure what the Buddha is trying to convey when he uses the word 'cause' multiple times ? ? ? Further, if we tally the dates of Sui (581-618) and early Tang (618-907) dynasties, these appear WAY after what the Buddha taught, approximately 2600 years ago!

6.4 The paper begins with . . .

the evaluation of a recent investigation by Yu et al. (2020), who took up in particular the Buddhist DOCTRINE of causality, which, Anālayo (2021b) considers to be of relevance to mindfulness practices, HOWEVER, he points the problem with this laudable endeavor is an APPARENT CONFLATION, of perspectives on this doctrine that arose at quite different times in the history of Buddhism.

Now according to Oxford University English language dictionary, DOCTRINE is a belief or set of beliefs held and taught by a Church, political party, or other group.

As has been recorded in multiple instances in the title - **The Jātaka or stories of the Buddha's former births : 6 Volumes**, by Cowell et al. (1895-1907), The Buddha himself follows the principle of questioning by enquiry - **Is it true?**, as that was the basis of investigating into the nature of truth, which the Buddha was always after. Even after Siddhartha became the Buddha, he kept on hammering this question of enquiry to whomever arrived to him. **Is it true?**

This line of investigating into the nature of truth, in the right manner, in my limited perspective, destroys the very basis of belief's or a set of beliefs, especially political or religious ones, that are taught and accepted by a particular group or DOCTRINE. Now, if one searches the Pali dictionary, the word DOCTRINE has a different meaning, @ several citations than, the belief or set of beliefs, especially political or religious ones, that are taught and accepted by a particular group.

Now according to Oxford University English language dictionary, CONFLATION, is the merging of two or more sets of information, texts, ideas, etc. into one, (often in error).

This CONFLATION, Anālayo (2021b) uses, by citing the work of Yu et al. (2020), via quoting an extract from the latter on Page1239, as an exemplification.

6.4.1 My limited grasp on ⊕ interconnectedness or interdependence, the idea that everything depends on everything else . . .

Anālayo (2021b), on Page 1095, column 1, paragraph 3, states -

Other parts of the above quote, however, reflect the notion of interconnectedness or interdependence, the idea that everything depends on everything else. This idea stands behind the notion that "the arising of all matters is conditioned on the arising of one another" and "all matters are mutually influencing one another and co-arising dependently." Contrary to the impression created by the authors, such

Each wave says something,
but the water is silent

Figure 1: Pictorial representation of waves on an ocean surface!

notions are quite different from what the quote from the Cūḷasakuludāyī-sutta refers to and also from what the example of the apple tree illustrates. The growth of the apple tree does not dependent on "all matters"; it only requires a set of specific conditions. Take the computer used to write this article. Although indispensable for such writing, it is of no relevance to the growth of an apple tree.

If i may, with a different analogy, let us look at this figure in 1. On the surface of the ocean, each wave appears different. To the human eye, it is NOT possible to see each an every wave. HOWEVER, the emergence of one wave or its awareness, on the surface of ocean, is interconnected or interdependent, on the all other waves, whether visible or invisible! Each wave says something SPECIFIC, . . . in the VICINITY of waves, . . . WHICH is a SET of SPECIFIC CONDITIONS (so to speak, as per Cūḷasakuludāyī Sutta, by Anālayo (2021b)), . . . HOWEVER, if one considers the OCEAN, IN TOTALITY, . . . the ELEMENT water, . . . of the ocean, is the same in all waves and . . . it is BY the same ELEMENT water of the ocean, that is EXPRESSED in different waves and is INTERCONNECTED and INTERDEPENDENT!

It is the life, that is INTERCONNECTED and INTERDEPENDENT, through and through in existence! Life does not move/go anywhere . . . only the configuration of the Cosmos, changes every fraction of a second (if that i take that depth of measurement!) So, in the next fraction, there is an entire change in the configuration of the Cosmos. One moment after another, this configuration changes, as it is impermanent (annica), in Mother Nature! Now, if you

look deeper, you might say birth happened or death happened. Life went out of the body or life entered the body! But if you shift your perspective, then life within you NEVER moved an inch! Only the configuration of Cosmos changed and the encasing of a physical body arose to encapsulate that life, which you think is encapsulated! During moments of death, the physical body will die OR there is a change in the configuration of the Cosmos, in which the current body just drops away as and the next moment, the configuration of the Cosmos has changed!

The principle / tattva of life IS . . . It exists in absolute truth of shunyata and is a part of the absolute truth! Life in you never came and never went anywhere! That is why the Buddha said - There is no coming and there is no going! (as has been recorded in Laṅkāvatāra Sutra! (see - link to Wikipedia page by Wikipedia contributors (2025b) and link to page on no-coming / going / striving in Laṅkāvatāra) available under GNU General Public License v2 @ Opensource). It is only the configuration of Cosmos that is changing and changing and changing . . . that is impermanent or annica! Just this awareness, that "i am life itself . . ." is enough, to start with! Whether you take birth or not is different matter! Just sit still and be! In the stillness of awareness . . . let Mother Nature unfold as it is . . . for you! Advanced stages, the Buddha dropped the principle / tattava of life itself and merged back in the absolute of shunyata . . . that is parinirvana!

In this above context, is it possible to see this these (following) words of Yu et al. (2020) on Page 1239? -

Take the growth of an apple tree as an example, simply having a seed cannot bear fruit to an apple tree. It must have the right conditions of suitable climate, adequate sunshine, moisture, and nutrients from the soil in order to grow and bear fruit (the configuration of the cosmos changes, however the interconnectedness/interdependence remains). Any condition missing or not in the appropriate amount may lead to a different outcome (but, one can only see what is in the vicinity, MAY BE, due to ONE'S own UNEVOLVED STATE!). Interconnectedness can be operationally defined as an awareness that the existence of all phenomena in the world is the result of the fulfillment of different causes and conditions, in which no entity can sustain independently without relying on other factors. The insight of interconnectedness, originating from the concept of dependent origination, lays the foundation of other Buddhist teachings in understanding the causes of suffering and ways to eradicate suffering.

6.4.2 My limited grasp on "interconnectedness" or "interdependence" reflects a mature stage in the evolution of Mahāyāna thought . . .

Further, *Anālayo (2021b), on Page 1095, column 1, paragraph 5*, states -

The notion of "interconnectedness" or "interdependence," in contrast to specific conditionality, reflects a mature stage in the evolution of Mahāyāna thought, arisen in particular in relation to teachings in the Buddhavaṃśa. Interconnectedness is definitely not "a central tenet underlying all Buddhist teachings." Moreover, another suggestion by Yu et al. (p. 1240) that "in Buddhism, conceptually, mindfulness and recognition of interconnectedness are part of the eightfold paths [sic]" is unfortunately wrong. Only mindfulness is part of the eightfold path, being its seventh factor.

Regarding, **The notion of "interconnectedness" or "interdependence,"** in contrast to specific conditionality, . . . i have already mentioned in section 6.3, about the Buddha's teachings on causality which is referenced in section 5, which is easy to grasp and build upon, and further, i have shared my limited insights on interconnectedness / interdependence in section 6.4.

Regarding, **reflects a mature stage in the evolution of Mahāyāna thought, arisen in particular in relation to teachings in the Buddhavataṃsaka** . . . **i firmly and politely disagree with such statements!** First of all, according to Anālayo (2021b), this phrase **Mahāyāna thought**, only depicts that one has compartmentalized the events or phenomena, into just thoughts or in the limited framework of mind! At one level, it might be true, however, there is knowledge and happenings in existence, which are beyond the comprehension of ordinary human mind! So for example, there are advanced stages in meditation, where there is experiential knowledge of void/emptiness, in which for a period of time, depending on the intensity of meditations and the purity/refineness of one's awareness, one observes first the cleaning of the mind and then over a long period of sustained meditation, there are times when one's own mind dissolves. That dissolution of mind, even if for a few moments, when it happens, the knowledge or the happenings beyond the limited mind is revealed! Now this is experiential knowledge! So, suppose, one asks the Buddha - you say Nirvana has happened! What is the proof? Then it is not possible to speak in words something that is unspeakable off!

So lets take the words of the Buddha in Netti, Paṭiniddesavāra, Vibhaṅga 11, Paññattihāravibhaṅga, which states the following -

Atthi, bhikkhave, ajātaṃ abhūtaṃ akataṃ asaṅkhatāṃ, no cetaṃ, bhikkhave, abhaviṣṣa ajātaṃ abhūtaṃ akataṃ asaṅkhatāṃ. Nayidha jātaṃ bhūtaṃ katassa saṅkhatassa nissaraṇaṃ paññāyetha. Yasmā ca kho, bhikkhave, atthi ajātaṃ abhūtaṃ akataṃ asaṅkhatāṃ, tasmā jātaṃ bhūtaṃ katassa saṅkhatassa nissaraṇaṃ paññāyati"ti.

There is an unborn, unoriginated, uncreated, and unformed . . . If there was not this unborn, this unoriginated, this uncreated, this unformed . . . Freedom from the world of the born, the originated, the created, the formed, would not be possible . . . But since there is an unborn, unoriginated, uncreated, and unformed . . . Therefore is freedom possible from the world, of the born, the originated, the created and the formed!

Given this statement by the Buddha, is it possible for one as a beginner (say, or with some years of meditation experience) on the journey to experience the truth behind these words? Ok! one reads through and contemplate and think about it and do all mental and intellectual gymnastics, write TOP quality research papers and defeat everybody intellectually . . . However, does one have the experiential knowledge of the truth that is hidden behind those words of the Buddha? This one has to introspect and evaluate oneself, in front of a Teacher called Buddha! I think one's own personal evaluation also matters in these cases, instead of writing tones of research papers on such subjects, without any experiential knowledge! However, one is free to continue on mental gymnastics in eternity to come! There is no end to it in existence . . .

Also regarding this phrase mature stage in the evolution of Mahāyāna thought points to certain lack of awareness in what is documented in Anālayo (2021b), probably. Am not sure if Bhikkhu Anālayo is aware of the following, but still for completeness, will share - A brief diversion from the topic!

First of all, Mahāyāna as thought is vastly different from Mahāyāna as action! As a proof of this, let us consider one of the lives of the Buddha, when he was unawakened and it has been recorded in Pali also regarding this **act of Mahāyāna INSTEAD of thought of Mahāyāna** -

Matsumura (2010), extended her previously abridged article Matsumura (2008), to give an extensive detail of the range of Pali scriptures available, that narrate the life of Sumedha, the hermit. Briefly, in reference to Sumedhakathā, she provides a list of Pali texts i.e (1) Buddhavaṃsa (2) Buddhavaṃsa-atthakathā (3) Jātaka Nidānakathā (4) Apadānaṭṭhakathā (5) Atthasālinī, or Dhammasaṅgani-aṭṭhakathā (6) Cariyāpitaka-aṭṭhakathā (7) Dhammapadaṭṭhakathā (8) Mahābodhivaṃsa (9) Thūpavaṃsa (10) Jinacarita and (11) Jinālaṅkāra, that she has explored in her research work. Readers are requested to go through Matsumura (2010), initially to get a bird's eye view of one of the Jataka, that is the life of Sumedha, before delving into deeper research work!

Extending on this work, I have drafted a preprint titled - **From hermit Sumedha to Siddhartha • The journey of a thousand li commenced with a single step : 千里之行始于足下- 老子, Lao Tzu : • A journey of four incalculable aeons plus a hundred thousand aeons** available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/g8bdc>.

Below is the abstract of this work which depicts the act of Buddha, when he was Hermit Sumedha, which talks of Mahāyāna ACT INSTEAD of Mahāyāna THOUGHT, which the Sumedha executed, AS A SACRIFICE to save many. One can have PROFOUND Mahāyāna THOUGHT with NO ACTION also, HOWEVER, it is vastly different from Mahāyāna ACT, when time and situation demands!

Hermit Sumedha seeing the ground was muddy, laid down and spread his long, matted hair on the ground to create a human bridge for the Buddha Dīpaṅkara and his monks, to walk on without getting dirty. In response to this selfless act, Dīpaṅkara Buddha prophesied that Sumedha would become a Buddha in a future age, known as Gautama Buddha (Shakyamuni). Inspired by the Dīpaṅkara Buddha's words, Sumedha vowed to become a Buddha for the sake of all beings. When you are ready in existence, then some will appear from the realms of the absolute truth of shunyata to tell you, that you are the one who will deliver the job! This is evaluation in the dimensions of the absolute truth and not love . . .

It was for the sake of others; he didn't have the desire to be a Buddha, initially! Do you see the intention of the pure heart? That purity in the heart of Sumedha . . . Not a speck of defilement was there, for something personal! Not even for personal glorification! For the sake of others, he made a sacrifice, of choosing to walk approximately four incalculable aeons plus a hundred thousand aeons, when he could have crossed over alone . . . while in front of Dīpaṅkara Buddha!

The Sakyamuni Buddha, approximately 2600 years ago, made a sacrifice for existence almost four incalculable aeons plus a hundred thousand aeons ago! Do you see the sacrifice? Do you see the long journey? Or do you only see the final culmination of the fully liberated and perfected one, from Siddhartha to Buddha, who in his final life, in just one life, in the final moments, renounced everything and merged back into the absolute truth of shunyata . . .

The pure heart, the intention, the will, the courage and the follow through, during that period of approximately four incalculable aeons plus a hundred thousand aeons! From hermit Sumedha to Siddhartha!

Next, I reproduce here, a section of my work in the Chapter 1 of the book titled - **Rummaging the teachings of Jetsun Milarepa : From a ruthless murderer to an enlightened master** in Sinha (2025), as follows (Note : The book titled "The Life of Milarepa" by Lhalungpa (1977)

under the sections, JaiGyan: Bharat Ek Khoj and Public Library of India (Public Resource) at [Archive link to book through CC0 1.0 Universal](#), was used to compose this work/book!)-

The understanding of the Hīna & Maha - yana

From this point, progressively ascending the Path, it is necessary to observe one's vows as carefully as one guards one's eyes. Even in failure, remedies must be employed. By not seeking one's own liberation on the path of the Lesser Vehicle, one develops Bodhichitta (enlightened mind), which seeks to work toward the liberation of all sentient beings. It is my understanding that the development of an enlightened attitude leads one to rededicate, for the good of all, the fruit of one's action, born of love and compassion. In order to embrace the path of the Greater Vehicle, one abandons the path of the Lesser Vehicle. Based upon the foundation of perfect seeing, he enters the supreme path of Vajrayana.

AS ONE PROGRESSES ON THE PATH, ONE HAS TO BE VIGILANT. THIS VIGILANCE IS NECESSARY TO PROTECT ONESELF AS WELL AS THOSE WHO ARE IN COMPANY. ON FAILURE REMEDY NEEDS TO BE EMPLOYED. IT IS NOT THAT IF ONE FAILS, IT IS THE END. IF ONE FALLS, ONE HAS TO GET UP! NOW A CLARIFICATION NEEDS TO BE MADE REGARDING THE LESSER VEHICLE OR THE HINAYANA SCHOOL OF BUDDHISM AND THE GREATER VEHICLE MAHAYANA SCHOOL OF BUDDHISM. FIRST OF ALL, IRRESPECTIVE OF ALL SCHOOLS THAT ENCOMPASS ONE ASPECT OF THE BUDDHA'S TEACHINGS OR THE OTHER, THE ANAPANA AND VIPASSANA MEDITATIONS ARE FUNDAMENTAL AND ROCK FOUNDATIONS OF THE BUDDHA'S TEACHINGS. THE THERAVADA SCHOOL HAS PRESERVED AND PRACTICED IT. THE SO CALLED AND WORLD FAMOUS MAHAYANA SCHOOL AND ITS VARIANTS OR FLAVOURS HAVE THE FOUNDATIONS OF THE SAMATHA AND VIPASSANA MEDITATION THAT WAS TRANSFERRED FROM INDIA TO TIBET, VIA THE INDIAN BUDDHIST MONK KAMALASILA, WHO WAS INVITED IN THE PERIOD C 700 TO 800, BY THE THEN KING OF TIBET. THE TEACHINGS OF KAMALASILA IS RECORDED IN THE TEXT BHAVANAKRAMA OF KAMALASILA (SEE TRANSLATION BY SHARMA (1997)). EVEN MILAREPA HIMSELF, HAMMERED THROUGH MOST OF HIS LIFE AS A RECLUSE, WHILE MEDITATING IN CAVES OF THE HIMALAYAS. THUS HE HIMSELF PRACTICED IN THE HINAYANA STYLE AND ONCE HE HAD ACHIEVED LIBERATION, HE SLOWLY STARTED SHARING HIS KNOWLEDGE TO THOSE WHO CROSSED HIS PATH. IT IS ALL STEP BY STEP. EVEN THE BUDDHA, IN THE JATAKA (SEE TRANSLATION BY COWELL ET AL. (1895-1907)) LIVED MANY LIVES AS AN ASCETIC AND PRACTISED. WHEN SIDDHARTHA WAS A KNOWN PERSONALITY IN SOME LIVES, HE WOULD TEACH AND SHARE WHATEVER HE HAD WITH LOVE AND COMPASSION FOR MANY. SO IT IS NOT POSSIBLE TO SAY IF ONE IS JUST PRACTISING THE HINAYANA OR MAHAYANA, EXCLUSIVELY.

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by T.W. Rhys Davids and William Swede OR the link to online Pali dictionary at University of Chicago at <https://dsal.uchicago.edu/dictionaries/pali/> -

- **Hīna** [pp. of jahati] 1. inferior, low; poor, miserable; vile, base, abject, contemptible, despicable Vin i.10; D i.82, 98; S ii.154 (hīnaṃ dhātuṃ paṭicca uppajjati hīnā saññā); iii.47; iv.88, 309 (citta h. duggata); D iii.106, 111 sq., 215 (dhātu); A ii.154; iii.349 sq.; v.59 sq.; Sn 799, 903 sq.; Nd1 48, 103, 107, 146; J ii.6; Pv iv.127 (opp. paṇīta); Vv 2413 (=lāmaka VvA 116); Dhs 1025; DhsA 45; Miln 288; Vism 13; DhA iii.163. - Often opposed to ukkaṭṭha (exalted,

decent, noble), e. g. Vin iv.6; J i.20, 22; iii.218; VbhA 410; or in graduated sequence *hīna* (>*majjhima*); *paṇīta* (i. e. low, medium, excellent), e. g. Vism 11, 85 sq., 424, 473. See *majjhima*. - 2. deprived of, wanting, lacking Sn 725= It 106 (*ceto-vimutti*^o); Pug 35. - *hīnāya āvattati* to turn to the lower, to give up orders, return to secular life Vin i.17; S ii.231; iv.191; Ud 21; A iii.393 sq.; M i.460; Sn p. 92; Pug 66; *hīnāya vattati id.* J i.276; *hīnāy'āvatta* one who returns to the world M i.460, 462; S ii.50; iv.103; Nd1 147. - *âdhimutta* having low inclinations J iii.87; Pug 26; °*ika id.* S ii.157; It 70. - *kāya inferior assembly VvA 298* (here meaning Yamaloka); PvA 5. - *jacca* low-born, low-caste J ii.5; iii.452; v.19, 257. - *vāda* one whose doctrine is defective Sn 827; Nd1 167. - *virīya* lacking in energy It 116; DhA i.75; ii.260.

- **Maha** (m. & nt.) [fr. mah, see mahati & cp. Vedic nt. mahas] 1. worthiness, venerableness Miln 357. - 2. a (religious) festival (in honour of a Saint, as an act of worship) Mhvs 33, 26 (*vihārassa mahamhi*, loc.); VvA 170 (*thūpe ca mahe kate*), 200 (id.). *mahā*^o a great festival Mhvs 5, 94. *bodhi*^o festival of the Bo tree J iv.229. *vihāra*^o festival held on the building of a monastery J i.94; VvA 188. *hatthi*^o a festival called the elephant f. J iv.95.

FROM A GREATER PERSPECTIVE, LETS SEE THIS. **HĪNA** OFCOURSE MEANS LOW OR BASE, HOWEVER, THE PRACTICE IN SECLUSION IS THE FOUNDATION STONE, WHICH MILAREPA HIMSELF PRACTICES. ONCE HE HAD CROSSED THE STAGE OF LIBERATION, AT WHATEVER LEVEL, HE STARTED SHARING HIS KNOWLEDGE, THUS CONVERGING TO **MAHA**. **Regarding active life that might prove beneficial to other beings**, Milarepa himself says on page 171 -

If there is no attachment to selfish aims, you can. But that is difficult. Those who are full of worldly desires can do nothing to help others. They do not even profit themselves. It is as if a man, carried away by a torrent, pretended to save others. Nobody can do anything for sentient beings without first attaining transcendent insight into Reality. Like the blind leading the blind, one would risk being carried away by desires. Because space is limitless and sentient beings innumerable, you will always have a chance to help others when you become capable of doing so. Until then, cultivate the aspiration toward Complete Enlightenment by loving others more than yourselves while practicing the Dharma. Dress in rags, and content yourselves with little food, clothing, and recognition. Discipline your body and be mindful of your spiritual goal. This should be done for the sake of all sentient beings. To guide you on this path, remember these words.

FOOLS SAY, THIS SCHOOL IS BETTER THAN THAT SCHOOL! THERE IS NO HIGH OR LOW, NO SUPERIOR OR INFERIOR OR EQUAL. ALL ARE INTERCONNECTED AND CO-EXIST SPONTANEOUSLY. **FOR EXAMPLE**, IF YOU SEE THE MOUNTAIN SUMMIT AND THE VIEW OF THE VALLEY BELOW, BOTH THE SUMMIT AND THE THALWEG OR TALWEG OR THE BOTTOM OF THE VALLEY ARE CONNECTED, THOUGH THE PERCEPTION SAYS THAT THIS IS HIGH AND THIS IS LOW.

6.4.3 My limited grasp on ☹ Instance of blatant omission of fact/reference, as was originally quoted by Yu et al. (2020) . . .

Apropos this "another suggestion by Yu et al. (p. 1240) that "in Buddhism, conceptually, mindfulness and recognition of interconnectedness are part of the eightfold paths [sic]", statement by Anālayo (2021b) on Page 1095, column 1, paragraph 5, Bhikkhu Anālayo, **DOESNOT or BLATANTLY REFUSES to MENTION the FACT that, he has OMITTED the FULL SENTENCE by Yu et al. (2020) on Page 1240, column 1, paragraph 3, BY CUTTING IT SHORT and adding his [sic]**, which states the following -

In Buddhism, conceptually, mindfulness and recognition of interconnectedness are part of the eightfold paths wherein each path mutually supports one another to relieve people from suffering through promotion of nonattaching attitudes (Bodhi 2010). However, empirical research has yet to investigate and compare the effect of both mindfulness and interconnectedness on well-being promotion through nonattachment.

To further add to this point, **this statement by Yu et al. (2020), is made with a reference to Bhikkhu Bodhi (2010)'s work titled - The noble eightfold path: The way to the end of suffering and Bhikkhu Bodhi happen(s/ed) to be Bhikkhu Anālayo's main mentor in the study of the Pali discourses. Is it not true?**

Further, in Volume 1 of the Buddhist Monastic code by Bhikkhu (2013), on Page 29, Bhikkhu Thanissaro discusses about the offences and states that in analyzing offenses in relation to determine the penalties as its degrees, the Vibhāṅga divides an action into five factors: the **effort**, the **perception** under which it is made, the **intention** motivating it, the **object** at which it is aimed, and the **result**. **Apropos, this factor of intention, possibly, Bhikkhu Anālayo, himself along with Bhikkhuni Dhammadinnā, might want to ask themselves about the intention behind this BLATANT OMISSION of reference of Bhikkhu Bodhi (2010)'s work and CUTTING/CLIPPING the FULL SENTENCE by Yu et al. (2020) on Page 1240, column 1, paragraph 3 ? ? ?** Also, speaking of omissions, there is a this one text which is quite profound in Mahayana thought and while going through this renowned advanced text, titled - **Mahamudra: The Moonlight - Quintessence of Mind and Meditation** by Lhalungpa et al. (2006), on the mahayana and vajrayana meditation methods in Tibetan Buddhist teachings, **foreword by Jetsun Jamphel Ngawang Lob-sang Yeshe Tenzin Gyatso**, one finds that in the list of sources cited at the back of the book, **there is reference of Bhavanakrama (of Kamalashila i.e Sharma (1997)), which talks about samatha and vipassana in detail, as a means in the spiritual journey, however, the original teachings of the vipassana meditation as recorded in the Theraveda, in Sattipatthana Sutta is missing . . . ! Why is it so?**

6.4.4 My limited grasp on ☹ "in Buddhism, conceptually, mindfulness and recognition of interconnectedness are part of the eightfold paths [sic]" is unfortunately wrong. Only mindfulness is part of the eightfold path, being its seventh factor . . .

Regarding the *statement by Anālayo (2021b) on Page 1095, column 1, paragraph 5 and continued in column 2, states that "in Buddhism, conceptually, mindfulness and recognition of interconnectedness are part of the eightfold paths [sic]" is unfortunately wrong. Only mindfulness is part of the eightfold path, being its seventh factor . . .*

Lets hold on first, and see what the components of eightfold path or ariya aṭṭhaṅgika magga is -

1. sammā-diṭṭhi or right view/understanding!
2. sammā-saṅkappa or right resolve/determination!
3. sammā-vācā or right speech!
4. sammā-kammanta or right action!
5. sammā-ājīva or right livelihood!
6. sammā-vāyāma or right effort!
7. sammā-sati or right mindfulness!
8. sammā-samādhi or right unification of mind!

Now each of the components of the eightfold path or ariya aṭṭhaṅgika magga, i.e view/understanding (diṭṭhi), resolve (saṅkappa), speech (vācā), action (kammanta), livelihood (ājīva), effort (vāyāma), mindfulness (sati) and unification of mind (samādhi), requires this human body (kaya), to begin with! Further, with the human body is the mind (chitta)!

From a holistic point of view, on simple observation, one finds, that to have right view/understanding, the mind should be working properly, along with the right resolve/determination. Further, in day to day activities, one need to use one's faculty of speech via the vocal cord and mouth to have right speech, when needed. Also, these day to day activities would require right action, which would inturn mean that the entire human body (kaya), will/must be working synergistically with all parts of the human body working in tandem (NOT that legs are working but hands are NOT working or everything is working but heart has stopped beating and doing its job). Added to this, is that to have right livelihood, the above all must be working in tandem that is view/understanding, resolve/determination, speech and action, which will require the right amount of effort on one's part! Finally, if work/activity of daily life is to be executed properly, to a fair amount of one's heart's satisfaction, then right mindfulness is as requisite! For all this, the most effective is to have right unification of mind, which can be obtained via regular meditation practices, daily!

Now, if i consider this simple scenario of day to day basic activity of this human body of mine, from eating to walking to working to talking to seeing something to listening to somebody, everything this is working in tandem, together and in synergy, though each part or faculty of the body might have different functions, which are getting executed simultaneously. **Then, is it not interconnectedness of mind and body that is working in synergy in the first place, through which the eightfold path or ariya aṭṭhaṅgika magga can be walked through or worked out, over years of practice? Is it not through this mindfulness that i have recognised the interconnectedness of the different aspects of human mind-body complex to take the next step of working for eightfold path or ariya aṭṭhaṅgika magga? This is so simple . . . !**

Am not sure if this rings a bell to Bhikkhu Anālayo, regarding interconnectedness/interdependence in existence in relation to one's own human body? One is breathing, while eating and sound from nearby is hitting the ear drums, all working synergistically, while the mind is in full coordination through the brain, via interconnectedness/interdependence?

How come one can't see such a simple thing and state that it is unfortunately wrong and only mindfulness is part of the eightfold path, being its seventh factor? Everything works in synergy in existence and it depends on which level of granularity one wants to see things, as they are (ie. yatha-bhuta), given the elucidation in figure 1!

6.5 Other observations - - - My limited grasp on . . .

6.5.1 ☉ As a foundation for proper research . . .

Further, *Anālayo (2021b), on Page 1095, column 2, paragraph 2*, states -

As a foundation for proper research, it is important that the operationalized concepts are clearly defined and that a conflation between divergent ideas is avoided. The praiseworthy wish to enrich the empirical investigation of Buddhist-derived constructs on well-being in a secularized manner needs to be grounded in a proper understanding of the relevant Buddhist concepts. In this way, an operational definition for research can be formulated in such a manner that it accurately reflects these concepts, rather than conflating quite different ideas. The following exploration is meant to provide a historical background for such proper understanding.

Given the limited insights i have presented hitherto, Anālayo (2021b), in my limited grasp, **goes on rattling down like a high velocity bullet train without breaks, making one technical blunder after another, and finally ends up asking/demanding for a foundation for research work to eliminate conflation between divergent ideas. For this, the wish or expectation from the rest is to grasp the relevant Buddhist concepts, grounded in proper understanding, for further experimental research, while Bhikkhu Anālayo himself doesn't grasp the basics of the teachings of the Buddha, in my limited view!** (If i follow the thread of limited insights i have while going through Anālayo (2021b)). Finally, for this, Anālayo (2021b) gives an exploration of historical background to develop proper understanding for experimental research work on the teachings of the Buddha.

6.5.2 ☉ imasmim̐ (a)sati . . . & its connection with 12 nidāna w.r.t Specific Conditionality . . .

In, *Anālayo (2021b), on Page 1095-1096, column 2 and 1, respectively*, , states -

This type of presentation often leads over to an exposition of the conditioned arising and ceasing of 12 links, to be taken up in more detail below.

The notion that specific conditionality can have such a general range of applicability, however, has been challenged by Shulman (2008, p. 299), proposing that dependent-origination addresses the workings of the mind alone . . . Viewing pratītya-samutpāda [dependent origination] as a description of the nature of reality in general means investing the words of the earlier teachings with meanings derived from later Buddhist discourse. This results in a misrepresentation of much of what early Buddhism was about.

Shulman (2008, p. 307) supported his position with the following argument, based

on the Pāli discourses:

When the Buddha says "When this is, that is, etc.," he is speaking only of mental conditioning, and is saying absolutely nothing about existence per se. The most significant evidence for this fact is that the phrase "imasmim̐ sati idaṃ hoti . . ." never occurs detached from the articulation of the 12 links, save one occurrence.

The one occurrence referred to by him is the Cūḷasakuludāyi-sutta (MN 79), already mentioned above, where the formula supposedly "involves a discussion regarding recollection of past lives, an issue closely related to what the 12 links are about."

i have not read through the complete article of Shulman (2008, p. 307) which Anālayo (2021b) cites as a case to build his point on the one occurrence of Cūḷasakuludāyi-sutta (MN 79), however, here are a few of the findings in just a few of the suttas that i was able to dig up . . .

First of all, regarding imasmim̐ (a)sati . . . which speaks only of mental conditioning, and is saying absolutely nothing about existence per se, as per Shulman (2008, p. 307); in section 3.2 above, there is reference of imasmim̐ (a)sati . . . , in the context of its application to kaya (body), cittaṃ (mind), mano (sentience) and viññāṇaṃ. Now, imasmim̐ (a)sati . . . can be applied at 4 different levels, i.e kaya (body), cittaṃ (mind), mano (sentience) and viññāṇaṃ.

Next, irrespective of the species that is present on the planet, WHETHER THEY HAVE THE FACULTY to GRASP the TEACHINGS OR NOT (say, a bird or a four legged one or a tree), each have kaya (body) or the more subtle rūpa (form), and when there is kaya (body) or the more subtle rūpa (form), there will be vedana (sensations), which will be perceived (i.e saññāya) in the due course of time, which might lead to generation of a range of impressions (i.e saṅkhārā) that later propels one to take action in the flow of consciousness (or viññāṇa), developed in its own right and degree, biologically, in Mother nature.

Further, in section 3.2 above, the word mano (sentience) which means the ability to experience and feel sensations, HOLDS TRUE for ALL SENTIENT BEINGS in existence! Given that, MAY BE, the Buddha already gave the HINT that imasmim̐ (a)sati . . . applied to ALL SENTIENT BEINGS in existence, in Mother nature and if i consider figure 1, i can infer that the WAVES in an ocean, can be DIFFERENT SENTIENT BEINGS, in DIFFERENT BODIES (depending on where life enters in which species).

Also, of importance, in section 3.4, this reference of the five lines, starting from the second one, it points to the Buddha stressing on the fact of ISNESS (i.e iti), ORIGIN (samudayo) and DISSOLUTION/ENDING (atthaṅgamo), of kaya (body) or the more subtle rūpa (form), vedana (sensations), perception (i.e saññāya), impressions (i.e saṅkhārā) and consciousness (or viññāṇa). Basically these 5 are the Khandha or [Sk. skandha].

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, the word -

- **Khandha** [Sk. skandha] - I. Crude meaning: bulk, massiveness (gross) substance. A. esp. used (a) of an elephant: the bulk of the body, i. e. its back S i.95; vāraṇassa J iii.392; hatthi - khandha - vara - gata on the back of the state elephant J i.325; PvA 75. Also with ref. to an elephant (hatthināga) sañjāta^o "to whom has grown bulk=a large back" Sn 53, expl. SnA 103 by susaṅṭhitakkhandho "well endowed with bulk." - (b) of a person: the shoulder or back: nagaṃ khandhe karitvā S i.115 appl. to Māra; Vism 100; DhA iv.168 (ohita^o - bhāra the

load lifted off his shoulder). - - (c) of a tree: the trunk. rukkhassa PvA 114, also as rukkha° J i.324; tāla° the stem of a palm PvA 56; nigrodhassa khandhaja (see cpds.) S i.207=Sn 272; mūlaṃ atikkamma kh° ṃ sāraṃ pariyesitabbaṃ "one must go beyond the root and search the trunk for sweetness" S iv.94. - (d) as t.t. in exegetical literature: section, chapter, lit. material as collected into uniform bulk; freq. in postscripts to Texts and Commentaries. See also khandhaka. - B. More general as denoting bulk (-°); e. g. aggi° a great mass of fire M ii.34, 41; J iv.139; udaka° a mass of water (i. e. ocean) A iii.336; S iv.179; J i.324; PvA 62; puñña° a great accumulation of merit A iii.336=S v.400; bhoga° a store of wealth A v.84; J i.6; maṇi° an extraordinarily large jewel (possessing magic power) J ii.102 sq. - II. Applied meaning. - A. (-°) the body of, a collection of, mass, or parts of; in collective sense "all that is comprised under"; forming the substance of. - (a) dukkha° all that is comprised under "dukkha," all that goes to make up or forms the substance, the idea of "ill." Most prominent in phrase kevalassa dukkhakhandhassa samudaya and nirodha (the origin & destruction of all that is suffering) with ref. to the paṭiccasamuppāda, the chain of causal existence (q. v.) Vin i.1; S ii.95; iii.14; A i.177; v. 184 & passim. Similarly: samudaya Vbh 135 sq. nirodha Nett 64; antakiriya A i.147; vyādhimaraṇatunnānaṃ dukkhakkhandhaṃ vyapānudi Th 2, 162. - (b) lobha° dosa° moha° the three ingredients or integrations of greed, suffering and bewilderment, lit. "the big bulk or mass of greed" (see also under padāleti), S v.88 (nibbijjhati through the satta bojjangā). - (c) vayo° a division of age, part of age, as threefold: purima°, majjhima°, pacchima° Nd2 in def. of sadā. - (d) sīla (etc.) kh° the 3 (or 5) groups or parts which constitute the factors of right living (dhamma), viz. (1) sīla° the group dealing with the practice of morality; (2) samādhi° that dealing with the development of concentration; (3) paññā° that dealing with the development of true wisdom. They are also known under the terms of sīla - sampadā, citta°, paññā° D i.172 sq.; see sīla. - D i.206; Nett 64 sq.; 126. tīhi dhammehi samannāgato "possessed of the three qualities," viz. sīla - khandhesu, etc. It 51; cp. A i.291; v.326. tīhi khandhehi . . . aṭṭhangiko maggo sangahito M i.301; sīlakkhandhaṃ, etc. paripūreti "to fulfil the sīla - group" A i.125; ii.20, iii.15 sq. These 3 are completed to a set of 5 by (4) vimutti° the group dealing with the attainment of emancipation and (5) vimutti - ñāṇa - dassana° the group dealing with the realization of the achievement of emancipation. As 1 - 4 only at D iii.229 (misprint puñña for paññā); cp. A i.125. As 5 at S i.99=A i.162; S v.162; A iii.134, 271; v.16 (all loc.=S i.99); It 107, 108; Nd2 under sīla. B. (absolute) in individual sense: constituent element, factor, substantiality. More especially as khandhā (pl.) the elements or substrata of sensory existence, sensorial aggregates which condition the appearance of life in any form. Their character according to quality and value of life and body is evanescent, fraught with ills & leading to rebirth. Paraphrased by Bdhgh. as rāsi, heap, e. g. Asl. 141; Vibh A 1 f.; cf. B. Psy. 42. 1. Unspecified. They are usually enumerated in the foll. stereotyped set of 5: rūpa° (material qualities), vedanā (feeling), saññā (perception), sankhārā (coefficients of consciousness), viññāṇa (consciousness). For further ref. see rūpa; cp. also Mrs. Rh. D. Dhs trsl. pp. 40 - 56. They are enumerated in a different order at S i.112, viz. rūpaṃ vedayitaṃ saññaṃ viññāṇaṃ yaṃ ca sankhataṃ n' eso 'ham asmi. Detailed discussions as to their nature see e. g. S iii.101 (=Vbh 1 - 61); S iii.47; iii.86. As being comprised in each of the dhātus, viz. kāma° rūpa° arūpa - dhātu Vbh 404 sq. (a) As factors of existence (cp. bhava). Their rôle as such is illustrated by the famous simile: "yathā hi angasambhārā hoti saddo ratho iti evaṃ khandhesu santesu hoti satto ti sammuti" "just as it is by the condition precedent of the co - existence of its various parts, that the word G chariot ' is used, just so it

is that when the skandhas are there, we talk of a G being ” (Rh. D.) (cp. Hardy, Man. Buddh. p. 425) S i.135=Miln 28. Their connotation ”khandha” is discussed at S iii.101 =M iii.16: ”kittāvatā nu kho khandhānaṃ khandhādhivacanaṃ? rūpaṃ (etc.) atītānāgatapaccuppannaṃ ajjhataṃ vā bahiddhā vā oḷārikaṃ,” etc.: i.e. material qualities are equivalent terms for the kh. What causes the manifestation of each kh.? cattāro mahābhūtā . . . paccayo rūpa - khandhassa paññāpanāya; phasso . . . vedana°, saññā°, sankhārā°, etc.; nā- marūpaṃ . . . viññāṇa°: the material elements are the cause of rūpa, touch is that of vedanā, saññā, sankhārā, name and shape that of viññāṇa (S iii.101); cp. M i.138 sq., 234 sq. On the same principle rests their division in: rūpa - kāyo rūpakkhando nāmakāyo cattāro arūpino khandhā ”the material body forms the material factor (of existence), the individualized body the 4 immaterial factors” Nett 41; the rūpakkhanda only is kāmādhātu - pariyāpanno: Vbh 409; the 4 arūpino kh° discussed at Ps ii.74, also at Vbh 230, 407 sq. (grouped with what is apariyāpanna) -Being the ”substantial” factors of existence, birth & death depend on the khandhas. They appear in every new conjuncture of individuality concerning their function in this paṭisandhi - kkhāṇe; see Ps ii.72 - 76. Thus the var. phases of life in transmigration are defined as - (jāti:) ya tesam tesam sattānaṃ tamhi tamhi satta - nikāye jāti sañjāti okkanti abhinibbatti khandhānaṃ pātubhāvo ā yatanānaṃ paṭilābho Nd2 on Sn 1052; cp. jāti dvī—hi khandhehi sangahitā ti VvA 29; khandhānaṃ pā-tubhāvo jāti S ii.3; Nett 29; khandhānaṃ nibbatti jāti Vism 199. - (maraṇaṃ:) yā tesam tesam sattānaṃ . . . cuti cavanatā bhedo antaradhānaṃ maccu maraṇaṃ kālakiriya khandhānaṃ bhedo kalevarassa nikkhepo M i.49=Vbh 137=S ii.3, 42. - vivatta - kkhanda (adj.) one whose khandhas have revolved (passed away), i. e. dead S i.121=iii.123. - kh°anaṃ udaya - vyaya (or udayabbaya) the rising and passing of the kh., transmigration Dh 374=Th 1, 23, 379=It 120=KhA 82; Ps i.54 sq. - (b) Their relation to attachment and craving (kāma): sattisūlūpamā kāmā khandhānaṃ adhikuttanā S i.128=Th 2, 58, 141 (ThA 65: natthi tesam adhik°?); craving is their cause & soil: hetupaṭicca sambhūtā kh. S i.134; the 4 arūpino kh. are based on lobha, dosa, moha Vbh 208. - (c) their annihilation: the kh. remain as long as the knowledge of their true character is not attained, i. e. of their cause & removal: yaṃ rūpaṃ, etc. . . . n’ etaṃ mama n’ eso ’ham asmi na m’ eso attā ti; evaṃ etaṃ yathābhūtaṃ sammappaññāya passati; evaṃ kho jānato passato . . . ahankāramamankāra - mānānusayā na honṭi ti S iii.103; - pañca - kkhandahe pariññāya S iii.83; pañca - kkhandahe pariññatā tiṭṭhanti chinnaṃ ulkā Th 2, 106. See also S i.134. - (d) their relation to dhātu (the physical elements) and āyatana (the elements of sense - perception) is close, since they are all dependent on sensory experience. The 5 khandhas are frequently mentioned with the 18 dhātuyo & the 12 āyatanāni: khandhā ca dh° cha ca āyatanā ime hetuṃ paṭicca sambhūtā hetubhangā nirujjhare S i.134; kh° - dh° - āyatanāṃ sankhataṃ jātimūlaṃ Th 2, 472; dhammaṃ adesesi khandh’ - āyatana - dhātuyo Th 2, 43 (cp. ThA 49). Enumerated under sabba- dhammā Ps i.101=ii.230; under dhammā (states) Dhs 121, as lokuttara - kkhandahe, etc. Dhs 358, 528, 552. - khandhānaṃ khandhattho abhiññeyyo, dhātūnaṃ dhātuttho, etc. Ps i.17; cp. i.132; ii.121, 157. In def. of kāmāvacarā bhūmi Ps i.83. In def. of dukkha and its recognition Nett 57. In def. of arahanto khīṇāsava Nd2 on sankhāta - dhammā (”kh. sankhātā,” etc.), on tiṇṇa (”khandha - (etc.) pariyante thitā”), & passim. - (e) their valuation & their bearing on the ”soul” - conception is described in the terms of namama (na tumhākaṃ), anattā, aniccaṃ and dukkhaṃ (cp. upādānakkh° infra and rūpa) rūpaṃ (etc.) . . . aniccaṃ, dukkhaṃ, n’ eso ’ham asmi, n’ eso me attā ”material qualities (etc. kh. 2 - 5) are evanescent, bad, I am not this body, this body is not my soul” Vin i.14=S iv.382. n’ eso ’ham asmi na m’ eso attā S i.112;

iii.103, 130 & passim; cp. kāyo na tumhākaṃ (anattā rūpaṃ) S ii.65; Nd2 680; and rūpaṃ na tumhākaṃ S iii.33 M i.140=Nd2 680. - rūpaṃ, etc. as anattā: Vin i.13; S iii.78, 132 - 134; A i.284=ii.171; 202; cp. S iii.101; Vin i.14. - as aniccaṃ: S iii.41, 52, 102, 122, 132 sq., 181 sq., 195 sq., 202 - 224, 227; A iv.147 (aniccānupassī dukkhānupassī); anicca dukkha roga, etc., Ps ii.238 sq.; Vbh 324. - 2. Specified as pañc' upādāna-kkhandhā the factors of the fivefold clinging to existence. Defined & discussed in detail (rūpūpadāna - kkhandha, etc.) S iii.47; 86 - 88; also Vin i.10; S iii.127 sq. Specified S iii.58 iii.100=M iii.16; S iii.114, 158 sq.; v.52, 60; A iv.458; Vism 443 sq. (in ch. xiv: Khandha - niddesa), 611 sq. (judged aniccato, etc.). - Mentioned as a set exemplifying the number 5: Kh iii.; Ps i.22, 122. Enumerated in var. connections S i.112; D iii.233; M i.190; A v.52; Kh iv. (expld KhA 82=A v.52); Miln 12 (var. references concerning the discussion of the kh. in the Abhidhamma). - What is said of the khandhas alone - see above 1 (a) - (e) - is equally applied to them in connection with upādāna. - (a) As regards their origin they are characterized as chandamūlakā "rooted in desire, or in wilful desire" S iii.100; cp. yo kho . . . pañcas' upādānakkhandhesu chandarāgo taṃ tattha upādānaṃ ti M i.300, 511. Therefore the foll. attributes are characteristic: kummo pañcann' etaṃ upād' ānaṃ adhivacanaṃ M i.144; bhārā have pañcakkhā S iii.26; pañcavadhakā paccatthikā pañcann' . . . adhivacanaṃ S iv.174; pañc' upād' . . . sakkāyo vutto M i.299= S iv.259. - (b) their contemplation leads to the recognition of their character as dukkha, anicca, anattā: na kiñci attānaṃ vā attaniyaṃ vā pañcasu upādānakkhandhesu S iii.128; rogato, etc. . . . manasikātabbā pañc' S iii.167; pañcasu upād' esu aniccānupassī "realizing the evanescence in the 5 aggregates of attachment" A v.109; same with udayavyayānupassī S iii.130; A ii.45, 90; iii.32; iv.153; and dhammānupassī M i.61. Out of which realization follows their gradual destruction: pañc' . . . khandhānaṃ samudayo atthangamo assādo, etc. S iii.31, 160 sq.; A ii.45, 90; iv.153; Nd2 under sankhārā. That they occupy a prominent position as determinants of dukkha is evident from their rôle in the exposition of dukkha as the first one of the noble truths: sankhittena pañc' upādānakkhandhā pi dukkhā "in short, the 5 kh. are associated with pain" Vin i.10=M i.48=A i.177=S v.421; Ps i.37, 39; Vbh 101 & passim; cp. katamaṃ dukkham ariyasaccaṃ? pañc' upād' ā tissa vacanīyaṃ, seyyathidaṃ . . . S iii.158=v.425; khandhādisā dukkhā Dh 202 (& expl. DhA iii.261). - 3. Separately mentioned: khandhā as tayo arūpino kh' (ved°, sañña°, sankh°) DhA i.22; viññāṇa - kh' (the skandha of discriminative consciousness) in Def. of manas: manindriyaṃ viññāṇaṃ viññ' - khandhotajjā manoviññāṇadhātu Nd2 on Sn 1142=Dhs 68.

Since the Buddha is pointing to the impermanence of the 5 factors, it is said that the Khandha or [Sk. skandha] are empty by nature. Further, **in the context of the Mahayana, THOUGH I DO NOT REMEMBER correctly which one(s), the Buddha often communicated with Śāriputra regarding being immersed in the state/field of void or emptiness and also gave him instructions/insights related to the state/field of void or emptiness. This has been mentioned in multiple chapters of Paṭisambhidāmagga, in Khuddaka Nikaya of the Sutta Pitaka.**

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, the word -

- **Suññata** (adj.) [i. e. the abl. suññato used as adj. nom.] void, empty, devoid of lusts, evil dispositions, and karma, but especially of soul, ego Th 2, 46; ThA 50; Dhs 344; Mhvs 37, 7; nibbāna DhsA 221; phassa S iv.295; vimokkha Dh 92; DhA ii.172; Miln 413; vimokkha samādhi, and samāpatti Vin iii.92 sq.; iv.25 sq.; samādhi (contemplation of emptiness, see

Cpd. 216) D iii.219 (one of. three samādhis); S iv.360, 363; Miln 337; anupassanā Ps ii.43 sq.

- **Suññatā** (f.) [abstr. fr. suñña] emptiness, "void," unsubstantiality, phenomenality; freedom from lust, ill - will, and dullness, Nibbāna M iii.111; Kvu 232; DhsA 221; Nett 118 sq., 123 sq., 126; Miln 16; Vism 333 (n'atthi; suñña; vivitta; i, e. abhāva, suññatā, vivitt' - ākāra), 578 (12 fold, relating to the Paṭiccasamuppāda), 653 sq.; VbhA 262 (atta°, attaniya°, niccabhāva°). -pakāsana the gospel of emptiness DA i.99, 123; -paṭisaṃyutta relating to the Void, connected with Nibbāna A i.72=iii.107=S ii.267; DA i.100 sq.; Miln 16; -vihāra dwelling in the concept of emptiness Vin ii.304; M iii.104, 294. See on term e. g. Cpd. 69; Kvu trsln 142, n. 4.

This build up of material is actually to point to the Heart Sutra of the Mahayana. In the article titled - **Prajna-Paramita-Hridaya/the Heart Sutra: Bhagavati, the Heart of Transcendental Knowledge** by Sinha (2017), available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/6zpsv>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i would like the readers to go through a section of this work on the emptiness of the skandhas, which i reproduce here for completeness -

T. Yang dey tse jang chub sem pa sem pa chen po pak pa chen re zik, wang chuk she rab kyi pa rol tu chin pa zab moy cho pa nyi la nam par ta zhing pung po nga po de dak la, yang rang zhin gyi tong par nam par tao/ T. And at the same time noble Avalokiteshvara, the bodhisattva-mahasattva, looking at the practice of profound transcendent knowledge, saw that those five *skandhas* are empty by nature.

N. *He looks at the practice of profound transcendent knowledge.* The practice of the way to enter *Samadhi* via meditation on form (i.e using support *alambana*) to meditation without form (i.e formless without support) in order to experience the truth of emptiness, has been stressed upon. He is looking at the practice first. The knowledge is there, but he is looking at the practice first. This is crucial. He is pointing to the fact that the practice is important. Without proper practice, it is not possible to acquire the deep knowledge. The way to acquire knowledge is absolutely essential.

Then, through the experience of the emptiness in heart, the bodhisattva experiences emptiness in *skandhas*. Experience in heart cannot be matched with limited understanding of the mind as they are beyond the mind.

Now, why does the sutta start with skandhas and not any other aspect? A stupid answer is that one has to start somewhere. But jokes apart, the spiritual journey begins with existence of constituents that form an important aspect of a cycle. Here, by experiential knowledge of the heart, the former Buddha acknowledges the existence of the cycle that is crucial for existence of cycle that is crucial for existence of samsara and later on uses the steps in the cycle to experience nirvana. So first there is recognition of existence of cycle through the experiential knowledge and then the cycle is used to unlock this process of repeated births and deaths. He does not say that the cycle is bad. If one notices, Siddhartha as Buddha starts his final journey as Bodhisattva some 534 life times back (as in Jataka Tales) and uses this knowledge of *Samsara* (the inherent cycle), birth after birth to enter *parinirvana*. Again, he is not condemning the cycle. There is an acknowledgement in experience. *If one has not experienced the fundamentals of the nature of the cycle by which things are working in Samsara, then it is not easy to grasp the way to unlock this cycle.*

Q. What are these five skandhas?

Exposition - The five skandhas or aggregates that constitutes the various aspects of samsara or the world i.e the form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental formations (*sankhara*), and consciousness (*vijnana*). There is form or body (*rupa*) and within the form are sensations (*vedana*). The perception (*samjna*) of these sensations exists and repeated perceptions (*samjna*) of the sensations lead to impressions (*sankhara*) in the mind body complex. And in the flow of consciousness (*vijnana*) the impressions (*sankhara*) pushes one to take the next action in order to maintain the cycle. These are fundamental elements which form an integral aspect of a greater cycle of *Samsara*. In a deeper sense Samsara or the world is a projection either dynamic or static and neither dynamic nor static aspects which has the property to veil and superimpose the universal truths regarding life and not allow one to see the way things are (i.e *yatha-bhuta*). There are two kinds of truths, namely - *paramartha* or the absolute truth and the *samvritta* or the relative truths of the world. One finds contradictions in the relative truths but the absolute is beyond the relative. Now this doesn't mean that the relative truths are of no value and *Samsara* is bad. It is *Samsara* which prepares one to transcend into the higher states of truth and leads to *nirvana*. Thus Samsara is a means or a school where one passes one step at a time to finally merge into the absolute. This is a way of expressing in the relative terms but note that the Samsara is connected to nirvana through and through. The goal (*nirvana*) and the way to the goal (in *Samsara*) are here and now as the river and the ocean is connected through and through. *Again, it is important to value the path that is there in this Samsara.*

Now again, there are two aspects of the journey. Mostly one is focused on the goal, but rarely one is focused on the way to the goal. The second is extremely rare case where the journey is more important than the goal. Kamalasila explains in his profound and deep treatise on Bhavanakrama (the steps of meditation) that there are usually two kinds of mindsets in enlightened ones. The first is the *pranidhi-chitta* or the mind fixed on the goal and the second is the *prasthanachitta* or the mind aware of the journey to the goal. This second one is an extremely rare case where a being is more focused on the journey rather than the goal and is referred to as entering the path of *anuttara-samyak-sambodhi*.

So to recapitulate, the five *skandhas* or aggregates, that constitutes the various aspects of samsara or the world are the form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental formations (*sankhara*), and consciousness (*vijnana*). Form (*rupa*) can be any image in any dimension that contains a boundary and gives the perception (*samjna*) of a compounded formation. Perception helps in the cognition of a form (*rupa*) and repeated perceptions of a phenomena or object of perception through sensations (*vedana*) towards the object of perception, in the flow of consciousness (*vijnana*) leads to mental formations (*sankhara*). Thus a cycle is formed. A cycle which leads one from birth to death to birth and so on!

Q. What is the procedure of seeing emptiness?

But before delving deeply into how the cycle works, it is important to know how one sees emptiness in all these five skandhas. Seeing is not through the ordinary eyes. It is through the heart. When the heart experiences and absorbs a knowledge through awareness, then the heart sees through the nature of the object under investigation. Thus the way is simple. It is by letting emptiness come to awareness and dissolving the individuality completely into emptiness. This happens through meditation. *Now one does not create emptiness. Emptiness is not an object of meditation. It is already there but it has not been experienced in the heart.* When the essence of emptiness or *shunyata* is experienced in the heart through meditation (i.e *bhavanamayi-prajna*), one experiences the emptiness

in form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental formations (*sankhara*) and consciousness (*viññana*). A more detailed explanation of experiencing emptiness is given in latter exposition below. That is how one sees emptiness in the *skandhas*. Finally, emptiness cannot be described in words as it is directly connected to the *paramartha* or the absolute truth. Being not connected to the relative truths or *samvritti*, it can only be experienced in heart. Emptiness in heart, leads to emptiness in mind.

Finally, *Anālayo (2021b)*, on Page 1096, column 2, last paragraph, states -

In sum, the suggestion that the principle of specific conditionality can at times have a general relevance appears to be correct rather than being a misrepresentation of early Buddhist thought.

. . . **appears to be correct** . . . Right! Right! It only APPEARS to be CORRECT, after approximately 2600 years! Till this day, everyone on the planet in these 2600 years DID NOT know about this "APPEARS to be CORRECT"! They all had made misrepresentations and we have illumination from Anālayo (2021b)!

This is not to deny that the overarching concern of this early Buddhist teaching is indeed the human predicament. The point is only that its application cannot be confined to the workings of the mind alone.

Well, such comments are NOTHING NEW, and i am NOT AT ALL SURPRISED and THIS IS/WAS EXPECTED from Bhikkhu Anālyo, (as well as Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā who has commented and might have approved this article also), who, in these LONG 30 years of this human life, FROM the time of pabbajjā, have SEARCHED by his own volition, the teachings of the Teacher called Buddha (the fully liberated and enlightened one), has LEARNED from the Teacher, TRAINED from Theravāda monk in ASIA, EARNED his sammā-ājīva, on the teachings of the Teachings of the Buddha, LIVES till this DAY on what the Teacher called Buddha has provided approximately 2600 back, and FINALLY writes about the teachings of a Teacher called Buddha . . . as HUMAN PREDICAMENT! It is like a student who goes to the teacher, learns everything from the teacher, feeds from the hands of the teacher, enjoys on what the teacher has given and then finally BITES the teacher in all ways possible while HUMILIATING the teacher on the planet earth, whoes teachings have withstood the test of time of say approximately 2600 years! ON TOP of it, with MULTIPLE TECHNICAL FLAWS in HIS OWN graspings, that is PUBLISHED officially in the Mindfulness journal, Bhikkhu Anālayo, (and probably Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā) MAKES IT A POINT to PROJECT THEMSELVES as MUCH SUPERIOR than the Teacher called Buddha himself, IN ESTABLISHING the teachings of the Dhamma, while CLAIMING the teachings of the Teacher Buddha as HUMAN PREDICAMENT (or if i may say explicitly . . . embarrassing situation as per one of the english language dictionaries)!

The so called SUPEPRIOR, MATURE, SOPHISTICATED, and ADVANCED LEVEL learning and CULTURE of Bhikkhu Anālayo, (and probably Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā) to CUT the HEAD OF THE Teacher called the BUDDHA (as the teachings are being a HUMAN PREDICAMENT), IN ASIA, TO PROVE his/her SUPERIORITY is IMPECCABLE and MATCHLESS in existence . . . IN FRONT OF what they might have LEARNT from the contributions of RARE GEMS like ADOLF HITLER from Germany, and BENITO MUSSOLINI from Italy! The bloodbath and

atrocities by these two are NOT HUMAN PREDICAMENT BUT the teachings a Teacher called Buddha is HUMAN PREDICAMENT!

Regarding his profound work titled - **Superiority Conceit in Buddhist Traditions** in Analayo (2021), and his LOVE and PENCHANT to RUFFLE SOME FEATHERS, like a SELF APPOINTED COWBOY VIGILANTE, in the Sangha, who considers the teachings of the Buddha also, as HUMAN PREDICAMENT, Bhikkhu Anālayo, has MUCH FAVOUR from his BELOVED Jetsun Jamphel Ngawang Lobsang Yeshe Tenzin Gyatso, who has recently written a FOREWARD for the title - **The Perfection of Wisdom in First Bloom: Relating Early Aṣṭasāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā to āgama Literature** in Analayo (2025).

To ADD CHERRY TO THE CAKE of the highly MATURE and EVOLVED Mahayana thought, in the PRFOUND GRASPING of Bhikkhu Anālayo and some LAMA, would LOVE this valuable Mahayana title - **Buddha's not smiling: uncovering corruption at the heart of Tibetan Buddhism today**, by Curren (2008)

In short, IF NOT, Bhikkhu Anālayo, (and probably Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā), then WHO ELSE . . . ? ? ?

In the words of the Buddha, the Teacher -

*Bahum-pi ce sahitaṃ bhāsamāno,
na takkaro hoti naro pamatto,
gopo va gāvo gaṇayaṃ paresaṃ,
na bhāgavā sāmāññaṃ hoti.*

Even though reciting abundant scriptures,
the heedless fellow, who does not do (what they say),
like a cowboy counting other's cattle,
does not partake of the ascetic life.

– Dhammapada 1.19

*Appam-pi ce sahitaṃ bhāsamāno,
Dhammassa hoti anudhammacārī,
rāgañ-ca dosaṃ-ca pahāya mohaṃ,
sammappajāno suvimuttacitto,
anupādiyāno idha vā hurāṃ vā,
sa bhāgavā sāmāññaṃ hoti.*

Even though reciting but few scriptures,
but living righteously in accordance with Dhamma,
abandoning greed, hate and delusion,
understanding aright, with mind well-released,
that one, unattached here and hereafter,
(surely) partakes of the ascetic life.

– Dhammapada 1.20

6.5.3 ☉ line of reasoning vs occurred to me . . .

In, *Anālayo (2021b)*, on Page 1097, column 1, paragraph 1, states -

The same line of reasoning then led via several intervening links up to ignorance as the initial cause in the series of conditional links that result in the human predicament. This series of links form specific conditions in the sense that their cessation leads to the cessation of the link that depends on them. For the case of old age and death, the relevant passage proceeds as follows:

Monastics, this occurred to me: With what not being do old age and death not exist, with the ceasing of what is there the ceasing of old age and death? Monastics, through wise attention there was a breakthrough by wisdom for me: With birth not being, old age and death do not exist; with the ceasing of birth, there is the ceasing of old age and death.

(SN 12.10: tassa mayham, bhikkhave, etad ahosi: kimhi nu kho asati jarāmaṇaṃ na hoti, kissa nirodhā jarāmaṇanirodho ti? tassa mayham, bhikkhave, yoniso manasikārā ahu paññāya abhisamayo: jātiyā kho asati jarāmaṇaṃ na hoti, jātinirodhā jarāmaṇanirodho ti.

May be, in my limited grasp, this **line of reasoning** is just a **train of thoughts which REQUIRES some mental effort**, which on the contrary, is vastly DIFFERENT from **occurred to me**, as the Buddha said, is a **natural spontaneous happening WITHOUT EFFORT, as he SAT STILL!** It might have HAPPENED, INSTEAD of being FORCED THOUGHT process, as the Buddha says! **Down the line, the Buddha himself states that WITH wise attention a breakthrough AROSE in me . . .**

6.5.4 © penetrative understanding / The basic principle enshrined in this way is hardly a novel discovery. Even animals must be able to recognize / . . .

In, *Anālayo (2021b)*, on Page 1097, column 2, paragraph 1, 2 and 3, states -

*The fact that old age and death are to be expected for one who has been born may at first sight not seem to warrant the qualification of being a penetrative understanding. However, this qualification applies similarly to each ensuing step in the entire investigation, which will eventually lead up to ignorance as the condition whose cessation leads, via the cessation of the other intervening links, to transcending old age and death. In other words, the net result of such **penetrative understanding** is the realization that the human predicament can be transcended by going beyond ignorance.*

The obvious relationship that obtains between birth and death can serve as a convenient exemplification of what specific conditionality implies. It involves identifying what is indispensable for the existence of something else such that, in its absence, the other item is unable to persist or even come into existence. The key aspect here is the cessation mode, as this provides the directive for transcending the human predicament.

The basic principle enshrined in this way is hardly a novel discovery. Even animals must be able to recognize certain specific conditions required for their own survival,

such as where food can be found and how predators can be avoided. The significantly Buddhist perspective on the matter lies in applying this basic principle to the human predicament in the understanding that the entire gamut of subjective experience is merely the result of conditional relationships, with no permanent entity found anywhere in addition to or apart from these.

In paragraph 1, above, apropos **penetrative understanding**, in my limited grasp, understanding is only of the mind! That is still a part of, what they call it in Pali as **Cinta-maya-panna**. It is just some mental gymnastics and nothing else. The mind is still churning and the mind has NOT stopped running! Even with that **penetrative understanding**, one goes on the ride of a deluded monkey! Keep jumping from one branch to other! There is a vast between **penetrative understanding** or **Cinta-maya-panna** and **Bhavana-maya-panna** or the absorption of the knowledge or wisdom in **one's own being or sentience** (i.e in Pali sacetanatta as in English-Pali dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989)). So **the journey is from pariyatti (theory), to patipatti (practice) to pativedha (attainment)**.

May be, for the benefit of the reader, i will reproduce the part of section 1.2.4, below -

Pariyatti or theoretical knowledge - There is a way to read the scriptures that records the teachings of the ancient ones, be it any path. First one meditates. Say you meditated for a 5 days. Then the next two days you pick up a text that you want to acquire knowledge from. After you have read a few pages, then again meditate. In the stillness of awareness and the depths of the meditation the essence of the knowledge written in words might appear in your awareness and your being might absorb that knowledge. This is a long process. There are 3 stages of acquiring knowledge in the higher dimensions of truth & the spiritual realm, i.e - (1) ***Suta-maya-panna or knowledge/wisdom acquired by listening***. Listening can be through any of the senses. (2) ***Cinta-maya-panna or knowledge/wisdom acquired via mental chewing of the knowledge***. As you chew the chewing gum, so also your mind starts chewing the knowledge, yet the knowledge/wisdom is not completely absorbed. (3) Finally, ***Bhavana-maya-panna or knowledge/wisdom is absorbed in your being***. That knowledge settles in your heart also, firmly. So you move from ***pariyatti (theory)***, to ***patipatti (practice)*** to ***pativedha (attainment)***. One has to continue on this whole life, as one meditates, contemplates and reads, again and again and again and . . . **Fools study voraciously to amass as much information as possible, whether it gets digested or not is not the issue, and will vomit it out in front of everyone to show something. Spiritual debates have the characteristics where one party tries to debate with the other and defeat the other party. Not that it is not useful, but whether knowledge has settled in a being is a vastly different matter. It takes long time to grasp the truths from the abstract dimension . . .**

The Buddha himself stressed on the personal experiential knowledge through deep meditations. Even after full liberation, he used to sit and meditate with those who used to learn from him. Those who trained with him, used to meditate and then after sustained period of meditations over a long period of time, they would themselves arrive at the conclusion regarding the truths that the Buddha expounded in words. **There is an incidence in the life of the Buddha. An ascetic came to him and asked - "what is it that you have acquired, please share?" The Buddha said - "Sit with me." And then they both immersed in deep meditation. The experiential knowledge was transmitted between the two just by sitting together in meditation, in silence. After the experience, the ascetic was full of tears of joy for the experience that was shared or transmitted, in silence in deep meditation. Neither the Buddha said a word and nor the ascetic said anything. As if the**

Buddha and the ascetic had aligned in oneness, in existence and what had to be shared was shared, in meditation. Thus, through experiential knowledge one moves and evolves and this is a time taking and natural process. **To hit the point**, in . . .

Poṭṭhilaṭṭheravatthu, Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada, Maggavagga, Pañcasatabhikkhuvattu, it is said -

- **Pali** : *Yogā ve jāyati bhūri*, **English** : From meditation springs wisdom,
- **Pali** : *Etam dvedhāpatham nātvā*, **English** : without meditation, wisdom ends.
- **Pali** : *bhavāya vibhavāya ca*; **English** : Knowing these two paths -
- **Pali** : *Tathāttānam niveseyya*, **English** : of progress and decline -
- **Pali** : *yathā bhūri pavaḍḍhati*. **English** : you should conduct yourself so that wisdom grows.

Further, in the Dīgha Nikāya, Mahāparinibbānasutta, The Great Discourse on the Buddha's Extinguishment, it says -

- **Pali** : *Yo imasmim dhamminaye*, **English** : Whoever meditates diligently,
- **Pali** : *appamatto vihassati*; **English** : in this teaching and training,
- **Pali** : *Pahāya jātisamsāram*, **English** : giving up transmigration through rebirths,
- **Pali** : *dukkhassantaṃ karissati*”ti. **English** : will make an end to suffering.”
- **Pali** : *'ye te, bhante, ahesum atītamaddhānam arahanto sammāsambuddhā, sabbe te bhagavanto pañca nīvaraṇe pahāya cetaso upakkilese paññāya dubbalīkaṇe catūsu satipaṭṭhānesu supatiṭṭhitacittā sattabojjhaṅge yathābhūtaṃ bhāvetvā anuttaraṃ sammāsambodhiṃ abhisambujjhimsu*. **English** : 'All the perfected ones, fully awakened Buddhas - whether past, future, or present - give up the five hindrances, corruptions of the heart that weaken wisdom. Their mind is firmly established in the four kinds of mindfulness meditation. They correctly develop the seven awakening factors. And they wake up to the supreme perfect awakening.'

Moving on, in paragraph 2, above, **the obvious relationship, which is so evident to Anālayo (2021b), is followed by this construct - It involves identifying what is indispensable for the existence of something else such that, in its absence, the other item is unable to persist or even come into existence. Question - By your own experiential knowledge, apart from what the Buddha has already stated, what is your contribution in the identification of this . . .**”indispensable for the existence of something else . . .”, which you have quoted? **The next statement - The key aspect here is the cessation mode**, as this provides the directive for transcending the human predicament. **Question - Think the Buddha already talked about cessation at multiple levels, if i am correct! What is the novel truth that you are expounding when the Buddha has already talked about cessation at various levels?**

Finally, in paragraph 3, above, **the The basic principle enshrined in this way is hardly a novel discovery. Even animals must be able to recognize certain specific conditions required for their own survival**, such as where food can be found and how predators can be avoided. **Bhikkhu Anālayo, i mean really . . . you ARE one SOME LOUSY LOOSE CANNON monk, who will**

NOT STOP SHORT of DEMONSTRATING the UNCULTURED ANIMAL behind those ROBES of yours that YOU ARE, when you WRITE in an INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL like this, stating that there is HARDLY a NOVEL DISCOVERY and what the Teacher Buddha expounded for the lay in simple language, AND COMPARING it (the teachings), with EVEN ANIMALS MUST BE ABLE TO RECOGNIZE certain specific conditions . . . SPEAKS VOLUMES of your ADVANCED level TRAINING and CULTURE over these 30 years as a Theravāda monk! Even your BELOVED Jetsun Jamphel Ngawang Lobsang Yeshe Tenzin Gyatso, who has written the FOREWARD for your new book, SUPPORTS you for COMPARING the teachings, that can be RECOGNIZED by ANIMALS. . . . Right! . . . Right! . . . And for this type of article, YOU ARE WORLD RENOWNED and that WHOLE LOT is engaged in and busy READING such articles by you! Since you have YOURSELF said it . . . - Why DON'T you take a STREET DOG or a SWINE as YOUR TEACHER to START WITH? Forget the Buddha! Take a MAD DOG or a SWINE as your TEACHER and start publishing in SPRINGER-NATURE Mindfulness journal!

The significantly Buddhist perspective on the matter lies in applying this basic principle to the human predicament in the understanding that the entire gamut of subjective experience is merely the result of conditional relationships, with no permanent entity found anywhere in addition to or apart from these. Thought the Buddha already has talked at various stages, about advancing through experiential knowledge of meditations and grasping the principle of impermanence, way before you took birth on this planet in this life time! You DON'T NEED to KEEP on PARROTING, what other people have already said or done, using SOPHISTICATED words/language! DON'T WASTE your time and other's valuable time!

6.5.5 ☉ Mindfulness of sense experience . . .

In, *Anālayo (2021b)*, on Page 1097, column 2, paragraph 1, 2 and 3, states -

An example is contemplation of the sense spheres, found in the Satipatṭhāna-sutta and its Madhyama-āgama parallel (though absent from a third parallel in the Ekottarika-āgama).

Just a RANDOM CHECK on [Wikipedia page on Madhyama Āgama in Wikipedia \(2025\)](#) states that -

Madhyama Āgama (Chinese: 中阿含; pinyin: Zhong Ahan Jing) **is an early Indian Buddhist text, of which currently only a Chinese translation is extant (Taishā Tripiṭaka 26).** The title means "Middle Collection." It is one of the four Āgamas of the Sanskrit Sūtra Piṭaka located in the Chinese Buddhist Canon and contains 222 discourses in 18 chapters. Its Pali equivalent, the Majjhima Nikaya, contains 152 discourses in 15 chapters.

In, *Anālayo (2021b)*, on Page 1099, column 1, paragraph 1, states -

The two parallels agree in applying this description to the other senses, illustrating the situation with the example of two oxen that are bound together by a yoke. Neither of the two oxen is the fetter of the other. Instead, it is the yoke by which they are bound together that constitutes the fetter.

Anālayo (2021b) repeats two sentences, translated from one in Pali, another in Chinese, which mean the same and then provides a third sentence, which also means the same thing!!! **What's the novelty and idea of doing this?**

6.5.6 ☉ Later notions of causality . . .

In, *Anālayo (2021b)*, on Page 1099, column 2, paragraph 1, states -

Cox (1993, p. 134) explained that, with the evolution of Sarvāstivāda exegesis, "abstract causal relations are beginning to be considered for their own sake, and not merely as part of a discussion of dependent origination." Eventually, "with the emergence of an independent and abstract causal theory, dependent origination . . . received its own particularized role, as an explanation of the process of rebirth, completely divorced from general causal theory" (p. 136)..

Just a minor question - If one is aware of Dr. Brian Leslie Weiss, psychiatrist known for Hypnotherapy and Reincarnation research and for his book titled - Many lives, many masters: The true story of a prominent psychiatrist, his young patient, and the past-life therapy that changed both their lives in Weiss (2012) and the documented experiences from the realm beyond the humans(i.e physical bodies), could you Bhikkhu Anālayo and Cox (1993, p. 134) demonstrate if your theoretical writings/publications connects to the experience of Dr Brian Leslie Weiss?

It is as part of the onset of such later developments that in Huayan thought in particular the notion of interconnectedness or interdependence came into its own. Poceski (2004, p. 346) explained:

Huayan's system of religious philosophy and practice is a vast conglomeration of abstruse doctrines. . . at its core is a holistic vision of the universe as a dynamic web of causal interrelationships, in which each and every thing and event is related to everything else as they interpenetrate without any obstruction. The Huayan depiction of reality is an ingenious reworking of the central Buddhist doctrine of pratīyasamutpāda (dependent origination). . . it postulates that each phenomenon is determined by the totality of all phenomena of which it is a part, while the totality is determined by each of the phenomena that comprise it. Therefore, each phenomenon is determining every other phenomenon, while it is also in turn being determined by each and every other phenomenon. All phenomena are thus interdependent. . . every phenomenon conditions the existence of every other phenomenon and vice versa. Accordingly, nothing exists by itself, but requires everything else to be what it truly is..

I never heard and read about Huayan literature till August 2025 and if I look at the depiction of figure 1 and the simple exposition I have shared with my limited grasp, I find Huayan depiction redundant given my personal insight, though I have not presented it in DRY POLEMICS. Also, with all the evidence presented in this article, I think I am happy with what the Buddha taught, way before Huayan depicts. However, this DOES NOT mean, I am CONDEMNING Huayan. Those who want are free to read it, however the Buddha has already aspects of it in his teachings, may be buried deep within, in simple language which even the ordinary can grasp!

McMahan (p. 172 and 178) explained:

Far from a chain of causes and effects binding beings to rebirth in a world of suffering, today's interdependence implies a sacred matrix of mutual communality and coparticipation, the extended body of all beings. And, most significant here, this shift in meaning and valuation developed not only out of the Mahayana tradition's rethinking of Buddhahood and the infusion of East Asian sensibilities into Buddhism but also out of some of the fundamental dynamics of modernity . . . The contemporary Buddhist ethic of interdependence . . . likely worked its way into contemporary Buddhist thought through remnants of the Romantic-Transcendentalist line of thinking that resonated with similar ideas in Huayen [sic] and Zen thought.

Similar TECHNICAL JARGON trying to DISCREDIT the teachings of the Buddha by providing some sophisticated terminology of sacred matrix of mutual communality and coparticipation, while EXTOLLING the Mahayana which found its way later on as the teachings were shared/transferred to Northern ASIA, specially Tibet and GOING ONE STEP FURTHER by promoting 19th Century Romantic-Transcendentalist thought as the ONEs who contributed to the Buddhist ethic of interdependence!

7 For those interested . . . a personal account

Please read through the following webpage on [how meditation helped me scientific & spiritual research.](#)

8 Conclusion

In retrospect, in these negligible 20 years of my journey through meditations and whatever limited i could grasp, i would say that the readers of the article **MUST** evaluate based on personal experiential knowledge of the meditations. **NOT BECAUSE** i have said so! Your personal experiential knowledge in meditation **IN TANDEM** with the (say, here) evaluation of my research work on the teachings of the Buddha, **IS THE REQUIREMENT**, IF interest and time permits. Also, one should be careful of what one is reading and is published in top international journals and evaluate with personal wisdom and insight developed via meditations, continued over long periods of time in one's life!

In this, i will not conclude! Your journey is your own and you need to see if you have benefitted from what has been shared, by any teacher/monk/nun, irrespective of their personal attainments! In short, **JUST DON'T GET MESMERISED!** Your heart will tell you who is what, in the long run and further, **DON'T JUMP** into quick conclusions and get stuck in words! Grasp the essence behind the frequencies of the words that have been used to share the knowledge!

In the end, i would quote here the teachings of the Buddha himself, as follows -

8.1 regarding development of wisdom and meditation . . .

In the Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada, Maggavagga, Pañcasatabhikkhuvatthu, Potṭhilattheravatthu

-

*Yogā ve jāyati bhūri,
ayogā bhūrisaṅkhayo;
Etaṃ dvedhāpathaṃ ñatvā,
bhavāya vibhavāya ca;
Tathāttānaṃ niveseyya,
yathā bhūri pavaḍḍhati.*

From meditation springs wisdom,
without meditation, wisdom ends.
Knowing these two paths -
of progress and decline -
you should conduct yourself
so that wisdom grows.

Further, in the Dīgha Nikāya, Mahāparinibbānasutta, The Great Discourse on the Buddha's Extinction -

*Yo imasmiṃ dhammavinaye,
appamatto vihassati;
Pahāya jātisaṃsāraṃ,
dukkhassantaṃ karissati”ti.*

Whoever meditates diligently,
in this teaching and training,
giving up transmigration through rebirths,
will make an end to suffering.”

8.2 regarding NOT because someone has said so . . .

In the Aṅguttara Nikāya 3.65, Mahāvagga, Kesamuttisutta (With the Kālāmas of Kesamutta), it is said -

Pali : ”Santi, bhante, eke samaṇabrāhmaṇā kesamuttaṃ āgacchanti. **English** : “There are, sir, some ascetics and brahmins who come to.

Pali : *Te sakaṃyeva vādaṃ dīpenti jotenti, parappavādaṃ pana khumsenti vambhenti paribhavanti omakkhim karonti.* **English** : They explain and promote only their own doctrine, while they attack, badmouth, disparage, and smear the doctrines of others.

Pali : *Aparepi, bhante, eke samaṇabrāhmaṇā kesamuttaṃ āgacchanti.* **English** : Then some other ascetics and brahmins come to Kesamutta.

Pali : *Tepi sakaṃyeva vādaṃ dīpenti jotenti, parappavādaṃ pana khumsenti vambhenti paribhavanti omakkhim karonti.* **English** : They too explain and promote only

their own doctrine, while they attack, badmouth, disparage, and smear the doctrines of others.

Pali : *Tesaṃ no, bhante, amhākaṃ hoteva kaṅkhā hoti vicikicchā* : **English** : So, sir, we're doubting and uncertain:

Pali : *'ko su nāma imesaṃ bhavataṃ samaṇabrāhmaṇānaṃ saccaṃ āha, ko musā''ti?*
English : 'I wonder who of these respected ascetics and brahmins speaks the truth, and who speaks falsehood?'

Pali : *'Alañhi vo, kālāmā, kaṅkhitaṃ alaṃ vicikicchitaṃ.* **English** : "It is enough, Kālāmas, for you to be doubting and uncertain.

Pali : *Kaṅkhanīyeva pana vo ṭhāne vicikicchā uppanā.* **English** : Doubt has come up in you about an uncertain matter.

Pali : *Etha tumhe, kālāmā, mā anussavena, mā paramparāya, mā itikirāya, mā piṭakasampadānena, mā takkahetu, mā nayahetu, mā ākāraparivitakkena, mā diṭṭhinijjhānakkhantiyā, mā bhavbarūpatāya, mā samaṇo no garūti.* **English** : Please, Kālāmas, don't go by oral transmission, don't go by lineage, don't go by testament, don't go by canonical authority, don't rely on logic, don't rely on inference, don't go by reasoned train of thought, don't go by the acceptance of a view after deliberation, don't go by the appearance of competence, and don't think 'The ascetic is our respected teacher.'

Pali : *Yadā tumhe, kālāmā, attanāva jāneyyātha:* **English** : But when you know for yourselves:

Pali : *'ime dhammā akusalā, ime dhammā sāvajjā, ime dhammā viññugarahitā, ime dhammā samattā samādinna ahitāya dukkhāya saṃvattantī'ti, atha tumhe, kālāmā, pa-jaheyyātha.* **English** : 'These things are unskillful, blameworthy, criticized by sensible people, and when you undertake them, they lead to harm and suffering', then you should give them up.

Pali : Bhavatu Sabba Mangalam

English : May all beings be happy

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